

Art(s) as an Expanding Social Sculpture

Maria Huhmarniemi & Mirja Hiltunen

Biography

Mirja Hiltunen (DA, MEd) is a professor of Art Education in the Faculty of Art and Design, University of Lapland, Finland. She has devised a performative art strategy and has been leading community-based art education projects over twenty years. The place-specificity, performativity and socially engaged art are particular interests to her. She is a Senior Research Fellow for the AMASS (Acting on the Margins: Arts as Social Sculpture) H2020-funded research project. She has presented numerous international research papers and published her work in art education journals, books and art exhibitions.

Maria Huhmarniemi (DA) is an artist-research-teacher in the University of Lapland, Finland, and Senior Research Fellow for the AMASS (Acting on the Margins: Arts as Social Sculpture) H2020-funded research project. Her post-doctoral research focuses on arts-based methods in environmental conflict mediation, creative tourism and transformative education. She has numerous peer reviewed research publications and she participated group and joint exhibitions as an installation artists and artists-researcher.

The thematic number on Art(s) as Social Sculpture in the Research in Arts Education (RAE) journal focuses on socially engaged art practices and research for using arts to overcome societal challenges. We present and discuss a variety of artistic and arts-based studies and innovative arts-based practices. While the RAE welcomes research papers on all arts disciplines (visual arts, music, dance and other performative arts, their theories, practices and education), this number focuses on socio-political contemporary art and artistic interventions in communities, such as care institutions, villages and educational organisations and networks.

Art(s) as an Expanding Social Sculpture

The call for research articles, practise-based reports and visual essays was based on the project *Acting on the Margins: Arts as a social sculpture (AMASS)* in 2020–2023. The project seeks to analyse, synthesise and promote the role of arts in societal challenges. The University of Lapland, located in Lapland in Finland, leads the research consortium. Local, regional and national research and development projects from different parts of Europe are brought into international discussion in the AMASS project and also in this number of the RAE journal.

The overall objective of the AMASS project is to address societal challenges, such as various forms of exclusion and poverty, while promoting resilience and inclusion in European regions through the strengthening arts and cultural policies for vulnerable groups and peripheral communities. International contemporary art and art education includes interest in socially engaged art, that is, forms of artistic practice that aim for social changes in some specific communities, contexts and locations (Lacy, 1996; Lippard, 1997). In Lapland, socially engaged art and community-based art education have been promoted and researched through some previous projects (Hiltunen, 2009; Hiltunen, et al., 2020; Huhmarniemi, 2021; Huhmarniemi et al., 2021), giving background for the development of AMASS.

Melanie Sarantou, Carolina Gutierrez Novoa, Silvia Remotti and Mira Alhonsuo discuss in the article “More patience and creativity” a design research project in which design practitioners and researchers collaborated to develop training guidelines and a toolset for a stakeholder workshop to be implemented by partner organisations of the AMASS project. The authors explore the team dynamics and approaches to design development within digital environments and present guidelines for teams developing and conducting online workshops in digital environments. The article has lots of relevance for developing international arts and research collaborations at the age of travel restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic and ecological awareness of the climate impact of travelling. Practical tools are needed for collaborations in digital environments. The article responds to some aims of the AMASS research to capture the

Art(s) as an Expanding Social Sculpture

avenues and methods that can be employed to build resilient communities, which are also in the margins.

Milosh Raykov and Raphael Vella discuss ethics reviews in socially engaged arts research. They describe issues that researchers may face when applying for ethical clearance for research projects that engage various communities in participatory activities with artists. Raykov and Vella consider how research goals, artistic outcomes, timeframes, levels of participants' involvement and the overall creative processes may become affected by regulatory procedures. They offer some recommendations for ethical review boards in the evaluation of socially engaged arts research plans and designs. While socially engaged arts research is a rapidly growing field of research, the article by Raykov and Vella has practical importance. The article also helps artists-researchers in recognising and considering the ethical issues of the research.

Ásthildur Jónsdóttir introduces artistic activities aimed at promoting greater ecological consciousness through different forms of participation and awareness activities. The participatory artistic activity Walk the Space created a platform for sharing ideas about sustainability in an academic community. The collaboration provided a space for transformative learning and active engagement, offering the potential for social change. This study by Jónsdóttir provides insights into how artistic actions can strengthen community building and ecological consciousness.

Timo Jokela discusses a socially-engaged environmental art titled Kuer's Journey (2018) created in the Art Äkäslompolo art event. His approach followed an art-based action research strategy to create a dialogic space that promotes decolonisation, cultural revitalisation and community resilience. Jokela uses the concept of Arctic art to reflect encounters with Western contemporary art practices, northern ecocultures and ways of knowing. The article by Jokela is strongly related to the aims of the AMASS research, while the AMASS includes aims to investigate the role of regional and international identities and traditions, and their role within the arts and resilient communities, as well as studies on implementing arts in the mediation of cultural

Art(s) as an Expanding Social Sculpture

and social conflicts. Jokela's study took place in the village of Art Äkäslompolo shadowed by an environmental conflict on the plan for an iron ore mine.

The practice-based paper by Marc Herbst has its background in central Europe, which is being transformed by climate change and recent refugee waves. Herbst presents a rich and inspiring documentation of a playground project and states that arts-based learning can provide a playful way for children, refugee and others to flexibly integrate and relate to each other and describes an artistic researcher's development of the Bauspielplatz Kunst Kammer museum. The essay illustrates one direction for arts as inclusive social sculpture in the 2020s.

More and more artists are collaborating with different sectors of society, such as healthcare institutions. In her visual essay, Niina Oinas reflects on her personal experiences of artistic work and entrepreneurship in Finland. She concludes that to consolidate art in the social and healthcare sectors, clearer structures and standardisations for artists' positions are needed so that the artists have better possibilities to create meaningful and impactful arts in care institutions. The visual essay has a relevance for developing policies for arts in the healthcare sector. Structural changes and good practices are needed for arts and cultural services that promote wellbeing and social coherence.

The visual essay by Nina Luostarinen illustrates the arts-based method for adult plays and the interpretation of visual arts to foster participants' relations to the environment. According to Luostarinen, the art activities that she has developed can lead to participants' increased empathy, emotions and activism. The visual essay effectively demonstrates the participatory method and its' playful strength.

The visual essay by Maria Huhmarniemi examines the expansion of the sense of empathy and community through the means of art education and community art. Huhmarniemi reflects educational socially engaged arts in the context of creative tourism and public art. She concludes that arts strive for openness and empathy through bodily, nonverbal or multilingual

Art(s) as an Expanding Social Sculpture

collaborations. Communality also expands into artist collectives, when artists collaborate with other artists, natural materials and other elements of nature.

Angela Saldanha, Raquel Balsa and Célia Ferreira present a visual essay that portrays a communication experience via postcards in the AMASS project under the social distance restrictions of the COVID-19 pandemic situation in Portugal. The visual essay presents dynamics and possibilities to overcome the limitations of digital communication in disadvantaged communities and arts-based projects.

We hope readers find this thematic number on Art(s) as Social Sculpture inspiring and useful when further developing and researching socially engaged arts and their policies, methods, ethics and impacts. Further, the AMASS project will continue exploring arts and arts-based approaches to enhance dialogue and foster social inclusion and well-being.

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Art(s) as an Expanding Social Sculpture

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More Patience and Creativity: Team Learning in Online Stakeholder Workshop settings

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Biography

Dr Melanie Sarantou is Senior Researcher and Adjunct Professor in Social Design at the University of Lapland in Finland. She currently coordinates the AMASS European Commission H2020-funded project, and participates as Research Fellow in areas of policy development, social design, service design and arts-based research amongst marginalised communities.

Mira Alhonsuo is a design researcher and service designer for multiple service design projects at the University of Lapland. She has examined research cases in digital services, tourism and healthcare services as well as with different companies and organizations. Her research interests include service design methods, empathy, narratives, process visualization, and public service development, especially in the healthcare sector.

Carolina Gutiérrez Novoa is a Chilean design strategist and researcher based in Italy. She currently collaborates with PACO Design Collaborative in Milan, where they address social innovation projects. Her job concerns the application of the design discipline to shape concepts, behaviours, interactions and strategies. Her research interest seeks to make sense and discover the full potential of each subject, which allows her to guide a conscious approach to work, with critical and reflective thinking.

Silvia Remotti is a designer and researcher based in Italy; in 2013 she founded PACO Design Collaborative. Her interest in design for social innovation and design for education started before founding PACO and it has grown over the years.

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

Abstract

This article discusses a design research project in which design practitioners and researchers collaborated to develop training guidelines and a toolset for a stakeholder workshop to be implemented by partner organisations of the Arts on the Margins: Arts as Social Sculpture (AMASS; 2020–2023) project. It focuses on the learning experiences of the design team, which was comprised of four people who created the online environment for the stakeholder workshop. The team members, who are also the authors of this article, were all designers and researchers with varied backgrounds and experiences. The workshop activities were adapted from a face-to-face format to an online environment due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The objectives of the article are to explore the team dynamics, approaches to design development within digital environments. The use of collaborative autoethnography (CAE) and reflection enabled the design team to assess their design processes and learn from critical discussion. The results will present guidelines for teams developing and conducting online workshops in digital environments.

Keywords

Team learning, design research, arts-based methods, digital environments

Introduction

This article seeks to understand how a team of designers engaged in learning through the generation of functional and approachable digital environments, such as online workshops, to enable communication in online policy stakeholder workshops for the purposes of policy

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

making. It explores the design and implementation of online stakeholder workshops in digital environments from the perspective of a design team that consisted of service designers and artist-designers from Italy and Finland. Stakeholder workshops were selected as a tool in policy making as they offer opportunities for engaging in inclusive and open policy making (Kimbell & Bailey, 2017; Kimbell, 2015). During the COVID-19 pandemic, the designers, in their various capacities and roles, tackled the design problems associated with implementing policy roadmap drafting across several project partner countries in Europe.

The objective of the study is to assess their design research process, understand the various roles, skills and capacities of the design team and reflect on their learning that was enabled through their chosen methods. This article asks the following questions: How can the various roles and capacities of a design team contribute to solving design problems related to the development of online toolsets and workshops? How can design research processes be assessed effectively by a design (research) team?

The initial plan was for the project partners to implement face-to-face regional stakeholder workshops in their respective countries to collect data, which would be used to draft practical policy roadmaps for regional and local implementation. However, due to the restrictions and safety considerations associated with the pandemic, travel was limited in 2020. The stakeholders that were identified for the workshops were various organisational representatives and individuals who were involved in the arts and cultural sectors in the partner countries, for example, decision makers, practitioners, educators and community leaders.

The AMASS project investigates how the arts can act as a vehicle for mitigating societal challenges on the margins of Europe. The project spans the margins of Europe: Malta, Portugal, the Czech Republic, Italy, Hungary, the UK, Sweden and Finland. The findings of the European-wide AMASS testbed, which will be implemented in most of these countries and consist of approximately 35 experiments, will be used, alongside design approaches, to deliver policy

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

recommendations on how the arts can mitigate societal challenges. The practical policy work, which implements design research and ABMs, is led by the University of Lapland in Finland and PACO Design Collaborative from Italy. The work is supported by a comparative policy analysis conducted by the University of Borås in Sweden. The analysis was conducted across all eight partner countries and provides a basic theoretical outline for policy action.

The project seeks to create concrete opportunities for bringing together communities and artists to be accompanied through artistic practises, methods and expression in creative projects and interpretations (AMASS, 2020). These communities, and in many cases also the artists, stem from marginalised contexts such as Indigenous and Roma peoples, children and youths, and otherwise marginalised groups, for example immigrants. The project itself is set up on the margins of Europe, from the far north in Finnish Lapland, to Malta, the most southern part in Europe and from the western part of Europe, Portugal is in conversation with Eastern European countries such as Hungary and the Czech Republic. The dilemma AMASS tackles is to investigate the role of the arts in mitigating societal challenges and which will be translated into policy recommendations, is that ‘policy is least answering to the needs of marginalised communities’ (Kimbell & Bailey, 2017, p. 216).

The first cycle of the policy making process of AMASS included the development of the toolset and workshop. The development of the toolset and training guidelines and the practical implementation of the workshop, all had to be converted by the design team from the intended face-to-face formats to online formats. During this cycle the AMASS partners were also trained to use the toolset and stakeholder workshop, to implement stakeholder workshops in their countries. The partners hosted online pilot workshops as part of cycle one to familiarise themselves with the workshop process and use of tools.

The complex design processes involved to develop the online toolset and workshop gave rise to the design research process by the design team who sought to assess this process after

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

the first working cycle of developing the toolset and workshop. The methodological approaches adopted to assess the design research process included CAE and reflexivity. While both of these are qualitative research methods, CAE is also collaborative and autoethnographic (Chang et al., 2016). Lapadat (2017) describes CAE as a multi-vocal approach, whereby several researchers collaborate by interpreting data by discussing personal experiences, knowledge sharing, reflection and interpretation of data. After the first cycle of the process, the same digital environment was then adapted and used by the AMASS partners to implement the training experiences for stakeholders in their countries. As results, the article illustrates how design research can be integrated into a design process for developing online stakeholder workshops, and how the selected methods used in the research additionally contributed to collaborative team learning through CAE and reflections aimed at understanding team dynamics.

Conceptual framework: The role of design research for engagement in online spaces and approaches to learning:

Design processes have been widely described for designers to draw on within the often complex and multi-layered contexts in which they work (Aspelund, 2014; Dorst, 2008; Smit & Melissen, 2018). However, it has been alleged that certain aspects of design processes, such as the contexts, actors and objects (e.g., design problems and solutions) in design activities, have been neglected due to a focus on process (Dorst, 2008, p. 5). This article aims to illuminate the roles of design actors—in this case, a design team—in a design research process to design an online workshop environment for engaging with stakeholders, for example in policy making processes.

The conceptual framework selected for this paper focuses and digital space in the context of digital environments in which online tools were used to facilitate the functioning of the environment. The further focus on the assessment by the team on their design process, through the use of CAE as a method, enabled a fast and effective means of knowledge sharing and learning. The

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

Figure 1. Conceptual framework with the design team at the centre of the action at the intersection of learning, digital approaches, and design research. Author: Carolina Gutierrez Novoa (2021).

assessment of the design process contributed valuable data for design research. The theoretical concepts, that underpin the practical implementation and assessment of the design process, is elaborated in below.

The article highlights how design processes and the production of research data overlap during active research processes (Muratovski, 2015). Faste & Faste (2012) note that research is often integrated into designing, and Tussyadiah (2014, p. 546) argues that ‘design research is conducted as a part of the designing process, where data and information generated from research activities are used to guide the designing process’. Design is transformational, as it involves ‘systemic thinking, sense-making and capacity building’ (Cautela et al., 2015, p. 749). However, calls have been made for more studies that go beyond design practice and explore co-creative projects involving collaborations between design practitioners and design researchers (Dorst, 2008; Muratovski, 2015) to avoid limiting design research and the scientific development of design as a discipline (Dorst, 2008, p. 5).

The design discipline today is characterised by the ways in which designers think and struc-

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

ture processes to create innovative solutions to complex problems (Miettinen & Sarantou, 2019). It is increasingly common for design to be applied at a strategic level due to the prominence of problem-solution and human-centred approaches (Burdick & Willis, 2011). Thinking like a designer involves shifting the focus from how situations are to how they could be in order to guide the creation of new contexts that can help people change the way they frame a situation through the use of analogies or metaphors (Dorst, 2008). This means adopting new perspectives within which to frame the new challenges that designers face when working in digital spaces. By commencing from a design problem, designers can work towards long-term or overall aims and devise new approaches. The collective intelligence and cognitive diversity (Aggarwal et al., 2019) of a design team can optimise design outputs, and in this area, designers can play a fundamental role in maximising optimal outcomes in collaborative processes. The objective for designers is to design or structure online activities that harness diversity and that support people in achieving a common goal through exploration, discussion and assessment (Salter et al., 2009). In digital spaces, participatory approaches increase the sense of ownership within the team by minimising power differentials and engaging participants in decision-making, which, in turn, motivates people to engage in interpersonal exchange and form relationships (Olmstead & Turpen, 2017). In a digital space, overall engagement becomes more challenging, so critical engagement is required to identify suitable online approaches (Salter et al., 2009). Workshops are designed to shape the behaviour of participants (Vogt, 2009), and designers are responsible for creating a temporary environment, such as a virtual or digitally enabled workshop session, in which participants feel safe to engage in work.

Learning is broadly understood as the acquisition of skills or knowledge through experience, iteration, study or instruction. Grayling (2002, p. 158) appreciates learning as the ability to 'think, and question, and know how to find answers' when needed. Mayes & De Freitas (2007) argue that no new models for digital learning or e-learning exist. Instead, existing learning

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

models have been digitally enhanced to enable learning outcomes. Technological developments in online interfaces can enhance learning once the underlying elements of learning are met, and digitally enabled learning enables learners to interact with one another using learning materials, tools and subject matter (Mayes & De Freitas, 2007, p. 13). Ongoing developments in digital culture, supported by the conception of new digital programs, require enhanced learning models that are underpinned by new approaches and modes of knowledge production (Burdick & Willis, 2011). Several authors have also argued for an integration of design thinking into human- and user-centred approaches and models for digital learning and knowledge production.

One of the challenges of digital learning is engaging participants in learning processes. This challenge can be addressed by devising learning approaches that are adapted to learners' needs and that offer flexibility and a variety of tools (Lin & Chen, 2017). The key responsibility is placed on the facilitator of the learning processes to systematically enable and equip the students with knowledge (Lin & Chen, 2017). A study by Sousa and Rocha (2019) illustrates that the primary digital learning tools in organisational environments are mobile technologies and devices such as tablets and smartphones. Mobile technologies and the kind of learning they enable should, therefore, be embedded into organisational strategies for digital transformation (Sousa & Rocha, 2019). The theoretical framework combines the main themes of designers as facilitators in digital spaces and digital approaches to learning. Digital learning environments should be flexible and adapted to the needs of the learners.

Description of the online toolset

Practical online tools were selected by the design team to foster their work in digital environments; for example, Microsoft Teams (MT) and the online whiteboard platform, Miro, that in combination constitute a kind of digital environment. Due to the limitations and rigidity of screen sharing, it is often better to use MT as a dialogical tool while better interaction can be achieved by 'real time' participating in the Miro whiteboard directly. The Miro platform en-

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

ables visual collaboration between participants as interactive sticky notes and symbols can be used. However, both the Miro whiteboard platform and MT in combination do not offer ideal solutions as both tools (screens) have distinct functions (Miro is a real time whiteboard tool and MT a conferencing tool) and are not simultaneously visible to a computer user with a single screen. This digital environment was used to develop the training guidelines and a toolset for the stakeholder workshops. Messaris (1987, p. 6) explains that spatial intelligence is possible through the spatial integration of this kind, where various multiple dimensional scenes (or screens) can be processed coherently and made sense of by an individual.

The online toolset consisted of the following elements:

Tool#1: Planning Tool

Tool#2: Stakeholder Mapping Tool

Tool#3: Stakeholder Selection and Gaining Deeper Insights

Tool#4: Inviting Stakeholders: Template

Tool#5: Cultural Policy Overview Tool

Tool#6: Workshop Introduction (PowerPoint Template)

Tool#7: Good Practice Conversation Cards

Tool#8: Toolset Evaluation Template

Tool#9: Data Collection for the Roadmap

Tool#10: Policy Roadmap Template

Methodology

The interdependencies in this research, which resulted from teamwork and knowledge sharing, presented an opportunity for the use of CAE to understand the roles of the team members, their interactions and how these roles contributed to the development of the research and design outcomes. However, CAE also enabled the team to critically discuss and assess their design process.

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

The article seeks to address the following research questions:

- How can the various roles and capacities of a design team contribute to solving design problems related to the development of online toolsets and workshops?
- How can design research processes be assessed effectively by a design (research) team?

Collaborative autoethnography is a subjective approach that draws on insider knowledge and personal experience (Ellis & Adams, 2014). The appeal of the method lies in its collective and reflexive nature; it enables autoethnographic data collection and subjective reflections while being a critical, non-exploitative, accessible and pragmatic approach to inquiry that includes all the subjects of the research in active and iterative dialogue, thus enabling ownership through the collective results of the research process.

Although CAE entails a focus on self-interrogation, its collective elements of data collection and analysis further enable ownership of the research process (Chang et al., 2016). Thus, CAE necessitates a shift from personal to group agency, as the personal engagement of the researcher and the research participants is stimulated as they are vested themselves (in the same person), but the research participants also share this same position in the researcher-participant team. The reflective practice of the researcher-participant teams also requires a focus on human-centred as opposed to problem-centred inquiry (Anderson et al., 2004), and this practice also involves analytical processes that can generate understanding through reflection.

A combined CAE and reflexive approach enabled the practitioner to facilitate change in processes and systems (Leitch & Day, 2000, p. 179). Attia and Edge (2017, p. 33) argue that reflexive researchers should uphold the integrity of the environments and contexts in which they work but at the same time work through conceptualisation by distancing themselves from the action. CEA enables a process of distancing and reflection, as it allows the group of researcher-participants to collectively step away from the experience to reflect on, collate and advance their

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

theories and ideas.

Participants

The participants in the CAE and data sources of the research were the four members of the design team (and authors of this article) who sought to analyse and assess their design process. The design team consisted of two researchers from the University of Lapland in Finland, and two service designers from the PACO Design Collaborative in Italy. The two researchers from the University of Lapland were also a service-designer and social designer respectively. All team members were females between the ages of 30 and 50 years.

The design team adhered to the Ethics Committee of the University of Lapland that provided ethical screening of the research. The ethical principles and guidelines of the Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity (TENK) were considered throughout the course of the research. Ethical issues were taken into consideration at every phase of the design project: planning the workshops and interaction among designer-researchers who consented to the collective design research before data collection commenced

Data Collection

The data collection methods included a qualitative questionnaire with which responses from the team were collected in writing. A set of questions was developed by the design team to foster their reflections. Throughout the design processes (developing the training toolset and guidelines and preparing the online workshop environment), note-taking and focus group discussions were used. For the CAE approach, these methods were combined with an online working session in the Miro environment during which the design team used reflexive note-taking, discussions and other visual tools from Miro to analyse, group and visualise the data and findings in various ways.

The questions for personal reflection were:

- What kind of roles did you have during the co-design practices (planning the workshops

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

and also during the workshops)?

- Why and how did you enact that role?
- How important your role(s) was/were for the workshops?
- How did you utilise your design knowledge (intelligence) during the workshop planning and workshop facilitation?
- Learnings and challenges between the interaction with the team

The data collection and design processes for developing the workshop guidelines and the toolset for the online training workshop were reflected upon critically by the design team using the written data collected from the set of questions, CAE notes and group discussion. The data were collaboratively grouped, analysed and discussed in a focus group discussion using the Miro whiteboard tool (Figure 2). The findings concern the various roles and capacities of the design team in terms of solving design problems and determining how to generate better experiences, solve challenges and produce solutions through design and finally, how to improve online facilitation.

Results: Team Dynamics

The dynamics that influenced the work of the team in an online environment are discussed next. These dynamics include the (a) adoption of various roles by the design team, (b) design solutions for digital environments, (c) facilitation in online and digital spaces, (d) the role of collective intelligence, (e) personal learning and (f) the use of arts-based methods (ABMs).

Adopting various roles

The team members took on different roles. They were able to identify and reflect on their roles and identities using their notes and observations, CAE notes, group discussions and collaborative content analysis. Sometimes, they chose their roles, and other times, the roles were

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

<p>TOOLS & METHODS</p> <p>Mixing methods.</p> <p>Easy tasks for participants.</p> <p>Visualisation for online participants.</p> <p>Simplified everything (when online).</p> <p>Logic structure.</p>	<p>THE CRUCIAL QUESTIONS TO CONSIDER</p> <p>How to trust that they know what to do in the future?</p> <p>How to get things done?</p> <p>How to impact to the participants?</p> <p>How people perceive the experiences in online?</p> <p>The very first moment of creating an experience of online tools is crucial.</p>	<p>CREATING AN EXPERIENCE OF ONLINE FACILITATION</p> <p>How people perceive the experiences in online.</p> <p>The very first moment of creating an experience of online tools is crucial.</p> <p>Examples.</p> <p>The previous experience of the tool (confident).</p> <p>"I'm used to putting myself into the participants perspective."</p>
<p>CHALLENGES</p> <p>Informal communication is missing.</p> <p>Seeing the participants is important.</p>	<p>OPPORTUNITIES</p> <p>Usefulness for the people who are not familiar with design methods and tools.</p> <p>Motivation of the facilitator and participation.</p>	<p>ONLINE FACILITATION</p> <p>Online facilitation requires more plan B, C and D's.</p> <p>Simplified everything (when online).</p> <p>Online facilitation requires more patience and creativity.</p> <p>"I'm used to putting myself into the participants perspective."</p>

Figure 2. Data collection, grouping and analysis of the qualitative responses from the team members through an online survey in the Miro whiteboard environment. After the online survey was completed, the data was collated and collectively discussed and analysed, following the CAE approach, in the Miro whiteboard. During the session key themes were identified and further developed through reflections and note taking. To show the authentic data, the use of English in the data clusters, which were created in the Miro environment employed by the design team to analyse and reflect on the data that they collectively reflected on, has not been edited or changed. All designers spoke languages other than English as their first language.

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

dictated by the responsibilities of each team member. From the analysis of the CAE, the roles of the different members of the design team and a list of the roles performed during the process emerged. Each role was assumed organically through balanced and harmonious interaction between the team members and in accordance with their diverse skills and competencies. One of the designers reflected: ‘Taking and enacting this (researcher’s) role was natural, (almost like) “automation”’, whereas another acknowledged ‘enacting my role in co-design practices’ as a familiar experience. One participant reported, ‘I’m used to putting myself into the participant’s perspective’. The roles of designers as empathisers, collaborators and weavers were central to the design process. Although many of the roles were shared, each role had its own autonomous identity defined by its relationship and interaction with other roles. The members of the design team each contributed their own personal background, interests and expertise to the project. They combined their capacities to achieve the project objectives, which, in this case, were guided by the European Commission grant agreement for AMASS and the requirements and deliverables of the work package. The funnelling of capacities into a common space enabled the designers’ roles to emerge, develop, be woven together and be interchanged depending on the complexity of the tasks at hand (see Figure 3).

For a successful design project, a heterogeneous design team composed of professionals who take on one role or several roles at the same time is crucial. The different roles the designers took on during the process were one of the elements that affected the dynamics within the design team. Examples of the identified roles the authors fulfilled were as follows:

The coordinator. Who is leading the process, deciding on time frames and remembering the tasks to deliver?

The strategic thinker. Who focuses on the final goal and leads all the actions towards its achievement?

The weaver. Who is concerned with the exchange of knowledge within the design team and

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

amongst the other teams involved and the training participants?

The decision maker. Who makes all the decisions?

The broker. Who takes on the tasks of coordination and decision making and assigns and organises the actions?

The critical thinker. Who critically and continuously considers and discusses issues to ensure that the process and outputs are steered in the right direction without taking the status quo for granted?

The researcher. Who is in search of particular information or data?

The empathiser. Who is putting herself in the shoes of the user and helping to make the output approachable, understandable and coherent?

The visualiser. Who is concerned with translating all the information into a visual representation to make the process and the outcomes easier to understand?

The facilitator. Who facilitates the processes with the participants?

The digital enabler. Who maximises the use of online tools by the team for ensuring successful outcomes? Who is concerned with enabling the online participation of key actors?

The reporter. Who records and collects the data needed for the analysis and compiles a coherent summary of the findings?

Design research for harnessing solutions for digital environments Second, for designing in online spaces, the challenges and opportunities for online knowledge sharing were derived from personal notes, observations, CAE notes, group discussions and collaborative content analysis. The designers reflected on what they had learnt, as a group, from the online toolset and guideline development process. They noted that complex design thinking is required to shift to online working modes and tools for process and training facilitation, with one participant noting that 'online facilitation requires more plan Bs, Cs and Ds'. The team's application of design thinking is self-explained by their phrases, such as 'keep in mind the larger aspects of the project', 'make

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

Figure 3. Funnelling of designer capacities into design spaces in accordance with the project objectives and requirements. Author: Carolina Gutierrez Novoa (2021).

all the connections to other work packages and tasks’, ‘takes a lot of reminding, prompting and also persuasion’, ‘work on a more strategic level’, ‘visualising the workshop processes’, ‘ideate the methods’ and ‘structure the methods in game board style’, which underpinned the critical and strategic approaches the team adopted in their design processes.

The designers described their collaborative working process as being ‘guided by intuition’ and ‘tried to understand their needs’, thus illustrating their human-centred that often find their expression and development in CEA and reflective research approaches. The key role of human-centred design in such online processes was stressed. The approaches to the design challenges, the work and their functioning as individuals and members of a team were described. Examples are ‘our planning with our objectives in focus’, ‘I used my skills to simplify processes’, ‘getting the pieces connected to the larger project’, ‘by sharing and mixing different methodologies’,

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

‘moving into new territories’, ‘visualisation and focus on the workshop process’, ‘sharing the work gave more quality’, ‘we used our organisational and graphic design skills’ and ‘ticking off tasks one at a time’. These statements are self-explanatory and also illustrate the systematic approach and focus within the team to reach their goals. The team also acknowledged that design research and selected methods impacted their ability to reflect and analyse, thereby using design research processes in seeking solutions to improve working in digital environments. They noted their analytical processes as follows: ‘our analytical approach and thinking at another level’, ‘positive and supportive feedback’, ‘analysis of the state of the art’, ‘clustering the results’ and ‘extract insights’.

Facilitation in digital spaces

One of the acknowledged design skills that received substantial reflection was the aspect of facilitation (Rautiainen, et al., 2021; Soto, et al., 2021). However, the team also emphasised that simplicity and clarity are crucial for enabling online learning and that ‘online facilitation requires more patience and creativity’. Practical aspects that constitute elements of facilitation were identified by the team, such as ‘time keeping’, ‘need to think of different scenarios’ and ‘structuring and organising’. In addition, the limitations of online facilitation, and considerations for more effective online facilitation, were also identified by the team. They indicated practical suggestions, such as ‘having breaks more often’, ‘speaking slower’, ‘explaining the tasks (or methods) more carefully’, ‘allowing more time’ and ‘learning to deal with digital tools’.

In addition, they pointed out the importance of visibility of the participants, and suggested ‘it is important to see the participants because the facilitator then understands when to intervene in the conversation’, ‘as facilitator you need to remain focused on how the participants are experiencing the process’, ‘you need to take care of participants’ and ‘you need to carefully follow all the participants and try to understand their needs’. These are sound advice for face-to-

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

face facilitation, which were somewhat taken for granted before the pandemic, but have shifted into focus once more in online facilitation processes. These highly practical, yet important skills for facilitation highlights the need for focused human-centred approaches to facilitation (Rautiainen, et al., 2021; Soto, et al., 2021).

How collective intelligence can affect team dynamics

The collective intelligence (Aggarwal et al., 2019) of the design team, who fulfilled varied roles, yielded high learning outputs and, to some extent, enabled participants to have satisfactory experiences of an online training workshop. The collaborative intelligence of the team evolved organically, intuitively and through honest and open discussions, which enabled the team to quickly develop trust in each other's opinions and capabilities. Only a few collaborative work experiences were shared by the Italian and Finnish designers, but these two groups had never worked together before and were, therefore, relatively unfamiliar with each other's working styles and capabilities. As the team members proactively took on certain roles, they embraced responsibility for certain tasks. For example, two designers had strong visualisation skills, one of whom took on the role of visualisation, whereas the other took on a more critical and strategic role in the process.

Due to the small size of the team (i.e. four members), the members could select and take on roles organically. The process was not forced, and roles were accepted and taken on in a respectful fashion and in the spirit of learning, which increased the trust that developed within the team. The high levels of trust between the team members, the wide variety of roles they played—both individually and collectively—and their varied levels of skill and expertise enabled the team to develop an optimal level of collective intelligence, which may not have been possible if the group had been remarkably larger or smaller. The design activities and outcomes were enabled by finding synergies and organically defining roles within the team. Finally, the design work in online environments was acknowledged to be exhaustive. One designer stated:

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

‘Some of these tasks are never ending, but things need to get done’.

The collective input of the designers, which includes their personal experiences, knowledge and skills, constitute their collective intelligence. Funnelled through the project objectives and the team’s aims, the sense of collective intelligence is illustrated by the variety of roles that come about and are taken on interactively in the collective workspace (see Figure 3), whether this is in a digital collective environment or a face-to-face work environment. Such an environment can contribute to a higher collective output if positive team dynamics prevails.

Personal learning

The design team expressed their general attitude to learning by reflecting on the digital environments they had to negotiate, learn to use and optimise through visualisations and approaches to game design by stating ‘we wanted to learn to use it even better’. The team also expressed positive attitudes to learning, which they viewed as essential, by stating ‘learning (is essential) because it enriches the final output’ and ‘the experiences and competencies gained helped me’. Learning was deemed important, as one designer critically reflected and admitted, ‘my own skills are not that great’ and ‘we were confronted with people who already have a great deal of experience’. Hence, learning was an essential aim for the designer. Critical reflections that shaped attitudes of learning within the team were, for example, ‘doing everything online was a bit more challenging’, ‘things are more difficult during an online workshop’ and ‘our main learnings occur from the different working areas we bridge’. Finally, one designer declared, ‘if we could work in physical presence, I could perform better because communication is much easier and immediate’. Therefore, continued hope was apparent for matters to return to ‘normal’ despite the team realising that their new learning may serve them well in future post-COVID contexts that are widely accepted will be different from the working environments that design teams have experienced in pre-COVID times.

One of the team members noted that the design and working processes, paired with de-

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

sign research and learning was 'a delicate dance'. Referring to performativity, this statement illustrates how different modes of work, from physical to virtual spaces need to be carefully balanced to create well-choreographed and synchronised work moments during which the team can work collaboratively and productively. It also refers to how the team had to actively employ their senses to create these favourable working environments. Stevens and McKechnie (2005, p. 243) refer to dance as 'non-verbal communication' that is 'rich in gesture, expression, and affect'. These authors also explain that dance can be inspired by ideas, emotions, spaces or surface, thus it facilitates concepts to become 'visible thoughts' that are 'declared through movement' (p. 244). The embodied performances by the design team, within their various spaces, whether in physical office or digital spaces (supported by the online Miro whiteboard and MT conference tools), involved delicate sensing, feeling and acting to make their thoughts visible to the rest of the team. After all, the arts and creativity assist reasoning through feeling (Best, 1996).

The 'delicate dance' also embodies and illustrates the careful reflective and learning processes that the team were involved in. They recognised in their discussions that they were involved in intricate 'feedback-feed forward' loops (Hughes, 2011, p. 360), which required ongoing sensitivity to reflect on and respond to queues coming from their different environments. Feedback-feed forward loops can imply learning processes that come about through experience. Such feedback loops can, through collective critical reflection and ipsative feedback by all team members, 'close the gap between current performance and expected performance' (Hughes, p. 360). This collaborative learning experience is based on negotiation and learning in collaboration with other. Thus, the process can be described as social constructivism (Kanselaar, 2002), which is defined as 'a theory of knowledge in sociology and communication theory that examines the knowledge and understandings of the world that are developed jointly by individuals' (Amineh & Asl, 2015, p. 13). This theory assumes that meaning making is developed in co-

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

ordination with other human beings through collective knowledge production that constitutes how learners perceive reality in moments of learning (p. 13). As such, social constructivism portrays learning as an essentially embodied and social process.

Use of ABMs

Although the designers did not explicitly reflect on the use of ABMs in their design practices, the importance of aspects, such as ‘visualising the workshop processes’, ‘structure the methods in game board style’ and, as stated before, ‘facilitation needs more creativity’ were mentioned. These phrases emphasise the need for ABMs to be integrated in the digital environments under discussion. Foster describes the abilities of arts-based methods as enabling ‘a diversity of experiences to be communicated in ways that disrupt “common sense” understandings and act as a reminder that there are possibilities for things to be otherwise’ (Foster, 2016, p. 1-2). ABMs involve sensory perceptions and emotion, as well as intellectual responses, by enabling a different understanding and exploring different ways of knowing the world through both visual and performative approaches (Leavy, 2017; Sarantou et al., 2018).

In ongoing experiments by the project team, arts-based methods were used to develop more interactive activities during stakeholder workshops (Sarantou et al., 2021). In the stakeholder workshop under discussion, ABMs were used to create the metaphoric ‘forest’, which represents an ecosystem of interconnected needs and best practices as the roots and trunks of the multiple trees in the system. The foliage is created by Miro whiteboard sticky notes on which the participants can create notations of possible resources, people and actions who should be involved in materialising the best practices. This activity is collaborative, based on discussion, listening and note taking by all the participants. In this example, ABMs offer new opportunities for creating collaborative activities in online stakeholder workshops for policy making.

Experimentation and new approaches are needed in policy making due to the said failures of policy in terms of mitigating complex societal challenges (Kimbell & Bailey, 2017). The

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

regard, ABMs can assist designers to cross divide and offer opportunities for the formulation of concrete strategies through approaches to visualisation.

Conclusion

This article presents the working and research design process of a design team whose aim was to engage in policy work through online stakeholder workshops with European research partner institutions. The article explores the different roles the designers engaged in during the development of an online toolset and training guidelines and an online training workshop. Based on the design team's reflections on lessons learned, CAE and collective analysis, the following guidelines are proposed for working in digital environments:

- *Provide a space of trust and security to ensure knowledge sharing.* The variety and complexity of roles the designers embraced, exchanged, shared and developed during the working process enabled the implementation of a complex policy-making intervention through online workshops. Some roles were supported by their skills and expertise, but other roles developed through knowledge sharing and learning. Collectively, the roles contributed to the ability of the team to upscale the policymaking activities.
- *Be open to change.* The design team learnt that many of the AMASS partners will pilot the training tools and workshops in online mode, as the time frame of the project and the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic will make face-to-face participation impossible in most of the partner countries. Technology, digital tools and online participation will, therefore, be important as possible instruments and approaches to implement needed change and for building resilient societies that are actively engaged in policy making at the regional and even European level.
- *Promote active participation and empathic engagement through ABMs and visualisation.* Visualisation through the use of visual tools and ABMs can create inclusion and empa-

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

thy (Miettinen et al., 2016), enable participants to speedily grasp complex issues under discussion and guide their activities during online workshops.

- *Create clear strategies with sustainable objectives.* The size of a design team and the methodological choices are important considerations for successful knowledge sharing, the harnessing of collective intelligence, ongoing learning and the development of tool sets and training activities. Without solid strategies for design, research and data collection, the design team will not be able to correct mistakes, implement improvements and scale up their actions.
- *Lead by example.* Human interaction and human-centred approaches, especially during the pandemic, which limited the operational environment of the design team, enabled the designers to develop empathy for one another and within the team and to transfer this into large training activities. Ensuring that participants are familiar with online tools can increase empathic encounters and improve the scalability of online tools in the long term.
- *Build an open environment to foster accountability and increase team empowerment.* Shared decision making, trust and a sense of belonging within the design team enabled the members of the team to scale up their own capabilities and knowledge, fostering commitment to take on important challenges, facilitating changes in time frames and modes of operations from a face-to-face or blended format to wholly digital, and improving the outcomes of their collective work to meet the objectives of the AMASS project.

The lessons learnt from operating within a complex online design research, design research and training environment may offer opportunities for translation to other policy activities and educational environments. Based on social-constructivist understandings related to learning, the team activities illustrate that learning is essentially social and comes about through collaborative meaning making and shared realities. Without an overlap between design process

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

and design research by using CEA approaches to understand the dynamics within the design team, and without data collection for evaluation purposes, the team would only apply limited improvements to the toolset and training, with not only an obvious detrimental effect on quality but also a negative effect on participants. From the viewpoint of the design team working with complex policy making, the importance of rigorous data analysis from note taking and CEA approaches throughout the process, especially their reflections on learning and feedback loops for improving their design processes, may better engage workshop participants and illustrate that their contributions are valued. Due to high levels of motivation among the AMASS partners, the users of the online toolset and workshop, participation levels were high. However, other stakeholders may not have such high levels of motivation and may not be willing to participate in workshops under similar circumstances. Hence, ongoing piloting and research is needed for a design team to manage the challenges faced by participants in online environments and to enable the effective implementation of online stakeholder workshops.

Systematically scaled and understandably visualised tools and ABMs offer opportunities for empathic engagement (Miettinen et al., 2016) and are therefore crucial in a complex design context, such as conceptualising and creatively constructing digital stakeholder workshop environments and user journeys for stakeholders who engage in policy-making processes. Illustrating expertise through ABMs and visualisation can win trust and enable engagement.

In addition, CAE illustrated to be an effective method for design teams who need to understand how their design results can be improved. Collective intelligence can also be analysed and harnessed more effectively alongside the CAE approach of collective reflection on personal experiences. CAE, combined with visual analytical tools such as the Miro whiteboard, can be an effective method for fast assessment by teams working in design research processes. Avenues for research and ongoing development were identified for further testing and refining of the toolset and training guidelines in different contexts and with different stakeholders, which

"MORE PATIENCE AND CREATIVITY": TEAM LEARNING IN ONLINE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP SETTINGS

will improve learning outcomes further and, in combination with design research, learning experiences in the upcoming post-COVID times. Sharing and disseminating best practices will not only benefit grassroots-level policy making, participation and intervention but also drive the development of one-off digital tools in online training initiatives.

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Ethics Reviews in Socially Engaged Arts Research

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Biography

Milosh Raykov is an Associate Professor in the Department of Education Studies at the Faculty of Education, the University of Malta, where he teaches research methods and sociology of education. He is involved in studies of early school leaving, student involvement in paid and voluntary work, and studies of socially engaged art.

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Abstract

This article explores researchers' perceptions of discrepancies between the creative goals of research projects in which artists are recruited and requirements established by ethical review boards in higher education. It describes issues that researchers typically face when applying for the ethical clearance of research projects that engage various communities in participatory activities involving creative professionals. While the observation of ethical codes of practice is very important in all academic research, it is equally important to understand how the goals of research and artistic outcomes may be affected by regulatory procedures as well as variable institutional practices related to

ethical reviews of research. Ethical requirements may impact research in any discipline and are certainly not unique to the arts, but it is important to understand the specific effects of ethics review boards on research projects that venture into new creative areas that might involve vulnerable participants or include unforeseeable artistic outcomes. The article analyses studies undertaken by a research team made of academics, artists and other entities at the University of Malta and shows how the ethics review process affects timeframes, levels of participants' involvement and the organic development of creative processes. Finally, it makes some recommendations for ethical review boards in the evaluation of socially engaged arts research projects.

Keywords

Socially engaged arts research, research ethics reviews, researchers' experience; barriers to research; ethics review boards

Introduction

Practice as research has become an established mode of academic inquiry that incorporates creative practices into research contexts, bridging age-old divides between theory and practice within the context of research infrastructures like universities, peer-reviewed journals and doctoral studies (Wilson & van Ruiten, 2013). During recent decades, this development in academia has had various implications for PhDs in the arts and other disciplines, bringing into play tensions relating to accreditation or standards and epistemological debates revolving around the development and communication of knowledge (Sullivan, 2010; Nelson, 2013). While the use of multi-modal research protocols and creative presentations in research contexts may have

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

had a liberating effect in certain academic circles, the repositioning of artistic practices within higher education and research, in general, has also meant that artistic research now needs to comply with regulatory requirements that are standard practice in universities. Specifically, ethical codes of practice are central to research projects in any field that brings academics into contact with members of the broader community. Given that the aims of socially engaged arts projects are generally associated with community-driven needs and political goals, management plans for artistic research involving the collection of data from participants now need to include provisions for participants' informed consent, secure storage of personal data, protection of the participants' identity, respect for the rights of individuals, and so on.

This article will not argue that ethical requirements in other university disciplines should not apply to research in the arts. Rather, this study is focused on a review of the issues that researchers encounter during the planning of research and applications for research ethics approval to conduct their studies, with a particular focus on socially engaged arts research. It explores specific constraints that are experienced by academic researchers as well as creative practitioners involved in research projects, particularly projects that interact with other communities like marginalised groups through the arts. The challenges it will discuss cannot be generalised, because different research proposals and ethics review boards may bring into play different scenarios. More concretely, the sort of research this article will discuss could involve researchers in fieldwork in a context in which an artist or creative team is interacting collaboratively with a community, such as a group of elderly persons in a retirement home. Such a scenario can be complicated further if one also takes into account the fact that academics working in arts departments are sometimes practising artists themselves, while freelance contemporary artists increasingly think of their artwork as a form of 'research' in its own right. While preparing applications for the ethical review of research, the mindset of persons trained in the importance of risk-taking and unpredictability in artistic disciplines may require a kind

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

of epistemological repositioning in order to cater for the minimisation of risk or to communicate potential risks in advance to all participants. As a result, persons who are trained as artists (amongst others) may perceive their institutional ethics review boards' requirements as restrictive due to the creative and not always predictable nature of artistic research.

While researchers would generally agree that the rights of participants in any form of research should be respected and that researchers must prevent harm to the participants, a number of researchers are concerned about the procedures and requirements imposed by International Research Ethics Boards (IREB). According to Oancea (2016), for example, a growing concern about ethical issues in research is particularly visible among researchers in the domain of qualitative and visual research. Also, in the complex and multidisciplinary domain of socially engaged arts research that focuses on exploring the intersection of social, educational, and arts-related issues, researchers face challenges specific to social research and the particular challenges inherent to socially engaged arts. While socially engaged arts or social practice revolves around creative and other processes that artists and other groups collaborate on to implement change, for the purposes of this article socially engaged arts research is being understood as academic research that studies these processes in order to understand and possibly assess the kinds of change that occur within such co-produced work.

According to Punch and Oancea (2014, p. 58), "Research ethics is a branch of applied ethics focused on the specific contexts of planning, conducting, communicating and following up research". Oancea (2016) also emphasizes that ethical issues are always present in educational research that includes human subjects, particularly when the research involves children or other vulnerable groups. There is general agreement among scholars that the ethics review process in research is important (Carr, 2015; Scherzinger & Bobbert, 2017) but demanding (Silberman & Kahn, 2011) and often a challenging (Lewis, 2008; Sikes, 2013) component of empirical research studies. Arts-based research and doctoral studies that include a strong

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

component of creative practice could not exist without an understanding of the value and application of ethics reviews. However, some issues were also identified in the domain of socially engaged arts research that represent an obstacle to pursuing quality educational research due to (un)reasonable requirements imposed by institutional ethics review boards (Sanders & Ballengee-Morris, 2008). Consequently, practices adopted for ethics reviews in the domain of social sciences enforced by institutional review boards are perceived by artists and researchers as highly restrictive and challenging (Israel, 2017; Dingwall, 2012; Schrag, 2010; Wassenaar and Slack, 2016).

Literature shows that scholars understand the ethical requirements for studies involving human participants and consider them as highly relevant. Still, they emphasize that the process is usually too long and restrictive (Shoenbill et al., 2017). Since institutional regulations frequently change, researchers involved in socially engaged arts-related projects and other researchers often experience difficulties through this process (Dingwall, 2008, 2012; Emmerich, 2013; Librett & Perrone, 2010; Lombardo, 2017).

Scholars unanimously agree that the observation and practice of ethical research are of utmost importance, and need to protect participants from any physical, social, legal, and psychological risk. Based on a critical analysis of research ethics regulations in the social sciences, however, Dingwall (2008, 2012) concludes that ethics reviews in social science limit the rights and freedom of researchers and jeopardize trust between researchers and participants and, in this way, represent a risk for the quality of social research. Research studies that apply an ethnographic approach are particularly affected by ethics regulations (Mapedzahama & Dune, 2017). According to Librett & Perrone (2010), ethics regulations and the required mandatory consent and monitoring compromise confidentiality and significantly affect “contemporary ethnographic research and has had serious consequences for both the research participants and the production of knowledge (p. 729).

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

In addition, several scholars claim that ethics reviews based on the biomedical model constrain research work in the social sciences (Israel & Hay, 2006), limit research methodology choices, and compromise academic freedom (Iphofen, 2020). Many researchers also perceive ethics reviews as too restrictive to the extent that they prevent research and debates about sensitive research topics (Scott, 2008).

Many researchers are aware of the volatility of the ethics review process, and studies that examine empirical literature evaluating institutional review boards demonstrate inconsistencies regarding risk level, recruitment, methodologies, and other vital aspects of research (Abbott & Grady, 2011; Lees et al., 2020). Analysed studies included in Abbott and Grady's review also show a site-to-site variability regarding institutional research board requirements and inefficiency of the institutional review process that often leads to changes in research proposals and, in this way, jeopardize the quality of science. Based on this comprehensive review of the existing literature about the work of institutional review boards, Abbott and Grady (2011) suggest several recommendations, including guidance or training for the members of the ethics review boards and additional research studies to inform the structure and processes of institutional review boards. In another comprehensive study of ethics review practice, Lees, Walters and Godbold (2020) found a similar inconsistency regarding institutional ethical review processes and outcomes with a particularly strong negative impact on studies that apply an ethnographic approach due to the epistemological assumptions which strongly oppose positivist models used by most ethics review bodies.

McCracken (2020) provided evidence that ethics review boards usually apply a positivistic approach in the ethics evaluation process with marginalized communities, and this is probably one of the main reasons for tensions that exist during the review process of socially engaged arts studies that are based on critical or interpretive methodologies and ideologies that are focused on social challenges. In addition, formalized research ethics review processes and bureaucratic

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

requirements are perceived by researchers as factors that negatively influence the quality of social (Hammersley, 2009) and educational research (Scott and Fonseca, 2010). Another comprehensive review of the literature (Anderson et al., 2012) found that studies of research ethics are usually conducted in the biomedical domain, while studies of ethics review processes in education and community-engaged research are largely neglected.

Overall, our literature review shows that an evaluation and improvement of the ethics review process are necessary since mandatory ethics reviews of social and art-related empirical studies affect many research studies and influence the selection of research problems and research methodology as well as efficacy, relevance, and quality of research. Problems related to ethics reviews in the domain of socially engaged arts warrant new studies in order to enable researchers to deal with challenging ethics review processes in this significant but complex multi-disciplinary domain.

In the domain of socially engaged arts research, the careful planning and predictability of data collection tools in research processes and applications for ethical clearance from institutional research ethics committee boards may seem to run counter to the twists and element of surprise found in many creative pursuits because professional standards of good practice and university directives tend to be regulated by procedures that were generated in other disciplines like medicine (Savin-Baden & Wimpenny, 2014). This could mean that certain discrepancies might arise between artistic goals or the expectations of researchers based in artistic disciplines and actual research outcomes or possibilities. At the same time, it must be acknowledged that participatory processes in the arts can be accompanied by instances of abuse of privilege by artists or other research coordinators as well as other issues related to ownership of data and creative outcomes, informed consent, and so on. It would therefore be unreasonable to expect anything less rigorous than a thorough ethics review prior to commencing such research projects.

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

In this article, the challenge of planning and implementing socially engaged arts research within the remit of university institutional research codes will be discussed by describing and analysing a series of funded research studies submitted for ethical review by a team at the University of Malta. These studies form part of an EU-funded, Horizon 2020 project called ‘Acting on the Margins: Arts as Social Sculpture’ (AMASS), in which several other European partners are involved. AMASS aims to bring people from different walks of life to work with artists on the development and implementation of multidisciplinary, creative projects. It also aims to study and evaluate the societal impact of the arts and present policy recommendations in different European countries and regions. AMASS research at the University of Malta was led by a team of researchers with expertise in art education and socially engaged art, drama education and empirical research. For the purposes of this research, artistic practitioners with years of experience in theatre, scriptwriting, screen printing, fashion, socially engaged arts and other artistic and educational areas were commissioned to support various aspects of the research projects. Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and other specialised entities also supported the research process by advising about different aspects like recruitment of participants, suitability of data collection tools, and so on.

The article will delve into a broad discussion about the nature of experimentation, ethics and possible instrumentalisation of the arts in research and social engagement. It will then examine mixed methods of data collection (including arts-based methods) adopted by the University of Malta team to understand the social impact of artworks and will discuss ethical procedures leading to submission and acceptance by the university’s ethics committees. Finally, it will reflect on the possibility of improving ethical reviews of partnerships between university researchers, artists and communities in order to ensure that such partnerships revolve around meaningful dialogues rather than problematic trade-offs.

Social practice: Between instrumentalisation and antagonism

Thompson (2012) writes that “social practice artists create forms of living that activate communities and advance public awareness of pressing social issues” (p. 8), thus expanding our understanding of art and involving new publics. In short, socially engaged art replaces representational goals prevalent in earlier artistic practices with more participatory goals that bring others’ work into the equation. The emancipatory goals of some forms of community-based arts (or their manifestation in discursive practices) have occasionally been criticised for developing paternalistic attitudes towards participants, characterised by the view that these artistic practices ‘improve’ the lives of others (Kester, 2013).

Alternatively, participatory projects can be problematic because they instrumentalise the arts by focusing on their ‘usefulness’ and minimise, or even do away with, antagonistic situations that form a necessary part of any democratic society (Bishop, 2012). The use of state funding to construct unrealistic narratives of consensus or inclusion can overburden the creative arena with expectations of social cohesion (Dewinter et al., 2020). Such narratives can also give the impression that individuals or communities, rather than institutions and systemic structures, are ultimately responsible for finding ‘solutions’ for societal challenges. There exists a risk that official cultural policies that prioritise arts projects with a social dimension can end up reducing the arts to an extension of government policy. Artists who make use of participatory processes in their practice need to be aware of this risk in order to maintain a good balance between social goals they embrace and the need to ensure that the arts remain critical of the status quo. Creating false expectations about the eradication of social inequalities through the funding of participatory arts initiatives is potentially exploitative of various social groups involved in such projects and artists could be instrumental in ensuring that communities use such platforms to develop political critique instead of ‘happy’ compromises that merely appease cultural authorities.

The criticality we associate with serious artistic practices may be reinforced in social prac-

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

tice by cross-medium tendencies that challenge “inherited parameters for defining the within and the without of art” (Jackson, 2011, p. 28). This necessary critical engagement between artists working in different media, participants and authorities shows that ethical considerations are indeed an essential condition of socially engaged arts. Rowe (2019) has also written about the importance of introducing a measure of antagonism in socially engaged, arts-based research projects. Clearly, these kinds of issues warrant a thorough review of ethical implications in higher education contexts, where qualities like honesty, transparency and academic integrity are a *sine qua non*.

When we consider the impact of ethics review procedures on the development of more antagonistic socially engaged arts research we might ask whether such university procedures confine practice as research and participatory, creative projects within ‘acceptable’ or altruistic parameters, hence making it difficult for artist-researchers to break through these inherited parameters. Might it become too challenging to simultaneously break through accepted aesthetic boundaries and satisfy ethical requirements? Putting this question a little differently, one could ask: do university codes of practice serve not only to protect members of vulnerable groups from abusive relationships and any form of risk or harm with artist-researchers but also to determine the extent of experimentation and collaboration that would be possible? Can ethics review boards discourage real participation by expecting academics to maintain a safe, professional distance from participants?

Description of University of Malta AMASS studies

As part of its AMASS obligations, the University of Malta team developed and is implementing a pilot study and four additional studies, all of which employ arts-based strategies and mixed data collection and assessment methods. Below is a brief description of these Maltese testbed studies, followed by an analysis of the work and difficulties involved in submitting

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

these artistic projects for ethical clearance. The pilot study was a theatrical project that aimed to engage with challenges experienced by persons living with HIV in Malta. Its final title was *Il-Pozittivi* (The Positives), and it was developed by a creative enterprise called Culture Venture as well as a scriptwriter and several actors. The data that helped the team to develop the script was gathered from a small group of persons living with HIV, who were interviewed by two social workers to maintain complete anonymity. The interviewees and other members of the pilot study's gatekeeper, MGRM (Malta LGBTIQ Rights Movement) were invited to give feedback about the play's first draft during an online rehearsed reading, and the script and title were changed on the basis of this feedback. A new version with a more positive outlook on the life of persons living with HIV was professionally filmed and shown to online audiences around six months later. Additional data was gathered using other means like pre- and post-test strategies and paper-and-pencil surveys.

Suitable Citizens was developed by artist/academic Raphael Vella with the support of a photographer, a screen printing artist, a fashion designer and an amateur filmmaker who was trained in filmmaking and video editing specifically for this project. The project revolved around the exclusion of migrants from cultural life in Malta and was supported by an NGO, *Jesuit Refugee Service Malta*. Participants from various African countries participated in different data collection strategies, including pre- and post-surveys, focus groups, photovoice, journals and other arts-based methods and open-ended discussions and workshops. They produced a series of photographs, which were screen printed on paper and different types of fabric, leading to colourful tote bags, face masks and scarves.

F'Ħakka t'Għajn is a theatre project developed by academic and drama educator Isabelle Gatt from the University of Malta, with the support of different actors. Assisted by *Active Ageing*, a national entity that works with the elderly in Malta, the team (which included a scriptwriter) worked with a small group of elderly persons on the development of a script for

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

a new play. Similar data collection strategies to the other projects were used, though the vulnerability of this group of participants led to various delays during the COVID pandemic. The project still hasn't reached completion at this stage, but Isabelle Gatt plans to have the play filmed and shown online to different audiences, given the restrictions currently in place for physical theatre.

The final two projects in the University of Malta AMASS testbed are still in their early stages, though both have already received ethical clearance. *Batman Gżirjan* is being developed by artist Kristina Borg with the support of an environmental and heritage NGO and a local community group. This project is currently being developed in a series of online and face-to-face workshops with elderly residents (or ex-residents) and fishermen in a small town called Gżira that is suffering from overdevelopment, particularly its more popular public spaces adjacent to the sea. The project leader aims to develop 'guerrilla' actions and a final performance near or in the sea, with the contribution of the participants. In this project, data will also be collected from passers-by, who will be asked to contribute with feedback about their perceptions about these developments in the town.

The final research project is also being developed by *Culture Venture*, with the support of Opening Doors, an NGO that works with adults with intellectual disabilities. A script for a new play will be co-written by participant-members of *Opening Doors*, with the assistance of professional actors, a director and a script writer, leading to a public performance that will engage with issues raised by the participants themselves during workshops and rehearsals. Data collection tools will include pre- and post-assessment interviews, focus groups, journals and audience paper-and-pencil surveys or structured interviews.

The Ethics Review Process

The ethics review process used at the Faculty of Education at the University of Malta is rigorous and typically expects a great amount of detail from researchers applying for ethical approval of their research projects. For each of the research projects described above, the AMASS researchers at the University of Malta supplied the ethics board with over fifty pages of project descriptions, data collection tools, recruitment procedures, participating artists and community members, risks envisaged at different stages, data management plans, and so on. Comprehensive applications like these are generally required to provide further details following a first evaluation by the board, and occasionally expand even further following a second evaluation. Of course, this process is to be expected in any serious ethical review of research.

It has been argued that partners in participatory research involving the input of community members should ideally choose their level of involvement with a university's ethics review board (Shore, 2007). In practice, this is not always possible, as the University of Malta AMASS team found when planning to engage with persons living with HIV in Malta in one of its theatre research projects. The level of caution exercised by the faculty's research ethics committee and the gatekeeper providing support in this project (MGRM, the Malta LGBTIQ Rights movement), as well as the request for anonymity of the interviewees, highlighted the difficulty of employing a more inclusive approach in this study (Gatt et al., 2021).

Another difficulty encountered by the University of Malta AMASS team and other researchers is related to the organic development of projects of a creative and/or community-based nature. Artists know that projects can rarely be planned very precisely in advance and may also argue that prescriptive models of artistic practice stifle the creative process. When artists collaborate with others, the problem is intensified because the participatory approach itself would appear to dictate that room must be left for possible changes in direction based on co-creators' input. However, the ethics review procedures in the team's faculty (particularly

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

the procedures' emphasis on informed consent and accurate information) require researchers to have very precise data management plans in advance, specifying the duration of different activities and expectations from all participants and stakeholders. Maintaining equity in community-based research processes would need to take account of the fact that research projects of this sort "involve learning and change at the individual, group, organization, and ultimately societal levels" (Wood, 2017, p. 2), but in practice, the strict rules and time-related limitations may not encourage changes in research plans that are inherent to creative artistic creation. Apart from its possible effect on artistic innovation, this adherence to ethical regulations could also lead to the conversion of potentially exciting research methods to relatively bland or conventional modes that would not take risks or present possible pitfalls during a review.

Other questions that arose during preparations for AMASS studies were related to the participant's right to withdraw from theatrical productions that would be virtually stalled if any actor occupying a central role decided to exercise this right at the eleventh hour. Difficulties like this led to countless debates involving the University of Malta research team and participating artists like theatre directors and scriptwriters. Of course, this does not mean that ethical review procedures can or should be done away with. Such practices go a long way towards protecting the identity of vulnerable persons, protecting participants from possible harm, ensuring that they are given relevant information about the research, and that collaboration is entirely voluntary. Instead, it is crucial that these and other difficulties in ethics review procedures are understood well in order to guarantee more creative freedom and equitable forms of power-sharing in participatory artistic research.

During the evaluation of applications for the above-listed studies, the AMASS team encountered many obstacles similar to the issues identified in the literature. Indeed, it is likely that academics in several other fields of research encounter similar obstacles during the process of ethical approval. One of the first issues encountered during the application process was the

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

submission of applications through an online system, a form similar to an online survey that is limited regarding the length of the fields, but the length of the answers was unknown, and the applicants needed to guess the expected length of their responses.

In addition, communication with the ethics committee through this system was limited and confusing since this form was designed mainly for submission of students' individual applications for approval of their dissertations. In this way, the communication was limited to only one member of the research team, which required additional effort to involve all team members in submitting and revising their applications. Re-submission of the requested revisions was also challenging since additional requests often led to additions above the capacity of this online system. Such re-submissions often required repetitive new submissions and the adjustment of the already accepted components of applications.

Due to a large number of applications for review, the limited number of committee members and complications due to the pandemic, in addition to the technical challenges related to the submission of applications for ethics reviews, one of the serious challenges was the amount of time required for reviews by the ethics committee since each application required several months to be approved. This was particularly challenging for applications that were part of large-scale international studies due to the strict deadlines, interdependent research activities, request for frequent reporting and synchronized delivery of results from various national studies. The slow review process also created anxieties amongst various members of the team, given that there was a risk that some artists' commitment to participate might have been affected by changing timeframes. This last problem was exacerbated by the pandemic, during which work in the arts was particularly precarious and artists could not afford to involve themselves at length in projects that might change considerably or fall through due to decisions taken by the ethics review board.

Probably the most serious challenge for researchers was the scope of reviews that were,

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

according to researchers, highly restrictive and mandatory for all studies regardless of the domain of research and the specific methodological approaches of various research disciplines. Researchers often felt that the ethics reviews went beyond the scope of the review process and protection of the participants since reviews also included assessment of research questions and issues of a more academic nature. Such reviews were perceived as a restriction of researchers' academic freedoms and a barrier that limits the application of the theoretical and methodological approaches specific for studies in various fields of social science, education, particularly in studies that make use of qualitative and action research in the domain of socially engaged art (Poggenpoel & Myburgh, 2005). Similar issues identified in the literature of social and socially engaged arts research were identified in a recent study of researchers involved in educational and social research (Gatt et al., 2021). Artists working with university researchers in this set of AMASS studies were vocal about their perception that institutional ethics reviews restricted their artistic work and freedom.

Conclusion

Although many conceptual issues emphasized by researchers involved in socially engaged arts research exist (Bolt, 2016; 2019; Klassen, 2016; Pavarini et al., 2021) that warrant further studies and scholars' continuous involvement in the search for acceptable solutions for complex ethical issues in social and socially engaged research, many issues could be solved that would improve the efficiency and the quality of empirical studies as well as creative outcomes.

Based on the conducted literature review and experience from these complex socially engaged arts studies, it seems that some of the identified issues could be solved through improved procedures and technology of the submission of ethics reviews. A more flexible online application system based on some of the available online database technologies would certainly eliminate many technical issues that researchers face during the application process.

ETHICS REVIEWS IN SOCIALLY ENGAGED ARTS RESEARCH

The identified difficulties in communication with the institutional ethics review boards and imbalance of institutional, researcher individual, and research teams' power (Locke et al., 2015) could be prevented through direct dialogue as suggested by Hammersley (2015) as well as through the training of all actors involved in the ethics review process, particularly those who evaluate socially engaged arts research proposals (Abbott & Grady, 2011; MacNeill et al., 2020). Centralized reviews and slow communication through official reporting and re-submissions could be much more efficient if the ethics review boards appoint members competent in the research domain of studies that require ethics reviews since many minor issues identified through the review process could be much more efficiently solved through direct dialogue with the appointed members of the institutional research board. Members of review boards with expertise in the arts could contribute positively to this process. The lengthy process of review (up to around six months in the case of AMASS) needs to be revised to avoid possible dropouts of participants and artists caused by changing timeframes.

The danger of restricting creative results to outcomes that have already been predicted in research ethics applications also needs to be taken into account by review boards. Such restrictions can skew creative and scientific results and negatively impact relationships between researchers and participating artists, who may find such constraints problematic. While the studies conducted in Malta worked around these constraints to allow for and even encourage unpredictable outcomes and tensions, the research process would definitely have been easier and less stressful had the ethics review board included members who had a stronger grasp of arts-based research methods and requirements pertaining to creative and socially engaged arts. Positivistic approaches and epistemological assumptions about what constitutes 'serious' or ethical research need to be counter-balanced by an understanding of the need for some level of flexibility, unpredictability and change in participatory, creative studies of this sort.

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Artistic Actions for Sustainability in a University Setting

Ásthildur Jónsdóttir

Biography

Dr. Ásthildur Jónsdóttir (1970), is an artist, curator and independent scholar living in Geneva Switzerland. She has studied artistic actions for sustainability and participatory art practices in finding a balance between well-being and the integrity of nature. For several years, she has been involved in the ecology of the planet. In her work, she is concerned about issues such as environment and places, memories, recollection and identity through authorship and collaboration, exploring what is unique and what is common and questioning individuality.

Abstract

This chapter introduces a case entitled *Walk the Space*. Webster University in Geneva took the opportunity to invite an artist to work with their students to rethink their ideas of what we can do to meet sustainability global challenges. The artistic activities aimed to promote greater ecological consciousness through different forms of participation and awareness activities, helping the participants to discover the connection to the nature that surrounds them. *Walk the Space* created a platform for sharing ideas about sustainability,

both individual and collective. Participants, both staff and students alike, exchanged ideas through dialogues, exercises including walking, memory work, and through developing slogans that were subsequently embroidered and exhibited in the woods surrounding the university. This collaboration provided a space for transformative learning and active engagement, giving the potential for social change. This article gives insights into how artistic actions can strengthen community building and ecological consciousness.

Keywords

Education for sustainability, Well-being, Ecological Consciousness, Artistic actions, Transformative learning

Introduction

There are many ways to work towards sustainability; focusing on ecological consciousness through artistic actions is one such way. There is a growing societal awareness of the importance of getting people outdoors to connect body and mind with nature (Ives et al., 2018). Ecological consciousness is important in education for sustainability (EfS). It provides a focus for the learner as it helps to develop a relationship with nature. This focus includes discovering the intrinsic integrity of nature. In discussing nature's agency, normativity and the worth of nature, the learner has the potential to develop a sense of exactly what "being-in-nature" can give us (Bonnett, 2021). These experiences can drive learners to consider how a relationship with nature aligns with problems of sustainability. We can view ecological consciousness in terms of a balance between a world of people, objects and nature. Research has shown that there is an increasing disconnection between humans and nature. Some scholars have argued that discon-

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

nection from nature is the root cause of unsustainability (Folke et al., 2011; Dorninger et al., 2017). Studies indicate that environmental consciousness requires a complex mental education involving cognitive, regulatory, emotional and ethical experiences, among other aspects.

In general terms the ecological consciousness is understood as a reflection of the psyche of a variety of man's relationship with nature, which mediate its behaviour in the "natural world", and express axiological position of the subject of consciousness in relation to the natural world. (Panov, 2013, p. 380)

Artistic action can create a dialogue about the need for harmony to reach ecological consciousness. Art-making can also influence how we think about our planet and it can stimulate the development of our values. This is in complete agreement with the EfS goals developed at UNESCO (2012, p. 12) as it seeks to enable global citizens to find a balance within the complexities, controversies and inequities arising out of issues relevant to the environment, natural heritage, culture, society, and economy. The ABAR (Art-Based Action Research) approach was used in this research. It is a case-specific, developmental qualitative method. The process follows the traditions of action research (Jokela, Hiltunen, & Härkönen, 2015; Jokela & Huhmarniemi, 2019) when gathering data, resulting in findings that add to an understanding of the potential of the project, and the potential consequences of the actions taken when connecting these to theories. In the process of planning, designing, organising, developing, and observing actions and concluding with evaluation, the research cycle developed at the University of Lapland was followed when seeking answers to: How can artistic actions can strengthen community building and ecological consciousness in university settings? The documentary photos included in this article are presented with the consent of the participants.

Creative transformative education for sustainability in university settings

Sustainability and EfS are complex concepts that have been studied by a wide range of scholars (Tang et al., 2018). In EfS it is important to examine the interaction between the factors influencing human survival and well-being. Giddings, Hopwood and O'Brien (2002) proposed that the connection between human activity and well-being should be linked to ecological issues and the environmental limits of the earth. Well-being itself takes several different forms, including well-being as a state of mind or as a state of the earth, capability for action or a basic needs approach (Dodds, 1997). In EfS it is imperative to keep in mind that what is considered well-being and/or good life varies between individuals themselves, and between different societies and cultures.

Every school setting must develop its own goals towards EfS because it would be misleading to take the concept of the good life developed in one cultural context and apply it to other cultures (Jucker & Mathar, 2015).

Artistic actions can be based on value-judgements inherent in the 'good life' approach to sustainability (Jónsdóttir, 2017). When positioning well-being at the core of community discussions the role of sustainability within it can become more clearly visible (Kjell, 2011). Ideas of scholars such as Ingold (2019), Ryan and Deci (2000), Giddings, Hopwood, and O'Brien (2002) and Kjell (2011) include the term well-being in their definition of sustainability and discuss different interpretations of it, including how what counts as the good life can have a great influence on creative transformative projects. These scholars are all in line with Bonnett's (2021) focus on the emphasis on reframing and rethinking our own place in nature as this forms the fundamental implication for holistic education. The potential to become active members of society increases as people learn more about their local environment and become more caring about the places they live in (Sobel, 2005).

When setting sustainability goals in university settings, building a sense of community is

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

vital (SDSN, n.d.). Research confirms that when students in schools have a strong sense of community; they are more likely to develop strong environmental values that can support them to become academically motivated, resulting in student-driven initiatives (Durlak et al., 2011; Schaps et al., 1997; Solomon et al., 2000). University students need to be motivated to take personal actions to engage in sustainability related issues. Everyone needs to feel that it is important we all participate (Kestin et al., 2018). They should be encouraged to become the generation that changes the world as active citizens. Through the transformative learning experience of EfS the students experience shifts in their values as sustainable changes are generated. The learners and the teachers work together, and everyone's beliefs and attitudes develop (Sterling, 2001, 2008). Lawy and Biesta have advocated the idea of citizenship as practice. They argue that:

[Citizenship is] not a status or a possession, nor it is the outcome of a developmental and/or educational trajectory that can be socially engineered. It is a practice, embedded within the day-to-day reality of people's lives, interwoven and transformed over time in all the distinctive and different dimensions of their lives. (Lawy & Biesta, 2006, p. 47)

In transformative learning for sustainability, the learner builds on his or her prior lived experience, thus making the educational process relevant to the learners' lives. In order to learn to understand themselves and their environment the learner needs to get a sense of their own place. Both in the context of the environment and their physical place or home in the world. A deeper knowledge of the local environment, increases learners' potential to become active members of society because it encourages them to care about the places where people live (Sobel, 2005). To do so the focus is placed on reflecting upon solutions to real problems that people are experiencing (UNESCO, 2012).

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

Studies indicate that there are many ways to engage communities in sustainability (Jónsdóttir, 2017). The role of sustainability can be enhanced by positioning the concept of well-being clearly within sustainability discussions. EfS, therefore, benefits from an interdisciplinary approach with one activity consisting of several components; this could include activities based in literacy, equality, or citizenship. Research has shown that art is a perfect forum for creating a personal connection to the task through transformative learning settings (Brookfield, 2003; Jónsdóttir, 2017; Mezirow, 2009).

A critical creative approach has potential for both practical and transformative elements. The approach is designed to break away from mere theorizing and instead actively engage with the society we are examining for real transformation. Transformative learning using a critical approach that focuses on local settings allows students to learn to connect to places in meaningful ways (Wakeman, 2015). “We need new ways of thinking about our place in the world and the ways in which we relate to natural systems in order to be able to develop a sustainable world for our children and grandchildren.” (Raven, 2002, p. 957) This kind of relation is transformative learning, and can be described as a process in which individuals alter their frames of reference for understanding the world. In transformative learning, all learning processes point towards the need for change. Transformative learning opens up new lenses of awareness and strengthens our competence for understanding diverse knowledge (Mezirow, 2009).

When organising artistic actions for sustainability and well-being, it can be useful to employ ecological consciousness. Students learn to have a deep commitment to nature and to care for it because it feels natural for them to do it (Naess, 1993). To learn about ecology, you need to experience nature in depth; from this you learn to develop a commitment to revealing, looking after, respecting, and conserving nature (Harding, n.d.). When focusing on commitment with heart and mind in harmony with nature and the world, students learn to be agents of change for

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

a more sustainable society (ChangeNow, 2020). This change is for the future but also about the present, because both the present and the past are vital (UNESCO, 2012) to our ability to build up community well-being wherein the integrity of nature is respected.

The project *Walk the Space*

In 2019 I was asked to be part of the lecture series Meet the Artist initiated by Dr. Julianna Sandholm-Bark located at the Geneva campus of Webster University located. The lecture series aimed to introduce critical thinking to the 490 students from many different countries. Before accepting the offer, I suggested creating a participatory work which would then become a follow up to the lecture. By inviting interested students and staff to participate in the project I was able to weave together artistic actions for sustainability in general, with the specific sustainability role of the university; this gave the project a focus on finding a balance between well-being and the integrity of nature. Tim Ingold (2020) has stressed that the purpose of universities is to educate future generations of citizens to sustain a just and prosperous world. In universities, students should extend the learning process beyond their own courses to consider the very nature of things, including ways of living, justice, peace, ecology, and responsibility. I wanted to create settings where the participants would learn to weigh different sustainability facts against their personal experience and to translate them into principles, values, and practices.

In organising the project, I collaborated closely with both teachers and students. In this way, I reached out to diverse groups within the university. With this work, the aim was to develop ecological consciousness by bringing attention to how human interaction can further both the understanding and practice of creating well-being in the integrity of nature. The participants were first encouraged to rethink their own attitude towards nature because attitude is the one small thing that can make a tremendous impact in the way we live our lives; attitude can also have an impact on all areas of human lives. If we all have the right attitude towards life and the

living organisms around us, the earth can thrive and flourish.

The 6-P framework for community engagement

In the project, the 6P community framework was used to organise settings that engage students in sustainability (Too & Bajracharya, 2015). This framework helps identify the major factors used to address the issue and engage a university campus community towards sustainability. Introducing this framework to students gave them the opportunity to get familiar with a useful tool that can serve as the foundation for their future work practice, using dominant factors that drive community participation in sustainability projects (Too & Bajracharya, 2015).

The 6-P framework for community engagement is in line with the UN Sustainable Development Solutions Network suggestions for developing community engagement (Too & Bajracharya, 2015). It perfectly fulfils the vision of a sustainable campus and is applicable to any university community. This framework is also useful for the students once they leave the university and take up their careers since it can be applied to most workplaces. The framework includes factors that should be kept in mind when organising activities, and includes a) psychological needs that provide community members with knowledge and values concerning the environment; b) physical facilities that connect availability to green surroundings; c) participants' motivations which help organisers to focus on time availability and performance requirements; d) public perception regarding the social norms in the community settings; e) price mechanisms that look at the cost of choosing green; f) policies relating to regulatory and management support in the community as shown in figure 1.

The process

I used participatory art to interlink together artistic actions for sustainability and the role of universities, with a focus on finding a balance between well-being and the integrity of na-

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

Figure 1. 6P community engagement framework for understanding artistic actions Based on Bajracharya Too and Isara Khanjanasthiti, 2013, p. 62.

ture. When community-based art is created in university settings it is often used to develop an awareness of social issues, in this case, sustainability. It fosters a creative approach to problems; through the process of making art the participants find different ways to solve issues collaboratively (Krensky & Steffen, 2009).

The community art form was used to initiate dialogue and collaboration which allowed me to examine and develop students social cooperation while at the same time allowing for new dialogues among people experiencing the work. By their very nature, community-based art activities have the potential to create new information, as the participants continuously develop their attitudes through cooperation and discussions. It was not possible for me to project the effects and the result of the processes I used in advance (Sederholm, 1998) as the aesthetic of the participants' conclusions, supported by their sense of community, only materialised through the process.

Three different groups took part in the project. I was connected to the student-led environmental group which included both students and staff. In addition, I worked with a natural

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

science class and an art history class because staff from those two departments had been instrumental in setting up the lecture series. Both the classes are elective courses comprised of students from different degree programs. Each group began with a discussion of sustainability through the means of an interactive lecture. The concept of community-based art was introduced to the participants. The six principles in the P6 framework guided both my talk and our discussions when introducing sustainability to the students. By putting the well-being concept in the centre of the approach to sustainability the aim was to create a setting for awareness of both sustainability and well-being. This included discussions on how well-being can exist if we see or know our actions are harmful to our environment or other human beings. The discussion developed to consider how we as individuals can contribute to sustainable developments.

Many artists have used their work to communicate important insights into the relationships humans have with the natural environment (Pollak & MacNabb, 2000). Different artists were introduced, and we discussed how artworks can encourage the observer to rethink their perspectives and their connection to nature. I introduced ecological consciousness by telling the participants about the ideas of different philosophers such as Deep Ecology by Arne Naess (1993) and the ideas of the German biologist and philosopher, Andreas Weber. Weber displays a highly unconventional way of describing the natural world around him and how we as humans need to learn to communicate with nature. He puts love in the forefront as a foundational principle of biology, and asserts that this opens up a profoundly sensual understanding of the world. He is the spokesman for a tender practise of forging relationships, yearning for connections, and of expressing these desires through our bodies. “To love means to be fully alive... This is true of all realities — physical reality and the reality of thought, but also especially the reality of the biosphere, the reality of bodies.” (Weber, 2017, p. 43)

We discussed Weber’s hope for the world which is to see where nature and people live in greater harmony, more equitably and sustainably. We discussed and collectively created mind-

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

maps reflecting on what we can do to fulfil this wish. Several short exercises were organised involving students walking in the wood outside the university. Walking was used to engage them in diverse learning opportunities connected to aesthetic experiences and memories from other places that have significant meaning to them. Being outside the university buildings encouraged the participants to get to know the local environment around the university better and this measure, I hoped, would increase their potential to become active members of the university community while at the same time encouraging them to care about its spaces. During the walks outside we selected spaces and a situation where it was practical and possible to take action. It was also necessary to create a situation in which the participants would feel at ease, which is important for the dialogue (Hiltunen, 2008). Place-specific art must be considered from the participants' perspectives, respecting the community and its environment (Lippard, 1997).

Through these exercises, scholarly approaches were connected to emotional and tacit knowledge. By being out in the open air, discussing what causes unsustainable practices for the earth and reflecting on our experience we worked towards a common understanding. The personal relevance made it easier for the students to connect to their morals and values. Students proved themselves to be more enthusiastic when positive methods were used to search for alternatives to a current situation that was leading to unsustainable actions. Methods such as these allow holistic and creative thinking about both values and about solutions for the future (Jónsdóttir, 2017).

When organising artistic action, the artist acts as a guide for the group, and at the same time has to step back to allow the participants' concerns and knowledge to inspire the process based on their own interests (Knight & Schwarzman, 2017). We discussed how slogans can point out solutions and lead to a change in values and attitudes right now.

Discussions and connection to memories

An important part of the work was the dialogue. The role of the dialogue for the artistic actions was tangible because we all learned from the interactions (Kester, 2004). The participants brought with them prior knowledge and were able to refer to their experiences of nature concerning societal interventions. Some participants explained how being in nature can nourish awareness when others noted that they had never spent time out in nature.

As an outsider, I entered the field of sustainability through the perspective of art, a perspective that was new to the participants. I built a bridge between different communities of practice through the sharing of different stories, and I drew out their compassion, awareness, curiosity, and engagement; all of these perspectives were important for the group dynamics given that the participants all came from different programmes within the university. The discussions in the workshop were based on a transformative ideology (Mezirow, 2009), where the dialogue stimulated active, not passive learning, and encouraged the students to be critical, creative thinkers, with the capacity to engage in future learning. This means not only transmitting knowledge but also transforming and extending it as well (Boyer, 1990).

We began the discussions with an open lecture about my art and sustainability. Then, through dialogue, we started to make mind maps, reflecting on what the participants themselves could do to become more sustainable in their daily activities. The challenge was to create an atmosphere that allowed for sharing and developing knowledge, skill and ability. I encouraged the students to look at their findings about others and asked them to reflect on the importance of working together (SDG 17) through finding common experiences and exploring their daily lives.

In one of the walking exercises, I instructed the participants to go outside into the woods and take a photograph of a natural object that reminded them of a positive “home” experience in which they had felt connected to nature. When they came back inside, we looked at how our

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

experiences were connected. By allowing time for a moment of uncertainty the participants had the opportunity to discuss and decide what is meaningful in their life and living environment. This was an important step as the participants jointly defined the meaning of the process in which we were engaged. In the context of critical pedagogy, this exercise is an example of how walking can engage participants to become more attentive in society. Reflecting on our walking experience in connection to memories gives countless possibilities to discuss significant issues, both small and large, and to find and think about structures of power in our surroundings. By its nature, walking is interdisciplinary and allows the potential of discovering new and unexpected connections. The discussions also brought interaction into the process so that participants could connect to common desires to create a better future.

My aim was to create settings where the participants would be encouraged to think creatively about the ecology of the planet. I divided them into small groups where they discussed both the objects they had found and the photographs, discovering ways to connect them together. In the small group discussions, they showed concern about places and their environment, recollection, and identity through collaboration while questioning their values and ways of living. I used the dialogue to emphasise the importance of students selecting words that had special meaning to them and they thought were worth fighting for. They then used those words to form slogans. Some wrote down slogans in their own words while others used well-known environmental slogans. Freire (2000, p. 88) believed words had constitutive elements and the power to define our thinking. “Words are never politically neutral but have the power to both limit and expand social reality through the concepts and values they supply.” (Dale & Hyslop-Margison, 2011, p. 95)

By using their handwriting, and their stitchwork (figure 2) the work also became more personalised as each piece was unique.

Embroidering and exhibiting selected statements

The embroidery method was used as a tool to make the participants conclusions visible. Embroidery was introduced (figure 2) as the students wrote down their slogans on the fabric. Embroidered banners used the perception of embroidery as a creative outlet to communicate social messages. Through the process of making the banners, we worked with the ideas developed by the students through dialogue and their creative imagination to give voice to artistic expression. The embroidered messages aimed to transform and challenge preconceived notions within our society.

Figure 2. Collage of students working on their statements. Photographs Ásthildur Jónsdóttir, 2019.

Art has often been used in this way as a tool of emancipation and transformation (Koczanowicz, 2015). Collectively they contributed to the search for their understanding of sustainability. Working with ecological consciousness as a part of developing values and meanings has been proven to raise sustainable awareness (Dahl, 2016).

An outdoor installation was created transmitting the participants' voices. A small creek

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

runs through the wood around the university, providing rich flora and fauna. Installing the messages in natural surroundings aimed at captivating the visitors' attention with sensory input, creating settings for them to experience themselves as relational beings, and where they could receive meaning. By positioning the installation in a community setting, the participants' voices interacted with the people walking around the area, thus potentially bringing the participants into further dialogues with the community.

Most of the materials used were recycled or reclaimed, which acts as a commentary on consumerist "throwaway" culture; focusing on natural fabrics that can later return to their natural cycles. One participant stated in a later event that she found the project so inspiring that she is now upcycling clothes and different textiles herself. This corresponds to Ingold's (2011) ideas of focusing on alternative ways of working with materials, on being part of the materials, learning to appreciate their quality and their possibilities rather than translating from the virtual to the actual. Through the act of embroidering, some of the participants also created personal connections to family, including linking this activity to memories of their mothers or grandmothers.

Ecological thinking, consciousness, responsibility

Participants' embroidery can be divided into different themes. Some of the slogans included ecological facts about the relationship between man and nature that could lead to sustainability (figure 3). Some slogans suggested people should spend more time in nature (figure 4). Other works involved warnings. If people did not change their behaviour, the danger would be clear (figure 5). People interacting with the installation were encouraged to take action and change their way of living (figure 6–7). One participant's work was influenced by Weber's idea of the imbalance between humans and other living creatures (figure 8).

Many of the participants reflected on the 17th UN SDG - that it is important to work col-

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

Figure 3. Facts about sustainability, Photographs Ásthildur Jónsdóttir, 2019.

Figure 4. Slogans that encourage people to connect to nature. Photographs Ásthildur Jónsdóttir, 2019.

lectively towards sustainability with an overarching ecological consciousness. Visitors were encouraged to act (figure 9). The experience of the participants was diverse and at its best enabled an objective common point of view. It thus influenced the attitudes and values of the recipients positively. The process made learning relevant to the participants: “I was working with memories but did not realise it, when doing it. I realize my values can have more or a deeper meaning because I’m passing on something to the next generation.” (student interview)

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

Figure 5. Embroidered slogans with doomsday prediction. Photographs Ásthildur Jónsdóttir, 2019.

Figure 6. Embroidery suggesting way of living. Photographs Ásthildur Jónsdóttir, 2019.

Understanding and attachment to places varied from one participant to another and through dialogue, they found what united them and what made them different. Using the idea of walking around the university surroundings as a pedagogical tool resulted in engaged students, diverse learning opportunities and an aesthetic experience because there was both space and place for exploration.

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

Figure 7. Embroidery suggesting way of living. Photographs Ásthildur Jónsdóttir, 2019.

Figure 8. Plants compared to humans. Photographs Ásthildur Jónsdóttir, 2019

Conclusions

When the goal is to strengthen a community through artistic actions employing a community-based approach is vital in maintaining individuality and the locality, but acceptance of differences is essential to support the transition to sustainability (Hiltunen, 2008). The aim of the project *Walk the space* was to encourage the students to become conscious about the local ecology while at the same time learning about sustainability issues. In the project, this setting was

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

Figure 9. The importance of collective approach to ecological consciousness. Photographs Ásthildur Jónsdóttir, 2019.

used by the participants to experience meaningful dialogue within the natural environment, and it was very successful. The aim of bringing students from different departments together to discuss their visions for their community and its significance for their living environment was fully achieved.

The results of the project can be seen not only in the objects that were created but in the artistic actions and the process. Joint decision making ensured that the artwork would represent the principles of the participants in a place-specific artwork. The aim of the project was not to provide one final answer, but instead to develop new questions on how to respond to the ethical ecological challenges we are facing through the use of an art form that gives space for natural encounters and dialogue.

This community-based art project brought together different groups within Webster University Geneva. It stimulated connections and built bridges, both between individuals themselves, and also with the community. Hence, the process and the interaction, including the discussions, were as meaningful as the embroidered banners the more visible result. There was an overall sense of the importance of working together towards sustainable development which

ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

is also proposed in the 17th SDG goal. For the participants, the process of developing ideas on how to implement changes in their community by working collectively encouraged them to discuss their ideas in a safe and secure environment. Different elements were used to connect participants to nature and each other, inspiring collective creativity and environmental action.

Both the local media and the university newspaper covered the community-based project which encouraged the students and the local people to visit the exhibition. This project supports the conclusion that by combining artistic actions and connecting practice to theory, art has great potential in EfS. The leader of the local University environmental group said he had discovered the strong potential of art to address environmental issues and added that he wanted more projects like this one to address sustainability challenges within the community. Participatory community-based artistic actions can create settings for community stakeholders to work together. *Walk the Space* encouraged students to visit nature around the university and promised severance from busy daily lives. This created distance from the “real world” and allowed participants to actively engage in the process of changing their perspective. Overall, the installation addressed the urgent issues of our times and the importance of participation in finding solutions to the widespread environmental issues affecting our planet; this included the opportunity to reflect on our personal values and motivations, and raising the collective ecological consciousness of participants, and the larger community.

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ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

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ARTISTIC ACTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

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Kuerin matkassa: Paikkaperustainen taideteos ympäristökonfliktissa

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Biografia

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Timo Jokela toimii kuvataidekasvatuksen professorina Lapin yliopistossa sekä johtaa kansainvälistä Arktisen yliopiston Arctic Sustainable Art and Design temaattista verkostoa. Hänen tutkimusalaansa kuuluvat taidekasvatuksen lisäksi soveltava taide sekä ympäristö- ja yhteisötaide joita hän tarkastelee kestävän kehityksen näkökulmasta.

Abstrakti

Tarkastelun kohteena on yhteisötaiteellinen ympäristötaideteos Kuerin matka sekä siihen liittyvä samanniminen videoteos. Teos toteutettiin kesällä 2018 yhteistyössä Art Äkäslompolo taidetapahtuman kanssa. Tapahtumassa luodut taideteokset olivat kukin tavoillaan osa sosiaalisesti ja ympäristöllisesti sitoutunutta nykytaidetta, joka paikallisten toiveiden mukaisesti tarkastelee kriittisesti kylän läheisyyteen Pallas-Yllästunturin kansallispuiston reunaan suun-

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

niteltua Hannukaisen rautamalmikaivosta. Kuerin matka teos toteutettiin taideperustaisen toimintatutkimuksen menetelmin pyrkimyksenä luoda dialoginen tila ja tilanne, joka toimii pohjoisen ympäristökongfliktissa dekolonisaation ja kulttuurin elvyttämisen, revitalisaation, välineenä ja samalla lisäten yhteisön joustavuutta ja sopeutumista, resilienssiä, vääjäämättömässä muutoksessa. Tarkastelun keskiössä on arktisen taiteen käsite, jonka avulla pohditaan länsimaisen nykytaiteen toimintamuotojen ja pohjoisten ekokulttuureiden ja tietämisen tapojen kohtaamista.

Abstract

This article discusses a socially-engaged environmental art titled *Kuer's Journey* and a related video work. The art work was created in the summer of 2018 in collaboration with the Art Äkäslompolo art event. According to local wishes, the event critically considered the plan for the Hannukainen iron ore mine targeted next to the Äkäslompolo village near the Pallas-Yllästunturi National Park. *Kuer's Journey* was carried out using an art-based action research approach to create a dialogic space and situation that serves as a tool for decolonisation and cultural revitalisation, while increasing community resilience and adaptation, in inevitable environmental and cultural change in the Arctic. At the core of the article is the concept of Arctic art, which is used to reflect on the encounter between Western contemporary art practices and northern ecocultures and ways of knowing.

Asiasanat

Asiasanat: Yhteisötaide, ympäristötaide, ympäristökonflikti, pohjoinen ekokulttuuri, resilienssi, taideperustainen toimintatutkimus

Keywords

socially-engaged art, environmental art, environmental conflicts, resilience, art-based action research

Johdanto

Toimin sekä taiteilijana että tutkijana *Kuerin matka* teoksen toteutuksessa. Näen työskentelyni taideperustaisena metodina, jolla pyrin tuomaan moniäänisesti esille pohjoisen ekokulttuurin kerrostumia ja kytkeytymiä posthumanistisessa ja uusmaterialistisessa hengessä. Vaikka kokemushorisonttini aiheeseen on taustastani johtuen pohjoinen, tarkastelen teostani myös taiteen kontekstissa ja liitän sen länsimaisen taiteen jatkumoon.

Vuonna 2021 tuli kuluneeksi 100 vuotta saksalaisen monitaiteilija Josef Beuysin syntymästä (1921–1986). Hänen luomansa sosiaalisen veistoksen käsite on yksi aikamme taiteen avainkäsitteistä (Gyorody, 2014). Beuysin taiteen ekologinen vire ja hänen argumentointinsa installaation keinoin innosti aikanaan myös minua kehittämään yhteisöllistä ympäristötaidetta. Beuysin sosiaalinen ajattelun lisäksi teoksellani on yhteytensä myös hänen tunnettuihin eläinten kanssa toteutettuihin teoksiin. Hänen eläinten kanssa tapahtuvia performasseja on usein tulkittu alkupe räiskulttuureihin viittaavina shamanistisina akteina. Näillä teoksillaan Beuys häiritsi taiteilijan, teoksen ja yleisön rooleihin liittyviä konventioita. Minua eläinperformanssit saivat pohtimaan omaa suhdettani eläimiin pohjoisen kylän kasvattina; metsästäjänä ja kalastajana. Eläimet tulivat 1980-luvulta alkaen vähitellen osaksi taidettani ja sen tekemisen prosesseja. Viimeaikoina

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

posthumanismi on ajankohtaistanut eläinten kanssa tapahtuvan kanssatietämisen, -tutkimisen ja taiteen tekemisen (Demos, 2016; Huhmarniemi ym., 2021). Tuomalla uhanalaisen meritaime-
nen Kuerin matka teokseni keskiöön leikkittelin Ulmerin (2017) lanseeraamalla posthumanisti-
sen kanssatietämisen ja -tutkimisen ajatuksella; ”kalan silmällä näkee laajemmin”. Lähtökoh-
tana oli tärkeän vesibiologisen ulottuvuuden ohella se, että kalan kautta kaivoksen uhasta pu-
huminen avaisi helpommin myös ihmisten suun ja ehkä mielenkin, näin erityisesti paikallisten
pohjoisten miesten kohdalla.

Beyusiakin suurempi merkitys taide- ja taidekasvatusajatteluuni on ollut Gablikin (1995)
modernin taiteen kritiikillä ja Lacyn (1995, 2008) avauksella nostaa yhteisötaide (new genre
public art) osaksi keskustelua julkisesta taiteesta sekä Lippardin (1995) paikkasidonnaisen tai-
teen (place-specific art) määrittelyillä. Äkäslompolon tunturikylässä toteuttamani *Kuerin matka*
-teos sijoittuu julkiseen tilaan kansallispuistoon johtavan reitin varteen. Vaikka teos on yhteisö-
ja paikkasidonnainen ja tarkastelen sitä arktisen taiteen kontekstissa (Huhmarniemi & Jokela,
2020a, b), on sen teema myös yleismaailmallinen. Liitän teoksen keskusteluun, jota useat tutki-
jat ovat jo avanneet osoittamalla, kuinka ympäristökriisien aiheuttamat pelot, levottomuus, me-
lankolia ja stressi ovat lisääntyneet 2000-luvulla ja samalla pohtien lähestymistapoja ahdistuk-
sen purkuun ja positiivisen toimintakyvyn säilyttämiseen (Pihkala, 2017; Searle & Gow, 2010).
Pohjimmiltaan kysyn teoksellani ja sen analyysillä, millainen on taideperustainen toiminta, joka
huomio nopeasti muuttuvien pohjoisten ja arktisten yhteisöjen haasteet, kulttuurisen haurastu-
misen, epäoikeudenmukaisuuden kokemukset ja antaa paikallisille tilan puhua tulevaisuudes-
taan omilla asuinsijoillaan konfliktoituneissakin tilanteissa.

Taustateoria

Artikkelissa keskeisenä oleva arktisen taiteen käsite otettiin käyttöön johtamani Arktisen
yliopiston temaattisen verkoston Arctic Sustainable Arts and Design (ASAD) tutkimuksen pii-

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

rissä (ks. Jokela & Coutts, 2018) ja selvennettiin Arctic Arts Summit 2019 kongressin keskusteluissa (Huhmarniemi & Jokela, 2020a, 2020b). Olen korostanut arktisen taiteen yhteyttä Lacyn lanseeraaman uuden genren julkisen taiteen -ajatteluun tutkiessani alueen nykyaikaisia interventioita; julkista taidetta ja esityksiä, jotka aktivismina kiinnittyvät ajankohtaisiin arktisiin kysymyksiin eri puolilla sirkumpolaarista aluetta (Jokela ym., 2021).

Arktisessa taiteessa on lähtökohtaisesti posthumanistisia pyrkimyksiä ihmisen ja luonnon välisen yhteyden ja ekologisen tietoisuuden vahvistamiseen. Globaalit ympäristökriisit ovat haastaneet jo tovin myös kasvatusteoriota ja opetusmenetelmiä niin kansainvälisesti (Jickling & Sterling, 2017) kuin meillä Suomessa (Huhmarniemi ym. 2021; Värri, 2018). Uusmaterialismi ja posthumanismi on todettu tärkeiksi nouseviksi suuntauksiksi yhteiskuntatieteissä (Gamble & Hanan, 2019). Myös kasvatustieteellisessä tutkimuksessa muun muassa Ulmer (2017) kehoittaa kehittämään kanssatietämisen ja -tutkimisen menetelmiä muiden kuin ihmisten (other than human) kanssa toimimalla. Uusmaterialismia voidaan pitää poikkitieteellisenä pyrkimyksenä muuttaa lähtökohta oletuksia ihmisen ja ympäröivän maailman suhteista (Fox & Alldred, 2019). Ymmärrän posthumanismin taiteen ja taidekasvatuksen tutkimuksen kentällä pitkään vallinneen sosiaalis-humanistisen paradigman rinnalle nousevaksi paradigmaksi, joka siirtää huomion ihmiskeskeisyydestä ihmislajin ulkopuolelta tapahtuvaksi tarkasteluksi ja samalla haastaa myös taiteen menetelmiä (ks. Demos, 2016).

Arktisen taiteen määrittely liittyy läheisesti keskusteluun kestävästä kehityksestä. Arktisella alueella kestävä kehityksen käsite on poliittisesti ongelmallinen, etenkin arktisen alueen kulttuuri- ja aluepolitiikassa (Huhmarniemi & Jokela, 2020a). Arktisen alueen tutkimuksessa niin kestävä kehitys kuin arktinen kestävyyskin määritellään monin eri tavoin ja tarkoituksiin (Fondahl & Wilson, 2017; Gad ym., 2019; Tennberg ym., 2019). Tällöin keskustelu liittyy usein luonnonvaroihin sekä ekologisiin ja taloudellisiin ulottuvuuksiin, joskus sosiaalisiin kysymyksiin, kulttuurin jäädessä vähemmälle huomiolle. Huhmarniemi ja Jokela (2020a) pai-

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

nottavat, että kulttuurinen kestävyys on tärkeä arktisen alueen kestävyiden neljäs ulottuvuus – ei vain alkuperäiskulttuureiden traditioiden näkökulmasta. Soini ja Birkeland (2014) ovat tutkineet kulttuurisen kestävä kehityksen määritelmiä ja heidän mukaan kulttuurista kestävyttä tulee ajatella, joko itsenäisenä kestävä kehityksenä tai osana ekologista, sosiaalista ja taloudellista lähestymistapaa. Tässä artikkelissa painottuu Soinin ja Birkelandin (2014) kategorisoinnista kulttuurisen kestävyiden näkökulmista paikkaperustaisuutta painottava linja, jolloin jokaisessa taidetoiminnan kohteena olevassa paikassa on arvioitava omat tarpeensa, oikeudet ja vastuut kestävämmän elämän kannalta (Härkönen ym., 2018; Härkönen, 2021).

Paradigman muutos kohti posthumanismia ja ajankohtaistuneet kysymykset kulttuurisesta kestävästä kehityksestä ovat johtaneet myös arvioimaan uudelleen sitä, kuinka nykytaidetta tulisi opettaa kouluissa ja yliopistoissa suhteessa arktisen ja pohjoisen ekokulttuureihin. Monet tutkijat ovat nähneet, että pohjoisessa paikallisella ja perinteisellä tiedolla (Helander-Renvall & Markkula, 2017; Valkonen & Valkonen, 2018) ja erityisesti alkuperäiskansojen tietojärjestelmällä (Indegenous Knowledge System) (Virtanen & Seurujärvi-Kari, 2019) on paljon annettavaa kestäväälle kehitykselle.

Arktisen yliopiston ASAD verkoston piirissä on käytetty pohjoisen tietämisen käsitettä (Northern Knowledge) kuvaamaan alueen ekokulttuuriin perustuvaa ymmärrystä ja tietoa, joka koostuu yhteisistä perinteistä, sosiaalisista järjestelmistä ja luonnon tarjoumien kestävästä käytöstä (Jokela, 2018; Huhmarniemi & Jokela, 2020a,b). Tällöin tarkastellaan miten kulttuuriperintö (Fairclough, 2009; Fairclough ym., 2014; Smith, 2006) tai vaikkapa maisemasuhde (Ingold, 1993) ilmenevät ja miten ymmärrys ilmentymistä voi kestävämmillä tavoilla edistää pohjoisen maaseudun ja haja-asutusalueen kehittämistä (Jokela ym., 2022; Vodden ym., 2015). Pohjoinen tietäminen ei takaa lähtökohtaisesti luonnon tarjoumien kestävä käyttöä, vaan se muodostaa lähtökohdan jatkuvalla oppimiselle kohti kestävä tulosta. Huhmarniemen ja Jokelan (2020a,b) mukaan pohjoinen tieto sisältää muun muassa materiaaliseen ja henkiseen kult-

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

tuuriin liittyvän hiljaisen tiedon. Taiteessa ja käsitöissä tämä ilmenee usein visuaalisena kielenä sekä tarinoina, jota voidaan jakaa uudelle sukupolvelle, mutta myös alueen uusille asukkaille. Pohjoinen tietojärjestelmä eroaa alkuperäiskansojen tiedosta, koska paikallinen tieto, joka on integroitu ekokulttuuriin ja eläviin perinteisiin, on myös muiden alueen asukkaiden luomaa, ylläpitämää ja välittämää. Pohjoisen tietämisen käsitteessä alueen yhteisöjen tavat tuottaa tietoa integroituvat nykyisiin tieteen ja taiteen pyrkimyksiin kohti kansatietämisen tapojen kehittämistä.

Tässä artikkelissa muut keskeiset teoreettiset käsitteet, joita käytän avaamaan arktisen taiteen agendaa toteuttavaa taideinterventiotani, ovat dekolonisaatio (Smith, 1999; Demos, 2016), revitalisaatio (Auclair & Fairclough, 2015) sekä resilienssi (Pretty, 2011). Avaan näitä tarkemmin artikkelini diskussio-osassa.

Kontekstina Art Äkäslompolo ja Hannukainen rautakaivoksen suunnitelmat

Yhteisötaiteellinen ympäristötaideteos *Kuerin matka* toteutettiin Kolarin kunnan Äkäslompolon kylässä kesällä 2018 yhteistyössä Art Äkäslompolo taidetapahtuman kanssa (Huhmar-niemi, 2021). Tapahtumassa luodut taideteokset ovat kukin omalla tavallaan osa sosiaalisesti ja ympäristöllisesti sitoutunutta nykytaidetta, joissa paikallisten toiveiden mukaisesti tarkasteltiin kriittisesti suunniteltua Hannukaisen rautamalmikaivosta kylän ja Pallas-Yllästunturin kansallispuiston läheisyydessä. Taiteilijoiden vetämä yhteisötaidetapahtuma järjestettiin ensimmäisen kerran kesällä 2017. Vuonna 2018 tapahtuman emäntänä toimi kahvilayrittäjä ja nukketaitelija Lea Kaulanen ja taiteilijat loivat yhdessä kyläläisten kanssa ympäristötaidetta ja installaatioita hänen omistamalleen kauniille mäntykankaalle. Tapahtuma perustuu yhteisölliseen ja sosiaalisesti sitoutuneen julkisen taiteen (Lacy, 1995, 2008) sekä yhteisötaidekasvatuksen paikkaperusteisiin strategioihin (Jokela, 2013; Hiltunen, 2010). Omalla teoksellani halusin tarjota kyläläi-

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

sille tilan ja paikan keskustella ja tuoda esille näkemyksiään ja huoliaan kaivossuunnitelmiin liittyen.

Hannukaisen kaivoshanke ei ole puheenaihe vain Äkäslompolossa, eikä Hannukainen liioin ainoa puheenaiheena oleva kaivoshanke pohjoisessa. Kaivoksilla on monia kytkeytymisiä paikallisten elämään ja ajankohtaiseen aiheeseen monia näkökulmia (Mononen & Suopajärvi, 2016). Similä ja Jokinen (2018) toteavat kaivosten vastustusten olevan tyypillistä matkailupaikkakunnilla, sillä kaivoksen avaaminen muuttaisi maisemaa, joka on elinehto matkailulle. Hannukaisen kaivoksen ja Kolarin osalta Jokinen (2018) painottaa, että kunta on voimakkaasti jakautunut; kaivosta vastustetaan siellä, missä matkailun työpaikat ovat ja missä asukasluku on nousussa. Kaivoksella on kannattajia kirkonkylässä ja etäämmällä, missä matkailun merkitys on vähäinen ja väestökehitys negatiivinen.

Vaikka asukkaiden huoli on paljolti matkailuelinkeinon taloudellisessa tulevaisuudessa, on aktiivisten kaivoksen vastustajien piirissä huomion kohteena ollut kaivostoiminnan vaikutus erityisesti Suomen ja Ruotsin yhteisiin vesialueisiin (Pro Ylläs, 2021). Juuri Pro-Ylläs nostaa kaivoskysymyksen Kolarin ja jopa valtakunnan rajoja suuremmaksi. Hannukaisen kaivoksen jätevedet suunnitellaan laskettavaksi 10 kilometriä pitkää putkea pitkin luonnoltaan herkkään ja ainutlaatuisen Tornion-Muonionjokeen. Pro Ylläksen (2021) mukaa purkuveden laatu on sen metallipitoisuuksien vuoksi kalojen surma ja Hannukainen Mining Oy ei ole selvittänyt kantaattien vaikutusta jokeen.

Pro Ylläksen mukaan Tornio-Muonionjokeen kutemaan nousevat luonnonlohettuottavat noin puolet koko Itämeren alueen lohisaaliista ja sitä kalastavat kaikki Itämeren lohenkalastukseen osallistuvat valtiot. Lohi ei kuitenkaan ole huomion keskiössä, vaan suunniteltu kaivos on Pro Ylläksen mukaan erityinen uhka Tornion-Muonionjoen äärimmäisen uhanalaiselle meritaimenelle. Äkäslompolon läpi virtaava Äkäsjoki on meritaimenen keskeisin lisääntymisalue. Äkäsjoki ja sen sivujoki Kuerjoki tuottavat 20–35 prosenttia kaikista Tornion-Muonionjoen vesis-

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

töalueen meritaimenista. Hannukaisen kaivos sijaitsee Äkäsjoen ja Kuerjoen välittömässä läheisyydessä eikä meritaimen tule kestäämään talvisen elinympäristön tilan huonontamista. Kaivoksen myötä pohjavesi alenee ja sen pelätään lopettavan jokien talvisen virtauksen. Tällöin syyskutuisen meritaimenen talveksi joenpohjaan jäänyt kutu tuhoutuu sen kehittymistä edellyttävän jokiluonnon kadotessa. On ymmärrettävää, että monet, niin paikalliset kuin asiasta huolta kantavat ei-paikkakuntalaiset, samaistuvat kaivoksen uhkaan juuri meritaimenen kautta.

Kuva 1, 2. Vuoroin suvantoina, nivoina, koskina ja kallioiden välistä syöksyvinä linkkoina virtaavat Äkäsjoki ja Kuerjoki ovat meritaimenen tärkeitä kutujokia. Kuvat: Timo Jokela, 2018.

Metodologiana taideperustainen toimintatutkimus

Metodologisesti *Kuerin matka* -projekti on luonteeltaan taideperustainen toimintatutkimus, jonka menetelmiä on kehitetty Lapin yliopistossa vastaamaan kuvataidekasvatukseen, yhteisöllisen taidekasvatukseen ja soveltavan taiteen tiedonintresseihin (Hiltunen, 2010; Jokela, 2013, 2018, 2019; Jokela ym., 2019; Jokela & Huhmarniemi, 2018, 2020). Taideperustainen toimintatutkimus on enemmän tutkimusstrategia kuin yksittäinen tutkimusmetodi. Menetelmä pyrkii kehittämään taiteilija-opettaja-tutkijan ja taiteilija-tutkijan ammatillisia työskentelytapoja. Sillä on yhteisiä piirteitä kansainvälisen taiteellisen tutkimuksen, taideperustaisen tutkimuksen ja toimintatutkimuksen kanssa. Kaikissa näissä tutkimusmenetelmissä käytäntö ja tutkimus on sa-

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

manaikaista ja tutkimusaiheet koskettavat taiteen ohella muita akateemisia aloja, kuten yhteiskuntatieteitä ja kasvatustiedettä tai esimerkiksi aluekehitystyötä.

Taideperustaisen toimintatutkimuksen strategialla tähdätään tutkimukseen, joka tuottaa käytännön muutosta sekä pätevää ja perusteltua tietoa, ymmärrystä ja uutta osaamista, jota kyseisen muutoksen edistäminen edellyttää. Taidekasvatuksen ja yhteisötaiteen työtapoja on sovellettu toteutetuissa tutkimuksissa muun muassa aluekehityksen ja hyvinvointityön menetelmiksi (Hiltunen, 2010). Kehittämistutkimukseen on sisällynyt paikkasidonnaisia ja yhteisöllisiä taideprojekteja, joihin on osallistunut muun muassa kylä-, koulu-, työ- ja yritys-elämän yhteisöjä. Kehittämistehtäviä on määritelty yhdessä yhteisöjen jäsenten kanssa. Tämä on yksi taideperustaisen toimintatutkimuksen lähtökohdista: yhteisön jäsenet ovat osallisia tutkimus- ja kehittämisprosessiin.

Jokela ja Huhmarniemi (2018, 2020) kuvaavat taideperustaisen toimintatutkimuksen syklisesti eteneväksi tutkimus- ja kehittämisprosessiksi. Sen ensimmäinen vaihe sisältää tutkittavaan ilmiöön perehtymistä, tavoitteiden ja tutkimustehtävien määrittelyä, tutkimuksen organisointia, toiminnan suunnittelua sekä teoreettista ja taiteellista taustatyötä. Toisessa vaiheessa edetään taiteelliseen työskentelyyn tai vastaaviin interventioihin. Kolmannessa vaiheessa ja useimpien käytännön toimintaa limittyen kerätään toiminnasta relevantti tutkimusaineisto. Neljännessä syklissä toiminnasta kerätty aineisto analysoidaan, tulokset käsitteellistetään ja kirkastetaan seuraavia kehittämistavoitteita ja täsmennetään jatkotoimenpiteitä saavutettujen tutkimustulosten avulla. Tämän artikkelin tutkimusaineisto on kerätty *Kuerin matka* -teoksen suunnittelu- ja toteutusvaiheiden aikana ja keskeisenä aineistona on ollut toteutuksesta ja sen ympärillä käydyistä keskusteluista tehdyt videotallenteet, jotka ovat olleet myös *Kuerin matka* -videoteoksen pohjana.

Teos rakentuu

Tultuani valituksi yhdeksi Art Äkäslompolo tapahtuman taiteilijaksi aloitin työni valitsemalla aiheen, jonka kautta kaivoskiistaa käsitteisin. Konfliktoituneen matkailun ja kaivosteollisuuden asemasta pyrin nostamaa teoksellani aluksi esiin paikallisten asukkaiden ekokulttuurisen elämismailman. Aloitin työni käyttämällä taideperustaiselle toimintatutkimukselle, mutta myös visuaaliselle etnografialle, tyypillisiä tutkimusmenetelmiä (Jokela, 2018, 2019). Visuaalinen kartoitus ja kylän ilmeen, toimeentulon, perinteiden ja tarinoiden analysointi kiinnostivat paikallisia ja auttoivat ottamaan heidät mukaan tutkimukseen. Aloitin työni tapaamalla muutamia kylän historiasta perillä olevia henkilöitä. Vuorovaikutus oli erittäin luontevaa, koska olen kotoisin Äkäslompolon kaltaisesta pohjoisesta kylästä. Oma apunsa oli myös Yllästunturin luontokeskuksen *Meän elämää* -näyttelyllä, joka monikerroksellisesti kertoo kylän elämästä. Kylästä on koottu myös ansiokas kuvateos Kalervo Niskakosken ja Keijo Taskisen toimittama *Äkäslompolo. Seitsemän tunturin kylä ajan virrassa* (2012). Kirja toimi myös oppaana ja avaimena teemoihin, joista asukkaiden kanssa keskustelin teosta hahmottaessa ja yhteistyötä rakentaessa. Kartoituksen pohjalta valitsemassani aiheessa yhdistyi paikannimistö ja kaivoksen uhka vesistölle. Kylän kupeella kohoaa Kuertunturi, sen sivuitse virtaa Kuerjoki. Useimmille nimet eivät enää kerro tarinaansa. Kueri tai kujeri on saamenkielestä periytyvä meritaimenen jo kadonnut vanha paikallinen nimitys, joka nyt elää enää paikannimissä. Merestä nousevan kalan suuresta merkityksestä kertoo jo se, että se on antanut nimensä joen lisäksi kylän vieressä kohoavalle tunturillekin.

Kueri nousi keskusteluissa vesistöihin kohdistuvan uhkan ikoniksi, ehkä myös siksi, että aikanaan Kuerlinkan ”koppapyynnistä” oli käyty oikeusprosessi, jonka kalanpyytäjät olivat voittaneet. Halusin tehdä teoksestani eräänlaisen muistomerkin jokeen nousevalle kalalle, joka nyt oli voimakkaasti uhattuna. Pohjoisen kylmissä puhtaissa virtaavissa vesissä kutevat lohikalat ovat koko sirkumpolaarisella alueella uhattuina ei vain luonnonresurssien hyödyntämisen

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

Kuva 3. Teoksen luonnokset syntyvät paikan, visuaalisen aineiston ja paikallisten kanssa käytöjen keskustelujen pohjalta. Kuvat: Timo Jokela, 2018, kollaasi Emmi Kinnunen, 2021.

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

Kuva 4. Kuvakaappauksia *Kuerin matka* -videoteoksesta (2019), jonka käsikirjoitti Timo Jokela, kuvasi Mirja Hiltunen ja leikkasi Ahti Nykänen. Kuvakollaasi. Emmi Kinnunen, 2021.

vaan myös ilmastonmuutoksen vuoksi. Yhdistelin luonnoksissani Kuerin tarinan aiemmin tallentamiini siperialaisten shamaanihautojen konstruktioihin ja lintupylväisiin, jotka suomalais-ugrilaiset kansat tuntevat *sielunlintuna* (Lempiäinen, 2008). Kuerista tuli luonnoksissani ”sielukala”, joka puolestaan nousi paikallisten kanssa keskusteluissa joen luonnontilan ja nousukalakantojen hyvinvoinnin symboliksi.

Suunnittelin *Kuerin matka* -teoksen toteutuksen siten, että se muodosti myös paikallisille luontevan tilanteen tulla avuksi tai muuten vaan seisauttamaan työmaan äärelle. Valitsin teoksen toteutustavaksi puun ja perinteisen hirsirakentamistekniikan, jotta voisin aktivoida erityisesti

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

paikallisten miesten jutustelua tutun työn parissa. Mirja Hiltunen dokumentoi teoksen toteutuksen vaiheet ja sen lomassa syntyneet keskustelut. Puheet paikallisten kanssa kulkivat varovaisen ohjailun ja teemoittelun myötä kaivosuhkasta marjanpoimintaan, kaloista kunnallispolitiikkaa sekä omista kokemuksista koko alueen ekokulttuurin muutoksen pohdintaa. Tallennetut keskustelut muodostivat aineiston niin tälle artikkelille kuin *Kuerin matka* -videoteokselle. Lisäksi teos tarjosi puitteet tuoda kaivossuunnitelmaan liittyviä uhkia esille niistä useimmiten aivan tietämättömille kansallispuiston reitillä kulkeville matkailijoille.

Meritaimenen eli kuerin tarina ei päättynyt Ars Äkäslompolo tapahtuman loppuessa. Teos on paikallaan kansallispuistoon vievällä reitillä ja sen ovat nähneet tuhannet ihmiset. Videoteosta on ollut esillä useissa näyttelyissä myös kansainvälisillä foorumeilla. Ja mikä tärkeintä Hannukaisen rautakaivoksen suunnitelmiin kriittisesti suhtautuvat paikalliset tahot ovat innolla jatkaneet yhteistyötä Lapin yliopiston kanssa. Syksyllä 2021 Äkäsjoen sillankorvaan, kylän keskustaan, syntyi Lapin yliopiston taidetyöpajassa pajuveistos, kun kaivoshankkeen vastustajat kutsuivat opiskelijaryhmän Äkäslompoloon. Teoksen teema käsitteli joen vesibiologiaa ja pääroolissa oli jälleen kueri eli meritaimen.

Valmiin teoksen ympärillä

Kuerin matka -teos voidaan nähdä nykytaiteellisena beuysilaisena sosiaalisena veistoksena, prosessina, jonka mukana olleet ihmiset toiminnallaan loivat. Syntyessään pohjoisen konfliktituneessa tilanteessa on teoksessa myös monia nykytaiteen ja pohjoisen ekokulttuurin kohtaamisen tasoja, jotka ansaitsevat lähempää tarkastelua arktisen taiteena.

Kuerin matka -teoksen juuret löytyvät ympäristötaiteesta, itsenäisestä taidemuodosta, joka luotiin 1960- ja 1970-luvuilla, kun maa- ja performanssitaiteilijat alkoivat luoda taideteoksia gallerioiden ja taidemuseoiden ulkopuolella. Taiteentutkija Malcolm Andrews (1999) mukaan tällaiset ympäristötaideteokset edustavat ympäristön ja taiteilijan suhdetta. Taideteos ei ole vain

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

Kuva 5, 6, 7. Teos valmistuu pala kerrallaan katselijoiden kanssa jutustellen ja välillä moottorisahan ja kirveen kanssa työskennellen. Kuva: 5. Mirja Hiltunen, kuvat 6. ja 7. Santeri Happonen, 2018.

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

Kuva 8, 9. Art Äkäslompolo tapahtuman avajaisyleisö tarkastelemassa valmista teosta ja kuuntelemassa tekijän taustoitusta aiheeseen. Kuva 8. Mirja Hiltunen, 2018, kuva 9. Timo Jokela, 2018.

ulos sijoitettu taiteellinen esine; sen sijaan sen merkitys syntyy sen suhteesta ympäristöönsä. Lisäksi taideteos luo sijoitusympäristönsä luonteen – tässäkin tapauksessa teos luo paikan kulkureittien varrelle kansallispuiston kupeeseen, Äkäsjoen välittömään läheisyyteen, ja sitä voidaan pitää ympäristötaideteoksena.

Ympäristötaiteen olemuksen lisäksi teoksen toteutus noudatteli Lacyn (1995, 2008) kuvailemaa julkisen taiteen lähestymistapaa (new genre public art) ja Lippardin (1997) esittämiä paikkasidonnaisen yhteisötaiteen periaatteita. Näitä lähestymistapoja käyttäessään taiteilijat viittaavat taideteoksissaan tietyn yhteisön tai paikan sosiaalisiin haasteisiin ja ottavat paikalliset toimijat mukaan taiteellisiin prosesseihin. Näin tapahtui myös *Kuerin matka* -teoksen toteutuksessa. Tästä näkökulmasta teostani voidaan pitää yhteisötaiteena, johon paikalliset osallistuivat, mutta myös kansallispuiston kulkureitille sijoittuvana julkisen taiteen teoksena.

Kuerin matka -teoksessa oli keskeisenä ulottuvuutena alueen miehille tuttu puurakentaminen sekä moottorisahan ja kirveen käyttö. Sahasin ja veistin teokseni 2–3 päivää kestävästä julkisena performanssina, johon osallistujat ja yleisö tuli kukin tavoillaan mukaan. Tässä tekemisen

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

ja keskustelun dialogissa meritaimen, kueri, muodosti beuysilaisen ”eläinkestelukumppanin”, vaikka kueri olikin mukana vain tarinoina ja muisteluksina. Käsityötaidon ja paikallisten kalatarinoiden yhdistäminen tarjosi hyvän lähtökohdan vuorovaikutuksen syntymiselle luontevalla tavalla. Huhmarniemen ja Jokela (2020a) mukaan arktisen taiteen keskeisenä tavoitteena on etsiä sopivia tapoja käsitellä sensitiivisesti ympäristö- ja sosiokulttuurisia kysymyksiä taiteen ja taiteen kasvatuksen metodologioiden avulla samalla edistäen kestävästä kehitystä ja tunnistuen pohjoisen ja arktisen alueen kulttuurinen monimuotoisuus. Huhmarniemen ja Jokelan (2020a, b) mukaan arktinen taide tarjoaakin vaihtoehtoisen tavan nähdä taide, muotoilu ja käsityöt toisiinsa tukevin ja integroituina sen sijaan, että taiteilija seuraisi dualistista länsimaista kulttuuria, jossa taide, muotoilu ja käsityö erotetaan omiin aloihinsa, niin käytännössä, kuin tutkimuksessa ja koulutuksessakin. *Kuerin matka* -teoksen suunnittelussa ja toteutuksessa kulttuurisen ja sosiaalisen kestävyysajattelu oli läsnä: teos toteutui yhteistyössä paikallisten asukkaiden kanssa arvostamalla heidän taitojaan, tietämystään ja tarinoitaan. Tämä synnytti luottamusta ja avautumista keskustelulle myös konfliktin aiheuttaneesta kaivoshankkeesta ja sen uhkista.

Arktiseen taiteeseen kiinteästi liittyvä pohjoisen tietojärjestelmän käsite (Huhmarniemi & Jokela, 2020b) viittaa toisiinsa liittyvään ekologiseen ja kulttuuriseen tietoon, jota *Kuerin matka* -teoksen toteutuksessa sovellettiin taiteen luomisprosessiin. Pohjoinen tieto korostaa, että tietoa ei aina jaeta suullisesti, vaan ne voidaan välittää myös visuaalisten merkkien, symbolien, materiaalivalinnan ja rakennustekniikoiden avulla. Tällä visuaalisesti muotoillulla kielellä on kommunikatiivista merkitystä sekä yhteisössä että sen ulkopuolella. Käsityön kieli on pohjoisessa tärkeä perinteiden, uskomusten ja maailmankatsomusten jakamisessa (kts. esim. Minnakhmetova ym., 2019; Schilar & Keskitalo, 2018) ja paikallisten aineellinen kulttuuri voi kantaa myös henkistä ja jopa uskonnollista sisältöä (Helander-Renval, 2009). *Kuerin matka* -teoksen tarkoitus ei ollut vain välittää pohjoista tietoa vaan myös uudistaa sitä. Pohjoinen tieto nähtiin tässä yhteydessä performatiivisena prosessina, jossa sitä yhdistettiin nykytaiteeseen. Siksi

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

Kuerin matka teoksen kaltaiset prosessit voidaan nähdä myös Danielsin ym. (2015) sekä Jokelan (2018) kuvaamana paikkaperusteisena alueellisena kehittämissstrategian toteuttajana, jonka ytimessä oli tässä tapauksessa Äkäslompolon kylä.

Kuerin matka -teoksen yhteisöllisen toteutus ja esille arvostaen nostettu *pohjoinen tieto* voidaan ymmärtää myös pyrkimyksenä kohti dekolonisaatiota. Teoksen toteutus seuraili Smithin (1999) näkemystä dekolonisaatiosta prosessina, joka perää hallinnollisten toimien rinnalla myös kulttuurisen ja psykologisen kolonialismin purkamista. Dekolonisaatio on askel kohti itsemääräämisoikeutta mutta myös kohti yhteisöllistä hyvinvointia. Tämä tarkoittaa, että paikallisten on itse rakennettava kulttuurinsa perusteista tiedostaen alueensa mahdollinen kolonialistinen historia. *Kuerin matka* -teoksen yhteydessä nousi esille se, kuinka Äkäslompolon tunturikylän asukkaat ovat kokeneet, ja yhä kokevat, kolonisaatiota ei vain kaivosyhtiön taholta, vaan myös oman kuntansa sisällä. Kolarin kunta ja enemmistö kirkonkylän asukkaista suhtautuu myönteisesti kaivoshankkeeseen. Jokinen (2018) onkin todennut jännitteiden vallitsevan tunturikylien ja Kolarin kunnan sekä kirkonkylän välillä

Dekolonisaatio on tärkeä ulottuvuus alkuperäiskansojen kulttuuriaktiivisuuden yhteydessä (Smith, 1999). Sillä on oma roolinsa myös Lapissa vuosisatoja eläneiden ei-alkuperäiskulttuureiden parissa. Perustuen tehtyihin tutkimuksiin Huhmarniemi ja Jokela (2020a) ovatkin ehdottaneet, että vastaavia dekolonisaatioprosesseja kuin alkuperäiskulttuureiden parissa on tehty, tulisi tavoitella pohjoisessa myös muissa kuin alkuperäiskansojen yhteisöissä. Vaikka *Kuerin matka* -teoksessa on dekolonisaation piirteitä, on ehkä hedelmällisempää tarkastella sitä revitalisaation ilmentymänä.

Revitalisaatio on keskeinen pyrkimys palauttaa perinteiden arvostusta vallitsevassa muuttuneessa sosiokulttuurisessa tilanteessa. Auclair ja Fairclough (2015) ovat kuvanneet revitalisaatiota käytännöksi, joka uudistaa perinteitä, jotka ovat osa yhteisön sosiaalista rakennetta. Arktisessa taiteessa revitalisaatio ei tarkoita paluuta historialliseen kulttuuriin ja identiteettiin, joka

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

olisi aito, alkuperäinen tai sekoittumaton. Revitalisaatio perustuu aina historian tulkintaan, joka muuttuu historiallisen tiedon lähteiden sekä henkilökohtaisten ja yhteisöllisten käsitysten, arvostusten ja arvojen mukaan. Näin myös Äkäslompolon matkailun muokkaamassa kyläyhteisössä.

Katsaus Arktisen alueen nykyaikaiseen tuo esille merkityksellisen tavan ammentaa inspiraatiota menneisyydestä (Guttorm, 2015; Hansen, 2016; Igloliorte, 2019). Itse asiassa aikamme nykyaikainen ja kulttuuriset käytännöt, ollessaan koulutuksen tai kulttuuripalveluiden tuotteita, voivat ajan myötä muuttua käytänteiksi ja lopulta perinteiksi. Siksi revitalisaation käsite on mielenkiintoisella tavalla perinteiden ja innovaatioiden risteyksessä. Arktisessa taiteessa tämä tarkoittaa usein nykyaikaisten sekä perinteisten luontoa kunnioittavien työtapojen yhdistämistä taiteeseen (Huhmarniemi & Jokela, 2020a, b; Jokela ym., 2021). Revitalisaatio on myös keskeinen lähestymistapa kulttuurisen kestävyuden tavoittelussa; se on usein sukupolvien ja kulttuurien välistä. *Kuerin matka* -teoksessa tarkoituksena on välittää pohjoista tietojärjestelmää, ei vain uusille sukupolville ja vaan myös uusille yhteisön jäsenille ja kalastuksen perinne saanut uuden käyttötarkoituksen. Muistelemalla ei elvytetty itse kalastusta vaan lähestyttiin kylän ja kokonaisen alueen identiteetin vahvistamista. Revitalisaation voidaan ymmärtää oppimisprosessina, jonka keskiössä on kulttuurinen vuorovaikutus.

Konfliktoituneessa tilanteessa Äkäslompolon asukkaiden kulttuurisen identiteetin ja ekologian pohjaa ravistavat muutokset. Tosin kaivosalan ei ole ainut muutosvoima vaan sitäkin voimakkaampi lienee matkailu. Stephen (2018) näkee tämän haastavaksi tilanteeksi kaikkialla arktisella alueella. Suurien ympäristömuutoksen jälkeen asukkailta vaaditaan sietokykyä, sopeutumiskykyä ja resilienssiä, myös syntyviin sosiaalisiin ja kulttuurisiin muutoksiin. Arvioitaessa *Kuerin matka* -teoksen prosessia voidaan helposti yhtyä ympäristö- ja yhteiskuntatutkimuksen Jules Prettyin (2011) näkemykseen, jonka mukaan yhteisöjen resilienssin lisääminen edellyttää kulttuurin ja koulutuksen yhteyksien uudelleen rakentamista paikallisiin ekokult-

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

tuureihin.

Pretty (2011) onkin ehdottanut, että ajatteluumme tulisi uudistaa lisäämällä paikallisen ja perinteisen tiedon sisällyttämistä alueiden suunnitteluun. Myös maaseudun kehittämisen professori Arora-Jonsson (2016) on painottanut, että yhteisöjen ja alueiden ekokulttuurisen resilienssin edistämiseksi on tunnustettava paikallinen tieto. *Kuerin matka* -teoksessa taustana toimi edellä kuvattu pohjoinen tietojärjestelmä, jonka perustana on luonnon kanssa tietäminen samaan tapaan kuin ehdotetuissa uusmaterialistissa (Gamble & Hanan, 2019) ja posthumanistisista tutkimuskäytännöissä (Ulmer, 2017).

Lopuksi

Näkemykseni on, että taideperustaiset toimintatutkimushankkeet, kuten *Kuerin matka* -teoksen prosessi, ovat toimivia ja vaikuttavia paikkaperusteisen koulutuksen muotoja. Osallistava toiminta elvyttää haurastunutta paikallista ekokulttuuria vahvistaen alueellista identiteettiä. Paikkaperustainen taidekasvatus tukee kestävyyttä vahvistamalla ihmisten ja heidän elämänpiirien välisiä yhteyksiä ja kuten Dessein ja muut (2015) painottavat, käynnistämällä keskusteluja yhteisöjen tulevaisuuden toiveista.

Kun työskentelen taidekasvatuksen alalla Lapin yliopistossa, toteuttamani paikkasidonnaiset taideprojektit uudistavat jatkuvasti myös alan korkeakouluopetusta. Pohjoisessa tapahtuviin nopeisiin muutoksiin reagoiminen siirtää taiteilijan ja taidekasvattajan työn ydintä ja samalla yliopistollisen koulutuksen tavoitteita itseilmaisusta ja individualismista kohti yhteisöllisempää, dialogisempaa ja monialaisempaa lähestymistapaan. Nykytaidekasvatus pohjoisessa ei voi jättää alueen ekokulttuuria huomioimatta, eikä se liioin synny vain perinteestä, vaan alueen ekokulttuurin ja nykytaiteen osallistavien toimintamuotojen kohtaamisesta.

Näen että *Kuerin matka* kaltaisten teosprosessien avulla taiteilijat ja taideopettajat voivat auttaa yhteisöjä välittämään arktisen aineellisen ja henkisen kulttuurin perintöä uusille suku-

KUERIN MATKASSA: PAIKKAPERUSTAINEN TAIDETEOS YMPÄRISTÖKONFLIKTISSA

polville, myös pohjoisen alueen ulkopuolelle. Kulttuurinen vaikutusmahdollisuus ja vahva alueellinen identiteetti lisäävät ekokulttuurista selviytymiskykyä. Perinteiden säilyttäminen elävänä myös uusissa tilanteissa tukee yhteisöjä heidän oikeuksiensa puolustamisessa samalla lisäten myös joustavuutta kohdata mahdolliset nopeat muutokset.

Päätelmäni on, että Kuerin matka teoksen kaltaiset prosessit, jotka toimivat keinona elvyttää ja kohdentaa pohjoisten tietämisen tapoja, ovat tärkeitä myös taidekoulutuksen onnistumiselle arktisella alueella. Näen toiminnalla myös maailmanlaajuisen roolin globaalin posthumanistisen kestävyysajattelun tavoittelemassa luonnon ja ihmisten välisen yhteyden ja tasa-arvon edistämässä.

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Learning to Play with the Rules: On the Development of the Bauspielplatz Kunst Kammer's Methodological Play with Variation

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Biography

Marc Herbst is a co-founder and co-editor of the Journal of Aesthetics & Protest that has been publishing since 2001, a PhD Advisor at Transart Institute a research fellow at ProArt and Commons. He is co-editor of the Laboratory of Insurrectionary Imagination's We are 'Nature' Defending Itself, co-published by Pluto Press in 2021. He is a co-curator of the Bauspielplatz Kunst Kammer, and here and elsewhere continues researching psycho-social and socio-cultural elements related to eco-feminist transformation in the light of our changing world.

Abstract

With social and ecological variation caused by climate change, cities and city residents will need to develop flexibility at the core of their structures and in their relationships to them. Cities' planning codes, design norms and their residents' food and comfort habits are established upon Holocene stability that has been upended by the Anthropocene. So, in addition to the routine socialization that children must undertake to learn to live together in their established settings, they must now learn to embrace flexible relations to these settings and their habits. European life is now transforming with changes driven

by climate change and recent refugee waves, and Germany responded to the 2015 wave by generously funding cultural integration projects with loosely defined goals. When properly situated, arts-based learning can provide a playful way for children, refugee or not, to flexibly integrate and relate to each other and to changes in cultural and architectural infrastructure towards heterogeneous conviviality. This practice-based paper describes an artistic researcher's development of an arts-based situation, the Bauspielplatz Kunst Kammer (BKK) museum, intended for such learning. It discusses initial insights into the practice of how a situated institution can ground such learning and looks towards wider questions such a project inspires.

Keywords

adventure playground, climate change, transformational play, play, eco-social play, arts-based research, refugees, integration, childhood learning, urban planning, social variation, institutional variation, play museum, museums. art pedagogy

Introduction

This essay, built on previous research (Herbst, 2020) on transformational artistic practice, is interested in how communities, impacted by changes in climate, might develop a space and capacity to improvise. Some critical political theory (Tronti, 1972; Virno, 2002) attends to meaningful social innovation that occurs through radical grassroots responses from below to troubling contexts. Other writing (e.g. Virno, 2008; Glowczewski, 2015; Zechner & Rübner Hansen, 2015; Sheikh, 2017) also highlights the role that cultural institutions play in scaffolding and supporting such change. I have come to understand that space for variation can be collaboratively scaffolded between institutional structures that exist and what needs to be socially established for conviviality, rather than created whole-clothed in abstract ideological space against what has been established.

I have been engaging with childhood arts-based learning situations on themes related to social and planning-based transformations in the shadows of the Anthropocene. My understanding about the nature of the Anthropocene can be succinctly understood through Jason W. Moore's (2015) discussion of humanity's capitalist entanglements, and refined through Haraway's (2016) descriptions of the messiness of those entanglements.

As an arts-based educator, cultural practitioner and researcher, I understand my roll to be that of a collaborative, social sculptor. I have been seeking to establish situations that can organize social learning capable of responding to such messy entanglements. I initially had the opportunity to learn through a practice-based situation with refugee children in a situation that was not explicitly intended for research. I began this investigation with a German project supported by generous public funds earmarked for an ill-defined goal of refugee integration via arts and culture. I was specifically working with the population of child refugees, mostly from Syria, living in settlement housing at the edge of Leipzig. It was through an initial creative engagement with this population that my trial-and-error process towards developing a meaningful social practice began.

In addition to the project afforded by these general funds, I was also invited to work with an adult-learning platform, the Nachbarschaftsakademie in Berlin, that also informs this interrogation. The Nachbarschaftsakademie is situated in an experimental garden, and utilizes innovative educational practices to collaboratively establish an eco-feminist pedagogy for learning through the coming hundred years of climate change.

Based on these two experiences, I developed and co-designed The Bauspielplatz Kunst Kammer (BKK) with kids at an adventure playground in Leipzig Germany. At present, the Bauspielplatz Kunst Kammer seems like an adequate platform where children can engage in structured play with an institution and its contents. This essay discusses the eventual conceptual and practical development of the BKK and its initial practice, and ends with a wider discussion around social sculpture and social play in the context of urbanity and climate change.

Presentation of the Cases

1. A Well-funded Integration Project

I began working in the Leipzig Pandechion refugee settlement house through a weekly encounter with the home's then-mostly Syrian children aged 4 to 14. I joined the project after it was established and did not contribute to its conceptualization. It was a loose, arts-based integration project afforded by the German Ministry for Families, Seniors, Woman and Youth in the welcoming atmosphere following the 2015 wave of wave of refugees from Syria to Germany (Karakayali, 2018). The encounters were situated in the house's "Creative Room"; our interactions with the children were mostly mediated through small drawing and crafting projects. Because there was no other populations for them to interact and integrate with, there would likely be no meaningful integration despite the Ministry's funding goals.

After getting to know the homes children, I co-conceptualized an intensive comic drawing workshop for them over the 2018 Easter holiday. I hoped that we could achieve something through this more focused workshop, hosted off-site within a neighborhood contemporary art space. The project would have a fully articulated pedagogical structure with hourly learning goals that introduced concepts like plot, narrative, character, and ultimately developing stories around social inclusion. Further, we planned to engage the children with aesthetic questions drawn from the fine arts context that our contemporary art space suggested; around questions of abstraction, autonomy and beauty. We assumed that as a secondary effect, the children might have some integration experiences because of the workshop's setting in a more diverse neighborhood.

On the first workshop day, I learned quickly what a more experienced art teachers would easily point out; most kids have little attention for a day of drawing and lectures. They like to play with rules. Our breakfast-time lecture using characters on breakfast cereal boxes was sidelined by spilled milk and discussions about who was served the most food. It was a disaster from the start, my workshop co-leader and I were bereft of a plan. I witnessed how quickly a bunch of kids could generate and toss aside drawings without giving their doodles a second thought (figure 1). We had a classroom, ample budget, but no actionable plan. Our unreflected reliance on art's institutions and their normative standards left us in a crisis and with little to do.

Figure 1. One of many drawings made and quickly forgotten at the Pandechion comic drawing workshop in Leipzig. Photograph by Luise Wonneberger, 2018.

Bored kids scanned the room for something better to occupy their time. They were attracted to the tape and cardboard swords that a previous group of children had left there. Suddenly and under their own initiative, they set the terms for the rest of the workshop week. In play-based situations, they quickly applied their creative and innovative capacities to make their own swords and shields. They established complex-but-ethically-horizontal social hierarchies that facilitated the rapid design and production of crafted items. Sword fighting was fun way to utilize the time we had together (figure 2). Still trying to maintain our pedagogical goals, I occasionally charged the kids of one sword drawing in exchange for helping them cut a shield out from the cardboard (figure 3).

Faced with a crisis, the children themselves developed an institutional framework and standards, one formalized through sword-play and characterized by innovation and exchange. Our educational goals proved pointless; insisting on the goals in the exchange between sword and drawing demonstrated that at best, they would just reproduce a capitalist exchange system of symbolic payments (in drawings) for labor. Upon reflection, I recognized that we'd chosen a learning structure and outcomes that were ill-defined and not child-appropriate. Art for itself would not suffice. In an essay I authored (Forthcoming) reflecting on the workshop and it being hosted in DDR era utopian housing, I reflected; "The gamble of radical social art practices' attempts to make inclusive space for displaced and marginal youth is that its ethical play may be more consequential than the force of the governing systems these practices must participate in.... (Radical institutional art may) have some benefits to the youth participants. Generally, though, the systemic accounting that makes art stand autonomously to the world mirrors the Socialist ideal of East Germany- not explicitly for its Marxism, but rather for its placing a better world beyond the here and now, that sits on the horizon as some kind of eventual social utopia." I learned through the arch of this engagement that a project with goals oriented towards social betterment needed a method that facilitates its overall goals, and goals that match its population's capacities and interests.

Figure 2. The construction of swords and shields quickly became a meaningful craft activity. Photograph by Luise Wonneberger, 2018.

Figure 3. Becoming an item for play, the topic of swords and knives could easily be thematized... "I will give you cardboard for a sword in exchange for a drawing of one". Photograph by Luise Wonneberger, 2018.

2. Experimental Garden

Around the time of this workshop, I was invited by artist/activist/educators Åsa Sonjasdotter and Marco Clausen to collaborate with artistic researcher Michelle Teran and co-facilitate the 2019 Berlin Nachbarschaftsakademie. The Nachbarschaftsakademie is an adult learning platform hosted in the Prinzessinnengarten in Berlin's fashionable Kreuzberg district. Sonjasdotter, Clausen and others had begun the Nachbarschaftsakademie project as a tool for the Prinzessinnengarten to consciously study eco-socialist and eco-feminist questions that emerge through managing their open, experimental garden (figure 4).

Our 2019 Nachbarschaftsakademie sessions investigated the management of the garden and its attendant social relations over time. After winning assurance from the city that the land upon which the garden sat would be public and open green-space for 100 years, our aim was to consider ways to pedagogically establish a speculative syllabus that would function as an ethical compass for those coming hundred years– years characterized by changing social and ecological climates. Among other responsibilities, Teran and I were tasked with conceptualizing and authoring a book about the syllabus. In reflecting on our task, questions around the malleability and play that facilitate institutional longevity came to the fore.

The forward that Michelle Teran and I co-authored states:

Here, collectively, it is as though we have allowed ourselves to be suspended in time. And the ether that affords and organizes this suspension is that mix of our individual personal economies, the organizations we are staggering to put in place and our collective political desires for many different things to come to pass. The Prinzessinnengarten's occupation is one of these things. It is also that time-traveling geographic fact that manages to contain all this suspension. This book, focusing on the garden, was intended to be written in stone and be authored between time." (Herbst & Teran, 2020, p.11)

The Nachbarschaftsakademie utilized arts-based funding from the German Ministry for Culture to host a variety of situated learning practices that dealt with questions of cultural variation over time and place. No singular learning project that we hosted over our 2019 program addressed the full range of questions related to possible changes, but cumulatively we observed how a site and its institution could be a host for so many of the possible questions we imagine the site would encounter over time. In relation to my desire to develop a place where children might engage with questions around social variation, the 2019 Nachbarschaftsakademie demonstrated how pluralistic and open institutions allow for a variety of relations– they can act as a petri dish for any number of relations that occur within them.

Figure 4. The Laube at the Prinzessinnengarten where the adult-oriented situated learning 2019 Nachbarschaftsakademie occurred. Photograph by Common Ground, 2017.

3. The BKK

Initially under the same funding that had supported the arts-based workshops in Leipzig's Pandechnion, I began doing arts-based workshops in the Bauspielplatz Wild Westen with my colleague Luise Wonneberger. Bauspielplatz is the German word for "adventure playgrounds"; they are guided play spaces where children are given a bucket full of nails, hammer and saw and allowed to play and build onto pre-existing structures (figure 5). Adventure playgrounds came into their own as an arena for childhood development in bombed-out London at the end of World War Two. Adventure playgrounds first came to Germany through Berlin's British occupation; an apocryphal British occupation official recognized that the play model might fill a similar niche in Berlin. Since then, they have evolved into spaces where progressive, inclusive and ecologically oriented social values are part-and-parcel of the play opportunities and open modes of access to the space. Shier (1984) describes many of the historical and social elements contingent to the adventure playground movement, while Cranwell (2003) discusses how it is the guided play inherent to such playgrounds that has made them a site for progressively oriented social development. Further, Kozlovsky (2008) draws parallels between their early development in bombed-out cities and their capacities to act as forums for social innovation, while Russel (2015) brings critical and schizo-analytic theory to the sort of exchanges possible at such sites.

The Bauspielplatz Wild Westen is located near another refugee settlement house with mostly Syrian refugees. In collaboration with this house, we were able to access the same project funds we had utilized for work described above. These house's children frequented the Bauspielplatz. Thematically, we could initially work with the concept of integration. Overall, the playground's neighborhood is much more diverse than the other Pandechnion house. Our experience there confirmed observations by Horton and Kraftl (2017) that wider contexts for play greatly effects play's content, and Visscher and Bouverne-De Bie (2008) and McGregor and Ragab's (2016) observation that efforts towards social integration function best in contexts where intercultural exchange is actually possible. Thus, it was clear to me that here all children could have direct experience with forming new ways of relating to one another— unlike in the situation at Pandechnion where we could only conceptually thematize integration through, for example, comic book writing. The Bauspielplatz' open-access nature where kids could come as they please and engage at their desired depth also differed from the working environment with Pandechnion. Based on my observations there and the experiences with the Nachbarschaftsakademie, it was clear that the Bauspielplatz provided a superior context for all forms of play. It had a culture of guided play that benefited from open cross-generational dialog with playground staff and parents of other children.

I recognized that we needed a vessel, an institution, through which to focus the creative and educational possibilities inherent to this context. A museum seemed like a natural fit; it could motivate creativity and children are already used to putting artwork on their schoolroom walls. They appreciate the cultural cachet suggested by a museum. I saw how a museological institution could provide a focused site to socially sculpt play around future-oriented social and cultural flexibility in relationship to our changing ecologies and cities.

Figure 5. Bauspielplatz Wild Westin in Leipzig, a kid-built structure based on progressive educational and play models. Photograph by unknown. 2018.

In developing our museological method, I was inspired by the work of conceptual artist Michael Asher who organized a long-term exchange between teenagers and the Los Angeles Contemporary Museum of Art (LACMA) where the students curated an exhibition at LACMA. (See Ulke & Asher 2003). I was also inspired by art and activist projects like Park Fiction and City From Below that opened up specialist urban planning and design practices to common people. This strategy would inherently play with hierarchies around whose voice matters. So, our museum would be a collaboration between the playground youth and our adult BKK team. On the playground over the 2020 summer, we hosted an architectural charrette with the kids to design a museum that we promised to build together. Fifteen museum models were constructed. When the children grasped that there would be a vote on the models, interest in the design process soared. One eight-year-old girl with a refugee background began heavily campaigning for her model of a gallery wing... and won. The second-place model was dome-shaped. We decided to combine both models for the construction plan when we realized that by constructing both we would have space for both two- and three-dimensional artwork (figure 6). All that we needed was an actual way to build the dome structure.

Figure 6. The two winning architectural models for the museum, installed now in BKK Museum's 2D hall for display purposes. Photograph by Marc Herbst. 2021.

Figure 7. The BKK museum, with ticket-booth entrance to the left behind the green flag. The booth abuts and enters into the 2D artwork hall. The hall leads to the sculpture atrium, a half-dome painted white. Photograph by Marc Herbst. 2021.

Brazilian sculptor Chico Togni, stranded in Leipzig during the Covid lockdown, was helpful here. He had experience building fabulous architectures with the sort of left-over material available on the playground. So throughout the autumn of 2020, Chico and I worked onsite with the kids; sourcing material, digging, sawing, hammering, and drilling our museum. At first, few kids grasped the project's overall vision, but piece by piece, and in improvisation with our plans, the building took form (figure 7). There was a lot of enthusiasm for the project now, and, rather than boredom, having too many helpers became a problem. At moments when there was a lot of available kids to work but little for them to do, we planned that several museum walls would be constructed using small planks perfect for kids to bang nails into. We would also use their energy to paint the walls; one wall would be multi-colored while the rest had to be kept white. Keeping the walls white was an ongoing task— playground kids have access to colored paint on site and were continually entering the museum and painting its sections in a rainbow of colors and forms.

Figure 8. Access to the employee-only area, "nur für mitarbeiter (employees-only)" written three times. Photograph by Marc Herbst. 2021.

As autumn turned toward winter, the museum really took shape. There were several kids who consistently participated and their interests helped refine design and construction. One girl insisted that a museum needed a ticket booth and set out to build it. Her construction assistants insisted that we also needed an employee-only area behind, and they built it. The kids were so excited about the employee-only area, they hand-lettered "Employees Only" onto the door three times! (figure 8). One boy became very efficient with the power tools we had, and when bored with our slow pace of construction, would run around the entire playground using the drill in areas that were otherwise not intended for power tool use. To utilize his skills, we asked him to design and build the museum's bar (figure 9).

Figure 9. Kid-designed and built bar. "Make it look slick" we instructed. Photograph by Marc Herbst. 2021.

On the successful completion of the museum structure, in the spring of 2021 we applied for and received specific funds from the German Museum Association with the support of the Bauspielplatz and a local contemporary art museum, Halle 14. Halle 14 was curating an exhibit on the theme of incorporating social, architectural and logistical flexibility into ongoing urban development. Over the course of the museum's design and construction, Chico noted that though the kids expressed little interest in the museum, they were very interested in spaces that allowed them to play with the rules and access that adulthood afford. The ticket booth and its ability to control access, an emergency exit, the bar and the employee-only area were all child-generated architectures through which rules might come into play. So, in echo of the Halle 14 theme and our own experiences building the structure, we conceived of our first curatorial concept, "Playing with the rules."

One basic rule of play we established was that all but one of our walls should be painted white- this was a museum after all. But, because it is an open play space as well as a museum, I have made sure to celebrate and document the copious graffiti and autonomously generated artwork that appears on the wall when our adult museum staff is gone (figure 10). I have heard that children who have an interest in the museum's operation have been debating the extent to which the white walls rule is meant to be enforced, and to what extent it is just a flexible rule intended to be bent. Among themselves, they are debating the intention of this rule- a debate that I see as directly relating to questions of the role of public space in a changing city.

Upon the museum's completion and over the course of our curatorial season, I have been curious to find out how such a play-based institution for kids could be utilized as a research platform to collectively play with the flexibility of and within institutions, in relation to our changing world.

Figure 10. Photo of the BKK Museum's 2D hall. We are continually having to paint over graffiti that appears when museum staff is not present. Photograph by Marc Herbst. 2021.

Findings, Social Sculpture at Play

Though early in our museum's season, we have developed at least two other methods for how we might utilize a play museum to play with institutional variation.

The first relates to the ticket booth (figure 11). Our first project under "Playing with the rules" involved drawing entry tickets and "optional" membership cards with the kids. So much energy has already come into play at the booth, it is difficult to recount all the games that these tickets and membership cards have inspired. Kids argue over who has the right to staff the booth so that they can regulate others' entrance into the museum. Access to space is an important theme in relationship to institutions and our changing world. In response, we instituted the museum's second rule- the employees at the entrance were not allowed to deny access. They were asked to not say "no" to anyone who wanted to enter, even if they had no ticket. Instead, we instructed them to follow the improvisational theatre guideline of responding to all situations with the words, "yes, and...". This rule means that kids working behind the desk should not say "no" but can say "yes" while adding other conditions, thus keeping a goal of access to the museum in play.

Another method for rule-based artistic play involves utilizing the structure's boundaries between outside and in. We aimed to use the fact of the building itself in order to explore rule-play around the material fact of the institution's physical presence. Over a weekend with individual kids, we explored the large gaps in the walls of our jerry-rigged building. At each gap, we asked the kids what they might imagine beyond the hole in the wall. The ridiculous question was made meaningful by the sincerity of our question. I saw that there were three basic answer-types, the ridiculous (a monster, candy), socially oriented responses (thieves, happy families), and answers that related to natural forces (powerful flows of water, storms, comets). We then asked children to draw pictures of the inside/outside that they imagined (figure 12). On the following weekend, we asked children to develop art projects that mediated the transition between the inside and the outside, taking into consideration the rainy early summer we had been experiencing (figure 13).

Figure 11. View of the BKK'S ticket-booth, and into the 2D hall. The sculpture atrium is at the end of the hall to the right. Note the current (weekly) exhibition poster and exhibition calendar located next to the booth. Photograph by Marc Herbst. 2021.

Figure 12. When asked to draw what is outside the museum, one of our child co-researchers drew a picture of a very powerful stream of water. Photograph by Marc Herbst. 2021.

Conclusion

Within the BKK neighborhood, word is spreading that there is a museum built and run by kids. We are curious to see how the concept of flexible play with rules will formally and institutionally develop there. Tsiolkovsky (2008) argues that the range of play within adventure playgrounds is overdetermined by both the structures for playing and their attending play workers. He claims that they do little more than press children "into subjects." (p. 187) rather than create competent improvisors.

But my experience has shown that a situated institution whose operating rules and *raison d'être* is to be capable of hosting meaningful children's play that can facilitate a skill of social variation, one conceptually attendant to climate change. So, our experience is more in line with Russel (2015) who describes how by playing with rules, adventure playground can be understood as a collaborative process of improvisation. In our case, ours is a collaboration between the museum's structure and concepts and individual children's development and creativity. Russel argues that play is not a cognitively fixed thing but is rather a melange of transversal psychosocial developments. Play, she proposes, is not a fixed process of individual subject formation. Nevertheless, as how Visscher and Bouverne-De Bie (2008) and McGregor and Ragab (2016) argue, I do appreciate how context serves a great determinant for its varying outcomes, so I continue to playing with the contextual possibilities of of the museum and what it hosts, in order to keep overall context at play.

Regarding how urban institutions might build play to their structure in order to better greet changes attendant to climactic transformations, it would seem that projects like Aksu, J., Karjevsky, G., and Quack, S. (2014)'s Playful Commons makes a valuable contribution. Playful Commons seeks to redefine urban planning and zoning under the open concept of how public space acts to hosts possibilities for urban life. That is, hosting against normative regulatory language that delimits space to particular predetermined uses. This idea of acting as host is in parallel with Russel's descriptions and our experiences with how children benefits from more open, though guided, play rather than via pedagogical interaction conceptually aimed toward progressive ideals.

Figure 13. A child made this felt and feather installation to mediate the transition between inside and outside and to dry the rain soaked backs of those traveling across this boundary. Photograph by Marc Herbst. 2021.

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Taidetta elääkseen – eloa taiteeseen: autoetnografista visualisointia toiminimellä työskentelystä

Niina Oinas
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Biografia

Niina Oinas on väitöskirjatutkijana Lapin yliopistossa. Väitöskirja pureutuu ajankohtaiseen kysymykseen taiteen, taiteilijan ja sosiaali- ja terveyssektorin kehittyvästä yhteistyöstä. Väitöskirjan näkökulmana on erityisesti taiteilijoiden uudenlainen asemoituminen sosiaalisesti sitoutuneen taiteen kentällä. Oinas peräänkuuluttaa sosiaalisesti merkittävää työtä tekevien taiteilijoiden parempaa tunnistamista, tukemista ja vakaampaa yhteiskunnallista asemaa.

Abstrakti

Suomessa yhä useammat taiteilijat hakeutuvat perinteisinä pidettyjen työskentely-ympäristöjen ulkopuolelle. Avaan omakohtaista kokemustani taiteellisen toiminnan muotoutumisesta ja kehittämisestä toiminimiyrittäjyyden muotoon peilaten kokemustani ajankohtaiseen tutkimukseen. Tämä visuaalinen essee on alku taideperustaiselle toimintatutkimukselleni, jossa kehitän ja määrittelen sosiaali- ja terveyssektorilla toimivan taiteilijan osaamistarpeita. Esseen näkökulmana on autoetnografinen tutkimusote, jossa omat kokemukseni ja niistä kirjoitetut tai muuten tuotetut kenttämuistiinpanot muodostavat tutkimuksen

keskeisen aineiston. Aineistonani ovat toimineet dokumenttivalokuvat, teokset, muistikirjat ja asiakirjat toiminimeni vuosilta 2016–2020. Osa esseen kuvista on ohjaamastani toiminnasta ja osa teoksista, joiden tekemisellä ylläpidän taiteilijuuttani ja jäsenen henkilökohtaisia kokemuksiani. Taideperustaisessa toimintatutkimuksessa tutkimustulokset syntyvät sykleittäin. Tässä esseessä päädyn johtopäätökseen, että taiteen vakiinnuttamiseksi sosiaali- ja terveysalalle tarvitaan nykyistä selkeämpiä rakenteita ja standardisointeja, jotta taiteen erityispiirteet voitaisiin huomioida laaja-alaisesti taiteen uusilla toiminta-alueilla.

Asiasanat

taideperustainen toimintatutkimus, työelämän muutos, yhteisötaide, taiteilija, soveltava kuvataide, sosiaali- ja terveyssektori

Kuva 1: Niina Oinas, 2021. 94999. Paperi, mustetulosteet, kierrätyskehys. Kuva: Niina Oinas, 2021.

Kuva 2: Taiteilijana esillä oleminen ja osaamisensa markkinointi ovat täynnä ristiriitaisuuksia, joita on opittava hallitsemaan.
Kuva: Soile Pyhähuhta-Karppinen.

JOHDANTO

Jatkuvasti kasvava määrä tutkimustuloksia taiteen ja kulttuurin vaikuttavuudesta terveydelle ja hyvinvoinnille on kiihdyttänyt alan kiinnostavuutta taiteen perinteisten kenttien ulkopuolella. Soveltavaksi taiteeksi luokiteltavaa taidetta on tehty ja tutkittu Suomessakin jo useamman vuosikymmenen ajan. Taidetapahtumilla ja -toiminnoilla on kuntoutettu, osallistettu ja voimaannutettu. Tutkimuksia toiminnan laadusta ja vaikutuksista on tehty muun muassa ikäihmisten palveluiden (Jumisko ym., 2013), työyhteisöjen tukemisen (Rönkä ym., 2011) kuin myös itse taidelähtöisten menetelmien vaikuttavuuden (Rantala & Jansson, 2013) näkökulmasta. Yhteisöllisen taidekasvatuksen väitöskirjassaan Hiltunen toteaa jo vuonna 2009 havainneensa yhteisöllisen taidekasvatuksen mahdollisuuksia ja merkityksiä erityisesti yhteistyössä ikäihmisten ja erityisryhmien kanssa (Hiltunen, 2009).

2020 vuosikymmenelle tultaessa Suomessa on kehittynyt vahva noste myös organisaatiotaiteilijuudelle, joka tavoittelee työelämän uudistamista taiteilijan ammattitaitoa hyödyntäen (Petäjajarvi, 2016). Petäjajarven määritelmän mukaan työyhteisöt haluavat tehdä yhteistyötä taiteilijan kanssa, koska taide nähdään toiseuden ilmentäjänä. Työyhteisö haluaa jotakin sellaista, joka on harppaus ohi perinteisten ajatusratojen ja edustaa selkeästi toista kulttuuria (Petäjajarvi, 2016). Tutkimukset osoittavat, että taideinterventioilla voidaan tukea organisaatioiden muutosta, vahvistaa luovuutta ja innovaatiokykyä sekä uudistaa työtapoja (Houni ym., 2020).

Kiihtynyt keskustelu taiteen ja kulttuurin hyvinvointivaikutuksista liittyy osittain myös Euroopan unionin hyvinvointipolitiikkaan, joka korostaa sosiaalista osallisuutta syrjäytymisen vastakohtana (Lehikoinen ym., 2020). Lisäksi sen voi nähdä olevan yhteydessä OECD:n jäsenmaailleen antamaan ohjeistukseen subjektiivisen hyvinvoinnin tarkastelusta (Lehikoinen ym., 2020). Ohjeistus on saanut OECD-maat huomioimaan ihmisten kokemaa onnellisuutta ja koettua hyvinvointia osana parempaa elämää edistäviä kansallisia ja paikallisia toimenpidesuosituksia (Lehikoinen ym., 2020). Sivistisyhteiskunnissa taiteilla ja kulttuurilla on tunnustettu arvo omana itsenään. Laajentuneessa hyvinvointiajattelussa niiden merkityksellisyys nähdään lisäksi yhä selkeämmin osana sosiaali- ja terveysalan palveluita.

Kuva 3: Erilaisia tekniikoita soveltamalla jokainen ihminen voi saada onnistumisen elämyksiä taiteen tekemisestä.
Kuva: Niina Oinas, 2019.

Myös taiteilijoiden ammatti-identiteetti on muutoksessa (Karttunen, 2017). Uusien toimintojen mahdollistama näkymä on usein epäselvä, mutta kiehtova. Yhä useammat taiteilijat eivät enää tavoittele yksinomaan työhuoneen rauhaa ja oman ilmaisutekniikan kehittämistä, vaan he haluavat olla aktiivisena osana yhteiskuntaa, yhteisöjä ja laajempaa kehittämistyötä. Tässä murroksessa on monia yhtäaikaista vaikuttimia, joita avaan esseessäni pääpiirteissään kartoittaessani tutkimuksen tarvetta autoetnografisesta näkökulmastani. Reflektoin ja analysoin omaa taiteellista toimintaani vuosien 2016–2020 ajalta rinnastaen sen kirjallisuuteen ja ajankohtaiseen keskusteluun taiteen roolista sosiaali- ja terveysalalla. Tämän esseen mukana avaan henkilökohtaisia näkökulmiani ja kokemuksiani käytännön kokemusteni kautta (kuva 2.)

Olen työlistänyt itseäni soveltavan kuvataiteen ja yhteisötaiteen nimikkeiden alle asettuvaan toimintaan vuodesta 2016 lähtien. Olen tehnyt paljon yhteistyötä kaupungin kulttuuritoimen, sosiaali- ja terveyssektorin, erityisesti palvelukotien, kanssa. Näkökulmani on yksittäisen taiteilijan työlistymiseen liittyvissä kysymyksissä, ongelmassa ja kehittämistarpeissa. Tämän visuaalisen esseen kuvat ovat kurkistuksia taiteelliseen toimintaani ja kuvaavat parhaiten maastoa, josta tutkimustehtäväni tarve nousee. Kuvat välittävät taiteessani korostuvaa materiaalisuuden merkitystä ja kohtaamisen tilanteiden konkretiaa käytännöntasolta (kuva 3.). Osa kuvista on teoskuvia, joissa olen käsitellyt oman työskentelyni kautta tutkimukseni teemoja (kuva 4.). Yhteisötaiteen kautta mahdollistan taiteen tekemisen muille, oma taiteellinen toimintani ylläpitää omaa luovuuttani ja ammattitaitoani. Nämä osa-alueet ovat toinen toisensa mahdollistajia, joten pidän ne myös tutkimuksessani rinnakkain kulkevinä elementteinä.

Tässä esseessä tarkastelen työhistoriaani kolmessa osassa. Ensimmäisessä teemassa pohdin taiteen paikkaa ja haasteita sosiaali- ja terveyssektorilla. Toisessa teemassa avaan taiteilijaidentiteetin haasteita muuttuvassa ajassa ja yhteisötaiteen kentällä. Kolmannessa teemassa tarkastelen työlistyyspolitiikkaa yhteisötaiteen näkökulmasta.

Tutkimusmetodinani olen reflektoinut kokemuksiani dokumenttivalokuvien, muistikirjojen ja virallisten asiakirjojen kautta (kuva 1.). Taideperustaisen toimintatutkimuksen yhtenä

Kuva 4. Niina Oinas, 2016. *Ero / Divorce*, 80 X 110, akryyli kankaalle. Kuva: Niina Oinas.

tarvekartoitusta jäsentävänä menetelmänä on ollut oman taiteen tekeminen ja yhteisötaidetoiminnoista minulle jääneiden elementtien viimeistely teokselliseen muotoon. Tämä visuaalinen essee on myös laajemman taideperustaisen tutkimusprosessini lähtökohta.

TAITEILIIJA SOSIAALI- JA TERVEYSSEKTORILLA

Iso käännekohta taiteen ja kulttuurin ymmärrykselle sosiaali- ja terveysalan kehittämisenäkökulmasta oli monelta osin maailman terveysjärjestö WHO:n vuonna 2019 julkaisema *What is the evidence on the role of the arts in improving health and well-being?* -raportti taiteen vaikuttavuustutkimuksista. Tähän yli 900 tutkimusjulkaisua sisältävään raporttiin viitataan ahkerasti puhuttaessa taiteen ja kulttuurin sekä terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin teemoista (Fancourt & Finn, 2019). Samaan aikaan omakohtaisesti koin ristiriitaa toiminnassani. Lyhytkestoiselle taidetoiminnalle oli kysyntää, mutta sitä ei vakiinnutettu organisaatioiden rakenteisiin pitkäjänteiseksi palveluksi. Vanhojen toimintatapojen ravistelu taiteellisen vapaantilan kautta herättivät innostusta, mutta myös hämmennystä. Yhteisötaiteen ja sosiaali- ja terveyssektorin väliltä tuntui puuttuvan ymmärrettävä yhteinen kieli, vaikka intoa ja kiinnostusta molemmin puolin löytyikin. Pysyvään muutokseen tarvittaisiin aidosti oikeaa rakenteellista paikkaa taiteelle.

Taiteellisen toiminnan vaikuttavuuden merkitys helposti unohtuu, jos yritämme vain välineellisesti lisätä taiteita lisukkeeksi. Tunnin viikottaisessa toimintatuokiassa ei vielä päästä kovinkaan syviin kokemuksiin, eikä myöskään saada kovin merkittäviä vaikutuksia osallistujille henkilökohtaisella tasolla. Toisaalta, jos lähestymme taiteita ja kulttuuria jo lähtökohtaisesti odottaen täsmävaikutuksia terveyteen, meiltä jää mahdollisesti huomaamatta, miten moniulotteisesti taide meille kokemuksena ilmenee tai mikä tekee siitä erityisen (Lehikoinen ym., 2020). Tämä seikka on aiheuttanut taiteen kentällä pelkoa taiteen välineellistämisestä ja taiteen vapauden menettämisestä. Kaikkien alan toimijoiden ja kehittäjien tulisi huomioida, että taiteen vaikuttavuus ja erityisyys katoaa, jos taidetoimintojen sisällöt päälle liimataan sosiaali- ja terveysalan hierarkiseen toimintaan. Taidetoiminnoille täytyy löytää omanlaisensa arvo organisaatioiden sisältä. Taiteen kanssa toimittaessa ei-tietämiselle ja vapaalle mahdollisuudelle antaa asioiden tapahtua on kehitettävä oma paikka, aika ja mentaalinen tila. Ohjaamassani yhteisötaiteessa olen korostanut jokaisen mahdollisuutta ilmaisuun. Kädet osaavat vielä muotoilla, vaikka muisti olisi jo vienyt puhumisen taidon (kuvat 5. & 6.).

Taiteen vaikuttavuuden merkitys on siinä vapaudessa, jonka taiteellinen ilmaisu tekijälleen ja kokijalleen antaa, ei-tietämiseen perustuva määränpää, jossa jokainen ihminen on riittävä sellaisenaan. Olennaista on, että taiteen ja kulttuurin vaikutuksia – olivatpa ne luonteeltaan esteettisiä, kulttuurisia, sosiaalisia, kasvatuksellisia, taloudellisia tai terveyteen ja hyvinvointiin vaikuttavia – ei olisi olemassa ilman taiteen kohtaamisen synnyttämää henkilökohtaista taidekokemusta (Crossick & Kaszynska, 2016). Siksi ajatukset taiteen kohtaamisesta, taidekokemuksen merkityksellisyydestä ja taiteen saavutettavuudesta on otettava mukaan taiteita ja kulttuuria koskevan hyvinvointikeskustelun keskiöön (Lehikoinen ym, 2020).

Kuvat 5 & 6.: Niina Oinas, 2021. *Se on se / It is it*. Paperisavi, peili.
Savielementit ovat rovaniemeläisen palvelukodin muistisairaiden asukkaiden muotoilemia vuodelta 2017.
Kuva: Niina Oinas.

Taiteilijan työnkuvan tarkka-alaisen määrittämisen tarve tulee ymmärrettävästi taidekentän ulkopuolelta. Esimerkiksi Suomen Terveyden- ja hyvinvoinnin laitos kerää tällä hetkellä selkeästi määriteltyjä (myös taidelähtöisiä) toimintamalleja arviointiinsa, jonka kautta rakennetaan tulevaisuudessa hyvinvointia tukevia sosiaali- ja terveysalan toimintatapoja ja -rakenteita (THL, 2021). Ollakseen tulevaisuudessa paremmin kiinni valtakunnallisissa rakenteissa ja toimintakulttuureissa, taiteen on jollain tavalla oltava aktiivisesti osana arviointiprosesseja. Määrittelyn tehtävä on haastava, mutta ei täysin mahdoton. Esimerkiksi taiteellisten interventioiden tutkija Berthoin Antal (2016) on tietoisesti määritellyt interventiot neutraalisti. Hänen mukaansa taiteellisilla interventioilla tarkoitetaan prosesseja, joissa ihmiset, käytännöt ja tuotteet, jotka tulevat taidemaailmasta, astuvat organisaatioiden maailmaan. Taiteelliset interventiot eroavat useilla tavoilla toisistaan, kuten ajan, tavoitteen ja organisaation prosesseihin liittymisen osalta (Berthoin Antal, 2012). Tällainen määrittely sopii mainiosti taiteen kentälle ja vaalii taiteen vapautta sekä taiteellisen toiminnan ei-tietämisen logiikkaa, mutta tarkoin säädellylle sosiaali- ja terveysalalle määrittely ei vielä sellaisenaan riitä.

Työskennellessäni yhteisötaiteilijana hoitolaitoksissa olen kaivannut tutkimustietoa visuaalisten ja osallistavien taidetoimintojen kehittämisen tueksi. Ideat ja ajatukset taidemaailman kautta katsottuna ovat hyvin erilaisia kuin käytännön toiminta hoivapalveluissa, joissa täytyy reagoida muuttuviin tilanteisiin hienovaraisesti. Usein pienikin lämminhenkinen kohtaaminen saattaa olla osallistujalle merkittävä (kuva 7.).

Omaehtoisten kokemusteni valossa näen, että taidekentälläkin on tarpeen kääntää kysymyksen asettelua uuteen muotoon. Pelko taiteen välineellistämisestä ja perinteisen toiminnan katoamisesta ei saa olla esteenä taidekentän kehittämiselle. Yhteisötaiteilijana sosiaali- ja terveysalalla toimiessani koin usein, että minulla olisi ollut paljon enemmän annettavaa kuin resurssit ja arkiset rutiinit antoivat myöten. On suuri yhteiskunnallisen kehittämisen kysymys pohtia, miten taiteen ehdoilla saadaan taiteellinen osaaminen mukaan rakenteisiin sosiaali- ja terveysalojen toiminnoissa sekä laajemmin yhteiskunnassa. Tutkimuksin todistettua taiteen vaikuttavuutta erilaisen kohtaamisen keinona ja vapaan tilan luojana ei saada aikaan, jos taiteilijan ammattikuva sulautetaan sellaisenaan esimerkiksi sosionomin työnkuvaan. Taiteilijan toiminta-aiستیusudella ja erityisellä empaattisella työotteella on paikkansa sosiaali- ja terveyssektorilla, mutta ei aiempien ammatti-arvojen korvaajana vaan moniammatillisena uudenlaisena työparina. Usein melko steriiliin ympäristöön tulemalla taiteilija tuo mukanaan lupauksen jostain erilaisesta (kuva 12.). Taiteen läsnäolo herättelee ihmisyyttä, tapoja ja asenteita (Heimonen, 2013). Heimonen (2013) pohtii työyhteisön hyvinvointia kehittäessään, että herättely, ikkunoiden avaaminen toisenlaisiin maisemiin on riittävä tulos taiteen näkökulmasta, mutta riittääkö se sosiaali- ja terveyssektorin näkökulmasta?

Kuva 7. Arviointiyksikön arki on hektistä ja tilanteet jatkuvassa muutoksessa. Taidetoiminta luo tilan kohtaamisille.
Kuva: Niina Oinas.

YHTEISÖTAITEILIJAN IDENTITEETTI KEHITTYY HITAASTI

Taiteilijan identiteetti on monisyinen. Kulttuuripolitiikan tutkija Karttunen avaa taiteilijaidentiteetin muutosta ja hybriditaiteilijan määritelmiä artikkelissaan *Laajentuva taiteilijuus – yhteisötaiteilijan toiminta ja identiteetti hybridisaatio-käsitteen valossa* (Karttunen, 2017). Taiteilijoiden ammatinkuva on muutoksessa yhteiskunnan muuttuessa ja uusien tulonlähteiden kehittyessä. Samaan aikaan, kun luovaa osaamista tarvitaan uusilla sektoreilla, taiteilijat ovat yhä useammin korkeasti koulutettuja ja kykeneviä monialaisiin työtehtäviin. Asettaessani yhteisötaiteena tehtyjä kuvallisia teoksia esiin ja koostaessani niistä kollaaseja, olen pohtinut, miten tekijyyden voi ilmaista ja millainen merkitys produktiolla on taiteen kentällä (kuva 8.)? Yhteisötaiteessa arvo määrittyy prosessin ja kohtaamisen kautta, joten lopullinen teos jää usein toissijaiseksi tavoitteeksi. Yhteisön näkökulmasta teokseen on kiinnittynyt tekoprosessiin liittyneet arvot, tunteet ja oivallukset. Mutta missä näkyy yhteisön kanssa työskennelleen ammattitaiteilijan kädenjälki? Karttunen toteaa, että taiteilijaidentiteetin rakentaminen on yleensäkin pitkä ja hankala prosessi. Vielä vaikeampaa voi olla yhteisötaiteilijan identiteetin muodostaminen, etenkin sellaisilla taiteenaloilla, joilla yhteisöllisen toiminnan asema on vakiintumaton (Karttunen, 2017).

Hybriditaiteilijuus, taiteilijan suhde rahaan ja ansaintalogiikoihin ovat olleet murroksessa jo pitkään. Perinteisesti taiteen vapaus ja aitous on nähty täysin mahdottomana, jos taiteeseen liittyy ansaintalogiikkaa tai kaupallisuutta (Lampela, 2012). Etsiessäni taiteen paikkaa yhteiskunnan rakenteissa ja vakavasti otettavana osaamisena, ymmärrän samaan aikaan etsiväni omaa taiteilija-identiteettiäni. Perinteisesti taiteilija näyttäytyy mystisenä ja jollain tavalla saavuttamattomana henkilönä, joka luo taidetta ylimaallisilla lahjoillaan, vailla huolta toimeentulosta. 2020-luvulla taiteilijat eivät enää asetu tuohon mielikuvaan. Stereotypia taiteilijasta ei sellaisenaan ole tuntunut kutsuvalta, päin vastoin, itsekin olen tuntenut suurta ristiriitaa ammattitaiteilijan määritelmien suhteessa haluuni tehdä taidetta yhteisöissä, yhteiskunnassa, ihmisiä kohdaten, erilaisuutta tukien ja ihmisyyttä tutkien.

Yhteisötaiteilija ja tutkija Francois Matarrasso piti puheenvuoron pohjoismaisen taiteen ja hyvinvoinnin tutkijaverkoston tapaamisessa (Nordic arts & health conference, 8.6.2021). Hän pohti puheenvuorossaan yhteisötaiteen etiikkaa ja ammattitaiteilijuuden suppeaa määritelmää, jonka taiteilijat itse usein luovat. Mielenkiintoinen huomio Matarassolta oli, että ammattilaisuus (engl. professional) juontaa juurensa termiin, jolla kuvataan kykyä ja taitoa, jolla henkilö asettaa oman osaamisensa palvelemaan muiden etuja. Osuva vertauskuva tästä ovat esimerkiksi lääkärit tai asianajajat. Ammattilaisuus on sitä, että asetetaan omat tiedot ja taidot toisen henkilön tarpeita palvelemaan.

Tutkimustehtäväni näkökulmasta taiteilijoiden yleisesti heikko yhteiskunnallinen asema ja epävarmat työllistymismahdollisuudet ovat yksi avainkysymys tilanteessa, jossa taiteilijoiden osaamisesta ja luovasta pääomasta halutaan nyt usealla saralla hyötyä. Konkreettisesti taiteilijoiden uusien roolien haastavuus tulee hyvin esille jo TAIKA-hankkeen taiteilijahaastatteluista vuonna 2013 (Heimonen, 2013). TAIKA-hankeessa pyrittiin kokoamaan ajatuksia, ideoita, kokemuksia ja tutkimustietoa taidelähtöisestä toiminnasta erityisesti työelämäkontekstista käsin. Uusissa sosiaalialan ympäristöissä

Kuva 8: Muistikuvia-yhteisötaideteos Rovaniemen Arviointiyksikön asiakkaiden kanssa 2020. Kuva: Niina Oinas.

toimivat taiteilijat joustavat uudenlaisiin työmuotoihin joutuen jatkuvasti pohtimaan taiteen asemaa, omia ennako-oletuksiaan, osaamistaan ja toiminnassa korostuvaa kohtaamisen arvoa (Heimonen, 2013). Toimiessani ikäihmisten, erityisryhmien, lasten ja nuorten taideohjaajana näyttäytyin heille aina taiteilijana, vaikka itse vielä hieman vierastin tuota määritelmää. Toisaalta en myöskään pahoittanut mieltäni, jos joku henkilökunnasta esitteli minut askarteluohjaajana. Koin, että osallistujat määrittivät taiteilijuuden laveammin ja suoraviivaisemmin kuin taidemaailman perinteiset instituutiot. Ajattelutapa tuntui virkistävän raikkaalta ja se osaltaan rohkaisi minua murtamaan omia ennakkoluulojani taiteen ja taiteilijuuden roolituksesta.

Taiteen edistämiskeskuksen julkaisema opas onnistuneeseen residenssitoimintaan sosiaali- ja terveyssektorilla muistuttaa, että pelkkä taiteellisen työn laajuus ja näyttö paperilla ei ole peruste palkata taiteilijaa yhteisöön (Lapio, 2019). Tällä toimialalla kohteena ovat useimmiten haavoittuvassa asemassa tai elämäntilanteessa olevat asiakkaat (Lapio, 2019). Oppaan mukaan soveltavan taiteen ammattilaisilla on oltava ammattitaito kohdata ihminen läsnäolon kautta. Taiteellisen työn osaamisen lisäksi oleellisinta on taito kommunikoida ja vastaanottaa palautetta niin henkilökunnan kuin asiakkaidenkin taholta (Lapio, 2019). Tätä ammattitaitoa ja osaamista jäseniän edelleen käynnissä olevan tutkimukseni kautta, jotta alaa voidaan kehittää eettisesti kestävään muotoon sosiaali- ja terveyspalveluissa taidekentän kanssa vuoropuhelua käyden.

Sosiaali- ja terveysalan yhteistyössä taiteilijastatus antaa juuri sen erityisen roolin, jolla voin olla tasavertainen niin dementiapotilaan, hoitajan kuin myös paikan johtajan kanssa. Perinteisesti tarkkaan hierarkisoidulla alalla tämä on laaja-alainen näköalapaikka organisaation toimintamalleihin, vaihtoehtojen näkemiselle ja toimintakulttuurin inhimillistämiseksi. Taiteilijana koen saaneeni vastaanoton, joka asettaa minut erityiseen asemaan, jota yhteisöt määrittelevät taiteilijastatuksella. Toisaalta on huomioitava, että esimerkiksi erityisryhmien kanssa työskennellessä yhteisötaiteilijalla tulee olla sellaista erityistä osaamista, jota perinteisillä kuvataiteilijoilla ei välttämättä ole (kuvat 9. & 10.). Taidemaailman sisällä taiteilijuuden määrittelyyn käytetään erilaisia kriteerejä, toisinaan taiteen norsunluutorniksikin kutsutulla ilmiöllä viitataan toimijoiden ja arvioijien sisäsyntyiseen näkökulmaan (Mononen, 2014). Minun taiteilijuuteni on tunnustettu erilaisten yhteisöjen kohtaamisella, heidän arkeensa tervetulleeksi kutsutuksi tulemisella ja luottamuksella, joka mahdollistaa tekemiseen mukaan heittäytymisen ilman selkeää päämäärää. Minulle se on merkinnyt paljon. Dementikkojen, koululaisryhmien, erityisnuorten, ikäihmisten ja mielensterveyshaasteiden kanssa elävien parissa, heidän kanssaan toimiessani taiteilijuuteni on kasvanut eheäksi, kokonaiseksi ja omanlaisekseni.

Hybriditaiteilijaksi voidaan määritellä taiteilija, joka valikoi itselleen mieluisan ja mielekkään portfolion erilaisia tehtäviä (Karttunen, 2017). Näin toimiessaan, perinteiset raja-aidat ansaintalogiikan ja taiteen välillä huomiotta jättävä taiteilija omaksuu jatkuvasti uusia taitoja, jotka toisaalta parantavat yksilön työllistymismahdollisuuksia, mutta myös vakiinnuttavat mahdollisuuden jatkaa taiteellista työtä (kuva 11.). Oma motiivini toiminimen perustamiseen ja vahvasti yrittäjäksi identifioitumiseen löytyy juuri tältä arvopohjalta. Koin, että haluan luoda jotain pysyvää ja omista käsissäni hallittavissa olevaa taiteelliselle ja muulle osaamiselleni perustuvaa työtä. Pohdin jatkuvasti useiden vaikuttajien ristipaineessa omaa paikkaani ja turvaverkkoani myös kuvallisen työskentelyni kautta (kuva 14.). Perheellisenä ihmisenä en nähnyt realistisena vaihtoehtona hakea isolla työmäärällä epätodennäköisiä apurahoja lyhyisiin määräaikaisiin prosesseihin ilman tietoa tulevasta. Avaan tätä teemaa hieman lisää työllisyyspolitiikan näkökulmasta.

Kuva 9. & 10: Ilmaisun tukemiseen on käytettävissä yksilöllisiä tukitoimia. Kuva: Niina Oinas.

TAITEILIJAN TYÖLLISYYSPOLITIIKAN RATAISSA

Taiteen tekemisen ja taiteen yhteiskunnallisen merkittävyyden rooli on ollut itselleni aina ensisijainen arvo, mutta koko koulutusurani ajan kehittymistäni on varjostanut huoli tulevasta, työllistymisestä ja taide-alan epävarmuudesta. Tämä murehtiminen on toisaalta estänyt minua heittäytymästä perinteisille taiteen kentille ja toisaalta ajanut minua pohtimaan ja kehittämään taiteen asemaa yhteiskunnassa. Ensimmäisen kerran, kun kuulin virallisessa kontekstissa puhuttavan taiteen hyvinvointivaikutuksista, muistan ajatelleeni, että ehdottomasti taiteessa on jotain taikavoimaa; niin monet eri alojen taiteilijat elivät lähes vailla tuloja tai sosiaaliturvaa, elossa sinnitellen, usein vieläpä aktiivisina yhteiskunnallisina toimijoina vaikuttaen.

Edellä hahmoteltujen, samanaikaisten ilmiöiden lisäksi suomalaisessa yhteiskunnassa on jo pitkään painittu taiteilijoiden, taide- ja kulttuurialan ammattilaisten ja asiantuntijoiden korkean työttömyysprosentin kanssa (Rautiainen & Roiha, 2015). Taide- ja kulttuurialat työllistävät pääasiassa matalapalkkaiseen pätätöihin, freelancereina tai monityöläisyyteen muovautuneessa työsuhteessa vailla selkeitä työsuhte-etuja tai vakautta. Erityisen haastava työllistymistilanne on kuvataiteilijoilla. Apurahalla tuettava työmuoto on pätättäistä, vaikeasti tulkittavissa työvoimapolitiittisissa päätöksissä ja hakijamäärien kasvaessa kilpailu alalla on kova. Esimerkiksi Taiteenedistämiskeskuksesta vuonna 2020 hakemuksia tuli ennätysmäärä, runsaat 2 800 kappaletta. Määrä kasvoi edellisvuodesta lähes kymmenellä prosentilla (Taike, 2020). Rahoitusta riitti vain 5–9 prosentille hakijoista, vaikka esimerkiksi kuvataiteeseen jaettiin määrällisesti eniten apurahoja, 58 kappaletta (Taike, 2020).

Kokonaisuudessaan apurahajärjestelmä on viime vuosina saanut osakseen paljon kritiikkiä vanhanaikaisuudesta, niin sanotun tähtikulttuurin ylläpitämisestä ja työehtoja polkevan työmuodon tukemisesta. Muun muassa Lehenkari (2018) on Pro Gradu -työssään käsitellyt kuvataiteilijoiden asemaa nykyajan Suomessa, muuttuvan taidekentän paradoksissa. Hän toteaa muun muassa, että kieli muokkaa asenteita, ja liikkeelle taiteilijoiden yhteiskunnallisen aseman parantamiseksi voisi lähteä myös kielelliseltä tasolta.

Kuva 11: Niina Oinas, 2021. *Verkosto / Network*. Käyntikortit. Kuva: Niina Oinas.

Apuraha merkitsee jotain aivan muuta kuin palkka, taiteen tukeminen jotain muuta kuin taiteeseen investointi (Lehenkari, 2018). Taiteilijan työ on erityistä, eikä sitä tule suoraan verrata muihin töihin, mutta arvostusta se ansaitsee siinä missä muutkin ammatit (Lehenkari, 2018). Useat taiteilijat, taiteen tutkijat ja kehittäjät puhuvat myös taiteilijapalkan puolesta (Ylitalo, 2020). Osana sosiaali- ja terveysalan työkenttää yhteisötaiteen kehittämisessä painotetaan palkallista, sosiaaliturvan ja vakuutusten piiriin kuuluvaa uudenlaista taiteen ammattilaisuutta.

Luovilla aloilla hyvin tunnettu palkattoman työn käsite tarkoittaa taidealoilla hyvin tyypillistä tilannetta, jossa taiteilijan oletetaan antavan työpanoksensa täysin ilmaiseksi näkyvyyden tai muun vastaavan varjolla (Hirvi-Ijäs ym., 2020). Vastentahtoiseen yrittäjyyteen viitataan, kun henkilö on ajautunut yrittäjyyteen olosuhteiden pakosta ilman varsinaista halua yrittäjyyteen. Omalla kohdallani kyse oli tavallaan pakotetusta yrittäjyydestä. Kotipaikkakunnallani ei ollut taitojani tai intohimojani vastaavaa palkkatyötä tarjolla. Jos avoin paikka joskus jostain ilmaantui, hakijoita oli yhtä työpaikkaa kohtaan toista sataa henkilöä. Koin olevani pakotettu yrittäjyyteen, koska vaihtoehtoina olivat työttömyys tai alan vaihto. Samalla halusin näyttää, että taideperustainen yritys voidaan ottaa vakavasti monialaisella, uuden ajan yritys kentällä.

Viimeisen viiden vuoden ajan taiteilijoita ja muita taide- ja kulttuurialan ammattilaisia on Suomessa yhä enenevässä määrin kannustettu yrittäjyyteen tai kevyt-yrittäjyyteen. Pikaratkaisuna alan järjestäytyminen, ja samalla myös helpommin löydettäväksi uusille yhteistyökumppaneille tekeminen, kuulostaa mainiolta ainakin tietäen edellisessä osiossa kuvaillun taiteen tarpeen ja kysynnän olemassa olon. Yhteiskunnan rakenteet eivät kuitenkaan vielä tunnista taiteenalan yrittäjyyttä kovin hyvin. Haastetta lisää se, että taidekouluissa ja -tutkinnoissa ansaintalogiikkaan pohdintaa ei ole suuremmin ollut ennen viime vuosien kehitystä. Muutoksia yhteiskunnallisiin rakenteisiin tehdään hitaasti, mutta 2020-luvulle tultaessa taiteilijat on tunnustettu entistä paremmin ammattilaisiksi ja esimerkiksi verotusta pikkuhiljaa pyritti muokkaamaan alalle soveltuvampaan suuntaan.

Syksyllä 2016 olin innoissani vuosia muhineen ajatuksen konkretisoitumisesta toiminimeksi ja omaksi yritystoiminnakseni. Uteliaisuus rohkaisi hypyssä tuntemattomaan ja uskomisen omaan visioon ajoivat eteenpäin. Samaan aikaan koin olevani todella yksin. Koin taiteen kentältä kantautuvan epäileviä katseita ja epäluuloa toimintani suhteen. Tunnistin rikkovani joitain tiettyjä normeja, mutta en vonut jäädä asiaa pohtimaan enempää, se olisi lamaannuttanut oman kehittymiskykyni. Myös taiteen välineellistäminen on yritystoimintaan liitettävä uhkakuva, joka täytyy tunnistaa taiteen ominaisuutteen vaalimiseksi. Itselleni oli kokoajan selvää, että toimin eettisesti, moraalisesti ja taiteen erityisyyttä korostaen. Seuraavana syksynä pidin yhteisöllisen valokuvanäyttelyn Pelkosenniemen Pyhätunturin Aittakurussa ja sain valtavasti positiivista palautetta osallistujilta. Jälleen osallistujien ja kohtaamisten tuoma tunne vakuutti, että valitsemani tie on minulle se oikea.

Pehmeistä arvoista ponnistavana tekijänä koin olevani yksin myös yrittäjäyhteisöissä. Jouduin kerta toisensa jälkeen selittämään yritystoimintaani ja asia tuntui kiinnostavan monia. Koin, että toimijuuteeni yrittäjänä ei suhtauduttu kovin vakavasti. Yrittäjäkentällä taiteellista toimintaa kohtaan on paljon ennakkoluuloja ja epätietoisuutta. Taiteellista toimintaa pidetään helposti jonkinasteisena puuhasteluna, vaikka tarkoitus on vakavasti elättää itsensä omalla osaamisellaan. Samaankaltaisesta arvostuksen noususta käydään kamppanjointia myös lastenkulttuurin puolella. Itse en tee eroa työskentelyssä lasten, nuorten tai minkätahansa ikäisten tai eri taustaisten ihmisten kanssa. Kaikessa yhteisötaiteellisessa toiminnassa on kyse lopulta samoista elementeistä: kohtaamisesta, näkyväksi tulemisesta ja uusien asioiden oivaltamisesta (kuva 13.) Jatkuvasti lisääntyvät luovien alojen yrittäjämäärät sekä taidemaailman avautuminen uusiin ympäristöihin hälventävät osaltaan vanhanaikaisia mielikuvia ja tuovat taiteilijoita samoihin kahvipöytiin muiden elinkeinojen edustajien kanssa.

Muutaman toimintavuoden jälkeen pystyin täysin työllistämään itseni yritykseni kautta. Toiminnan keskiössä oleva taidetoiminnan ohjaaminen sosiaali- ja terveyssektorin rajapinnoilla nosti isoja arvokysymyksiä eteeni. Periaatteessa kysyntää ja tilausta oli, mutta ei siinä muodossa, jossa itse olisin kokenut työni eettisesti ja pitkäjänteisesti kestäväksi. Turhauduin siihen, että toiminnot usein tyypistyivät tunnin tai parin virkistystoiminnaksi, vaikka minulla olisi ollut paljon enemmän annettavaa. Lisäksi haasteeksi nousi eettinen vastuu. Minulta puuttui työmuotoni rinnalta sosiaali- ja terveysalalle muuten olennaisena kuuluva työpari sekä työnohjaus. Koin ison vastuun asiakkaiden hyvinvoinnista saamatta itse tukea tai todellista vaikutusmahdollisuutta asiakkaiden tilanteisiin.

Tutkimukseni tarkastelee näistä lähtökohdista tukielementtejä ja rakenteellisia muotoja siihen, miten taiteilijat ja taiteen alojen ammattilaiset voivat työllistyä uusille aloille muille ammattikunnille vakiintuneilla työehtosopimuksilla ja etuuksilla taiteen itseisarvon säilyttäen? Taiteilijat työllistyvät kulttuurihyvinvoinnin toimijakentälle kulttuurihyvinvoinnin portaita (taulukko 1.) mukaillen: tekemällä omaa taidettaan, ohjaamalla taide- ja kulttuuritoimintaa, soveltamalla taidetta spesifisti hyvinvoinnin ja terveyden edistämiseksi tai laajentamalla taidelähtöistä toimintaa työelämän kehittämiseksi (Houni ym., 2020). Tutkimusintressini keskittyy edelleen jatkuvassa tutkimuksessani tarkastelemaan taiteilijan asemaa nimenomaan soveltavan taiteen ohjaajana ja yhteisötaiteilijana sosiaali- ja terveysalalla kulttuurihyvinvoinnin merkitysten alaisuudessa. Tutkimuksellani selkiytän määritelmiä taiteilijan osaamistarpeista osana hoitoa ja kuntoutusta tehtävää monialaista työtä.

Muuttuva työelämä ja yhteiskunnalliset haasteet ovat kasvattaneet tarvetta taiteelliselle toiminnalle, rutiinien uudelleen ajattelulle ja luovalle kehittämisosaamiselle. Yhteiskunnallisesta näkökulmasta yksi haastavimmista työkuulttuurin muutoksista koskettaa juuri sosiaali- ja terveysalaa. Työelämän murroksen kanssa samaan aikaan sosiaali- ja terveysalan organisaatiot ovat ymmärtäneet taiteen tekijöiden potentiaalini omassa ympäristössään, perinteisen hoitotyön rinnalla kulkevana voimavarana (Lehikoinen, 2017). Taide luo parhaimmillaan vapaan tilan, jossa ihmiset uskaltavat kohdata toisensa ja nähdä asioita uudesta suunnasta (Rantala ym., 2013).

Kuva 12: Taiteilija tuo mukanaan lupauksen jostain erilaisesta, tavanomaisesta poikkeavasta tapahtumasta. Kuva: Niina Oinas.

Taulukko 1. Kulttuurihyvinvoinnin portaat

Itä-Suomen Hyvinvointivoimalan strategiaa mukaillen (Mäkinen & Riekkinen, 2018)

1. Esiintymistoiminta, näyttelyt, taideinvestoinnit ja arkkitehtuuri (kokeminen)

2. Omaehtoinen harrastaminen (tekeminen ja oppiminen)

3. Osallistavat taiteilijavierailut (esim. yhteisömuusikot ja -taiteilijat) sekä soveltavan taiteen käyttö

4. Eri alojen välinen yhteistyö koulutuksessa ja työelämässä

- yhteiskehittäminen
- uusi osaaminen, hybridiset työnkuvat
- kuntoutumista edistävä toiminta
- erilaiset terapiat

5. Pysyvä toiminta: kulttuuri osana sosiaali- ja terveysalan toimintaa

- systemisyys, moninäkökulmaisuus
- kokonaisvaltainen hyvinvointi
- toimintakulttuurin muutos
- työhyvinvointi

Kuvituskuvat: kuva 1. Kuvia ikiajassa - näyttelyn avajaiset 2017, kuva 2. Koululaisten taidekerhon tuokiosta 2017, kuva 3. Kolpeneen palvelukeskuksen päiväpajan taidetuokiosta 2020, kuva 4. Yksityiskohta teoksesta Verkosto 2021, kuva 5. yksityiskohta valokuvasta Valoa 2019 Kuvat: Niina Oinas

JOHTOPÄÄTÖKSET

Taidealan opintopoluilla minulle ei ole muodostunut minkäänlaista virallista pätevyyttä liittyen muistisairauksiin, vaativan erityisen tuen ja vammaislain piirissä elävien henkilöiden arkeen tai mielenterveyden haasteisiin vastaamiseen. Muodollinen pätemättömyyteni on kuitenkin ollut toimijuuteni keskiössä hierakioista vapaasta taiteilija-asemasta toimiessani. Taidealan koulutukset ovat valmentaneet minut kohtaamaan erilaisuutta, vaalimaan empatiakykyäni, hiomaan tarkkavaisuuttani ja kehittämään luovaa ongelmatilanteiden ratkaisukykyäni. Erilainen toimintatapa ja uudenlaiset ajattelumallit ovat olleet työni tuoma erityinen lisä sosiaali- ja terveysalan käytäntöihin. Tätä taiteen vapautta ja olemusta korostetaan paljon juuri taiteen vaikuttavuudesta puhuttaessa.

Jotta vastuu ja alan kehittyminen eivät jäisi yksittäisen taiteilijan toiminnan varaan, alan standardisointi ja määrittely ovat tarpeen myös taiteen tekijän työnkuvan hallinnassa. Kokemukseni mukaan yksittäiset taiteilijat ovat nykytilanteessa liian suuren vastuun kantajina ilman turvaverkkoa, vaikka taiteen arvoa korostetaankin jatkuvasti enemmän ja enemmän hyvinvointipuheissa.

Käynnissä oleva taideperustainen toimintatutkimukseni kehittää taiteilijan työnkuvaa tukevia, yhteiskunnan rakenteisiin asettuvia määritelmiä sille, miten taidetoiminta voitaisiin eettisesti ja kestävästi sisällyttää sosiaali- ja terveyssektorille. Hyötyjä, tarvetta ja vaikuttavuutta taiteesta löytyy, mutta alan kehittämisessä huomio täytyy pitää taiteen erityisluonteen säilymisessä ja ei-tietämisen vapaudessa. Taiteellista toimintaa täytyy kuitenkin kyetä standardisoimaan ja skaalaamaan, jotta palvelua voidaan sisällyttää pysyviin toimintamuotoihin sosiaali- ja terveysalalla. Standardisoimalla luodaan alojen välille yhteinen kieli, jota molemmat osapuolet voivat yhteistyön onnistumiseksi vaalia ja myös kehittää. Haasteita toiminnan vakiintumisen tiellä edelleen on, mutta ala etenee nyt kohti rakenteita tarpeiden, tutkimustiedon ja osaamisen kohdatessa.

Kiitos: Lapin yliopisto on tukenut tutkimuksen toteuttamista

Kuva 13: Taiteellinen toiminta antaa työkaluja tunteiden, ajatusten ja identiteetin käsittelyyn kaiken ikäisille ihmisille.
Kuva: Niina Oinas

Kuva 14: Niina Oinas, 2021. *Kaikki on hyvin / Everything is just fine*, akryyli vanerille, 122 X 170, 2021. Kuva: Niina Oinas.

Kiitos: Lapin yliopisto on tukenut tutkimuksen toteuttamista.

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Sculpting Places with Play: Revealing the Alternative Dimension (of Place) with Participatory Photoplay

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Biography

Nina Luostarinen is a Doctoral Candidate at the University of Lapland. She is fascinated by visual things in general and especially by the power of photography. A common thread in her work has been believing in serendipity, existence of the invisible worlds and enabling illusions. In her current work she is researching the possibilities of art-based play in regards to place attachment.

Abstract

This visual essay works at the confluence of art, place and play and presents a practice which asks: what can happen if we take a group of adults and classical paintings as inspiration and have them play together in specific places? It aims to demonstrate the visual souvenirs of adult play, the photographs taken by the participants. The objective is to interpret them in order to gain an understanding of how hierarchy-free encounters in the liminal space of play can foster empathy for places. Pausing to gaze at the visual data, it seems that with art-based play, we create lasting memories after which the place, the players and the source art can never be seen with indifference again. This can

lead to emotions, actions and activism towards a more desirable future.

Keywords

Re-interpretation; empathy for places; photoplay; future; art-based intervention

Figure 1: Participants have been introduced to the Mätasmetäs artistic method and given an excuse to indulge in play. Photograph by Nina Luostarinen, 2019.

The film spoof: An introduction

This visual essay presents my second Art-Based Action Research (ABAR) research cycle of an artistic method called Mätäsmetäs. The Mätäsmetäs artistic method is one excerpt of my assemblage of piloted experiments, which are all linked to the phenomenon of ludic turn (Sutton-Smith, 1997), the shift in sensibility that enables experiencing living through play. My experiments share a common question: when creating a playful intervention within a place, thus revealing its narrative and otherworldly dimensions, can we generate the soil for place empathy to emerge?

I am a doctoral candidate in the University of Lapland, Faculty of Arts and Design, and the Mätäsmetäs development process presented here is part of my research, which deals with the confluence of art, place and play. Mätäsmetäs has been developed since 2014 following the principles of ABAR. As Jokela and Huhmarniemi (2018) state, ABAR is a research strategy which guides the progress of research in the cycles of action research and uses art as a catalyst for development work. The original aim of development work in Mätäsmetäs was to give visitors new insights into recreational parks (Vartiainen & Luostarinen, 2015). To reach this goal, the playful task was created: make a photographic reinterpretation of nature-themed original folklore, literature or a fine art painting related to that place. The results of the first cycle were surprisingly versatile and profound and thus encouraged me to continue with this topic. The prime motivator for these additional sequels was to enhance empathy for places. It seemed that if people were to discover and playfully experience the narrative layers of places, lasting memories and emotional bonds would be created (Luostarinen, 2020). Based on the findings of the first Mätäsmetäs project, it seemed evident that there was potential for this artistic method to be developed further (Luostarinen & Hautio, 2019, Luostarinen 2019a).

Since the original project in three national parks in Finland in 2014, the artistic method has been sprouting out in various places for different groups. It was adopted by, for example, a refugee integration staff member and a mental health nurse for their purposes and reuse. I have developed this artistic method further and conducted workshops with the method in venues such as the *Sustainable Placeshaping Conference* in Tampere, Finland (Luostarinen, 2019b), *The EUROPARC Conference* in Jurmala, Latvia and the *Celebrating Our Diversity Forum* in Hanasaari, Finland. These last two are the image sources for this visual essay (Figures 1–10). Even though it may seem like a huge leap from a national park into conference surroundings, all the conferences were dealing with topics somewhat linked to this artistic method. In Tampere, the conference was about means of placeshaping; in Jurmala, it involved national park staff from all over Europe; and in Hanasaari, it was about developing an inclusive and sustainable future. So, the participants were eager to find new tools for their objectives, and, furthermore, all the mentioned conference locations were set in noteworthy nature locations. So, my second ABAR development cycle mainly focused on comparing these leader-guided workshops in varied surroundings with the first cycle, which was tasks distributed individually online and through posters.

The shutter speed: Theory

In the Mätäsmetäs artistic method, the key elements are imagination, alternative worlds and adult playfulness. The method's development work is related to Abramovich's (2020) thoughts on parallel worlds and how artists should help to reveal these invisible dimensions as well as to Salami's (2020) idea of sensuous knowledge. The artistic method encourages participants to dive into places in multisensory ways and find new meanings of the objects, textures and structures that exists there. The aim of the artistic method is also related to synaesthesia – perceiving other dimensions of reality (Campen, 2007). Through this method, introducing playful art-based interventions into places, we can create intended synaesthesia even for those who do not have the neurological capacity for it. The artistic method encourages pretend play in adults: seeing alternative and narrative dimensions and beyond the mundane.

Lennon (2015) suggests that an artist is needed for suggesting alternative patterns of imagining in artistic interventions, but I propose that artists are merely needed to unleash the participants' imaginations and give them an excuse or permission to behave in an unorthodox way. As Deterding (2018) states, alternative, adult-appropriate motives are needed to account for their play, to give permission for an adult to engage in playful or imaginary activity. In the case of Mätäsmetäs, the alibi to reach this liminal space is found in the form of a living statue reinterpretation task. Or, as Legaard (2020) sums it: play experiences typically unfold in a realm of their own, typically in a middle ground between reality and imagination. So, we still have the place where the playing took place, but we blend it with the fanciful play-layer. Rosen (2017) pointed out that play can provide a counterpoint to cynicism because play allows experimentation and creation as well as imagining and enacting new ways of being and living. She suggests that, conversely, activism can help shift the contours of play. Linking emotions and imagination to activism is not to discount the importance of rational deliberation but rather to add to it. Bruce (2011) sees play as rehearsing for the future and Shepard (2011) sees play as a step away from reality to conjure up new possibilities for the future. I agree very much with them that if we, though play, can imagine the (un)desired future, it can lead to activism. Rosen (2017) and Bruce (2011) discuss about play as politics in regards children. I am willing to suggest that the same arguments are valid for adults as well.

Pithouse-Morgan and Samaras (2020) search for a sense of place using bricolage as a method, describing it to be working on something in an experimental way, using materials that are readily available. In Mätäsmetäs, this just happens. People use the props available at the place or in their pockets and experiment with how they can be used to depict their imagined narrative created in that place. As Rannikko (2020) suggests, places are not only geographical places, but they can also be emotional communities where one's own and shared stories are being searched. All this intertwined with Tuan's (1977) thoughts on how place is created and maintained through people's emotional attachment and Thrift's idea of how place is involved with embodiment (Hubbard et al., 2004) leads to motivation to re-experiment with reinterpreting or paraphrasing (not mimicking!) art in various places to evoke the multisensory experience of place. Positioning oneself in scenery demonstrates the proportions, and enacting in art-based play helps to foster new kinds of relationships to nature and place and to the development of an environmentally appropriate culture (Fromm, 2009; Heyd, 2007).

Film processing: The research method

During the past years, there has been a phenomenon of statues being dismantled (New York Times, 2020) for representing racist persons or evil reigns. With the images presented here, I am asking if we can reverse this course of disassembling, turn the idea upside down and possibly create alternative realities by setting up scenes with living statues. If we play at being sculptures and enact with places when doing so, can we, at the same time, carve out the desired future?

The Mätäsmetäs artistic method borrows an idea from the popular Finnish children's play Photographer (Leikkipäivä, n.d.) in which participants make living statues. With this, I aim to bring a double meaning to Beuys' idea (Mesch & Michely, 2007) of social sculpture: everyone can be an artist. In Mätäsmetäs, both the facilitator and the participants are seen as artists. And here, additionally, everyone can be a sculpture worth being photographed when reinterpreting existing artworks. Living statues do not need to be violently dismantled, they stay solid only as visual souvenirs of the play: the photographs.

Leavy (2020) suggests that images can make lasting impressions. Visual art may serve as a vehicle for transmitting ideology and can be just as effectively used to challenge, dislodge and transform belief systems and stereotypes. She explains how in participatory projects the aesthetic quality of the resulting visual art may take a back seat to the other advantages of the methodology but underlies how, although produced by amateurs, the visual art produced by research participants can still be quite powerful, especially with respect to conveying emotion.

In Mätäsmetäs, the groups chose the original art images that pleased them and sparked their imaginations for reinterpretation from the large – more than 100 pieces – collection of paintings suggested and printed for them. Here, the visual art worked in intricate ways: as an assortment for inspiration and finally as a photographic pastiche at the end of the participatory play. The participants were asked to freely associate and update the original painting and make pastiche of it to depict either a current situation or the imaginable future. First, they were instructed to build their interpretation in miniature. In order to stage the miniature interpretations of the original, the participants needed to observe their surroundings with a new curiosity. They gained a multisensory experience of the place while touching the materials and envisioning their proportions. The next stage was to create free interpretations of the same painting. Participants were especially encouraged to re-narrate it related to the place where it was interpreted and focus on the roles in their groups. In the discussion part of the workshop, they shared thoughts on transferring the idea in their own surroundings.

Also, the results are analysed by gaining an understanding of and interpreting the visual material: the photographs produced by the participants. Excerpts of proofs of play moments are presented side-by-side with the original visual source art, and each output is briefly discussed when presented. All of them aim to answer the overall questions of how to get adults to play enthusiastically in the middle of a conference, how to prompt them to build up imaginary scenes based on iconic nature-themed fine art paintings and what kind of alternative dimensions both the place and the original art gain during this process.

The contact sheet: The case

Figure 2: The participants discovered the place from new angles during their play. Photograph by Nina Luostarinen, 2019.

Figure 3: The final interpretations with the inspirational piece behind. The participants told a new story while explaining their interpretations. Here, they explained how the migrants crossed the Baltic sea guarded by an angel-like creature. Play can address serious topics while being tactile and fun to make. Original painting *Sammon puolustus (Defending the Sampo)* by Akseli Gallen-Kallela, 1896 (reprinted courtesy of the Turku Art Museum). Photograph by Nina Luostarinen, 2019

Figure 4: Here, the tortoise statue located on Jurmala Beach symbolizes the endangered sea turtle trying to come to lay eggs but is being surrounded by tourists who want selfies with it and clashing with animal activists. Original painting same as in Figure 3. Photograph by Nina Luostarinen, 2019.

Figure 5: Here, the original piece of fine art describing reindeer hunting has transferred into an interpretation depicting serious bullying. Original painting *Seremonia (Ceremony)* by Ilkka Lehtinen, 1977 (fragment), (reprinted courtesy of Kouvola Art Museum). Photograph by group 6 in Jurmala, 2019.

Figure 6: In order to find your next stepping stone between good and evil choices, you need to leave your shoes behind.

Original painting *Tienhaarassa (At the Crossroad)* by Hugo Simberg, 1896. (reprinted courtesy of Ateneum Art Museum). Photograph by group 3 in Hanasaari, 2019.

Figure 7: In the making of....in order to create art, some sacrifices are required. Luckily, there was a hairdryer, and the stockings could be dried out after the workshop. Photograph by Ella Kapias, 2019.

Figures 8 and 9: Two different interpretations by international groups about the same original painting.

The interpretation in Figure 8 depicts our dependency on our mobile phones and how we miss our real surroundings because of this.

In Figure 9, the vehicle suddenly stops, and someone flies from aboard. This group had to do so many takes to get the desired image that they laughed so much that the whole place was filled with laughter.

Original painting *Kesänviettoa Ramsön saarella (Summer Day at Island Ramsö)* by Olga Forslund, 1922, (reprinted courtesy of Helsinki Art Museum).

Photographs by group 2 in Jurmala and group 4 in Hanasaari, 2019.

Figure 10, video 1: The ghost from the illustration by Tove Janson in the book *Exploits of Moominpappa*, 1950, has turned into a nightmare of too many trees being timbered. (To see the video, follow this link: <https://bit.ly/3xHWP4I>). The original reference image can be seen here: <https://bit.ly/3xHWP4I>

Figure 11: Art-based playful interventions into places have the potential to generate emotions. Emotions can lead to place attachment and empathy towards places where playing occurred. Once revealed, the narrative and playful dimension and layers of places can no longer be unseen.

The exposition: Discussion

This ABAR research cycle showed me the potential of the Mätäsmetäs artistic method for social interaction as well as the earlier goals of place awe and empathy. As all the conference topics where these workshops took place were dealing with consciousness and fair development, the depth of the interpretations – even in the limited workshop time (30–90 minutes) – was overwhelming to me. While not naively claiming that play would be immune to historically sedimented power relations, I agree with Rosen (2017) that if adults approach play within openness, imaginative play has the potential to allow engagement with the possibilities of a more just future. As the images in this visual essay demonstrate, the power of play seems undeniable in evoking a multisensory, emotional and lasting art-based experience of place and also in allowing the experiencing of hierarchy-free encounters in the liminal space of play. The participants brought new and up-to-date meanings to the source art and interacted with the places in witty ways. With a careful selection of inspirational imagery, further adaptations could be easily developed, serving both to find new insights for chosen art pieces as well as to fertilize the novel perception of place. If we create visual images of desired futures, we are creating goals to reach for, and perhaps that can lead to lesser need for disassembling in the coming decades.

As to the evaluations of the conducted workshops, I was overwhelmed by the enthusiasm with which the given task was embraced. I was prepared to be accused of arrogance and to be despised: why would adults want to play outdoors when they have come to a conference to discuss serious academic topics indoors? So, I might have started apologetically and felt like a jester. But no, the opportunity was faced broad-mindedly, and no pushing was needed from my, the facilitator's, side. It was not long till I could hear bubbling laughter from the surrounding bushes. The instant feedback I received from the participants in all the workshops was sparking with ardour and mirth – rare emotions to be spotted in symposiums. Many participants in these international conferences said that they will take the artistic method home for local adaptation.

Based on my facilitator experiences of Mätäsmetäs, having witnessed participants' reactions and the visual data produced during the workshops, I suggest that emotional experiences may be the key factors needed to plant a seed for place empathy and our equal existence in places. With empathy towards places and a vivid relation to them, we can pursue the desired future: the future we have already imagined and visually realized.

Watermark: Conclusions

The Mätäsmetäs artistic method is useful by connecting play, the interpretation of visual art and social interactions in relation to a place. There could be several pedagogical implementations, such as in building strategies and future scenarios; in art and environmental education; for refugee and migrant integration into local places, heritage and folklore; and in mental health recovery process. I can also see a potential in tourism and destination design: what a fun product through which to deepen one's connection with a heritage or natural site and at the same time find new insights from your travel mates or colleagues when seeing them taking on a new role during the play.

Playing and having fun is not an obstacle to addressing serious topics. I argue that it is quite the opposite. With art-based play, we create lasting memories after which the place, the players and the source art can never be seen with indifference again, leading to emotions, actions and activism towards a more desirable future.

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Empatian ja yhteisön laajentaminen taidekasvatuksen ja yhteisötaiteen keinoin

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Lapin yliopisto

Biografia

Maria Huhmarniemi (TaT) on taiteilija-tutkija, joka käsittelee pohjoiseen liittyviä kysymyksiä sekä ympäristöasioita, kuten ihmisen ja luonnon suhdetta sekä ympäristövastuullisuutta, -politiikkaa ja -etiikka. Hän työskentelee Lapin yliopiston taiteiden tiedekunnassa lehtorina sekä erilaisissa taiteen, pedagogiikan ja aluekehityksen hankkeissa. Hän on julkaissut useita tutkimusartikkeleita ja toiminut myös julkaisujen toimittajana.

Abstrakti

Ympäristökriisit ja yksinäisyyden kokemukset haastavat taidekasvattajia ja taiteilijoita tuottamaan tilanteita, joissa osallistujat tuntevat yhteisöllisyyttä. Posthumanistinen filosofia suuntaa yhteisökäsitystä verkostoksi, joka sisältää myös ei-inhimillisen luonnon. Tässä visuaalisessa esseessä tarkastelen yhteisön laajentamista taidekasvatuksen ja yhteisötaiteen keinoin taideperustaisessa toimintatutkimuksessa. Analysoin yhteisöllisyyttä luovan matkailun kontekstissa paikallisten ja vieraiden kohtaamisena sekä osallistavassa installaatiotaiteessa, joka pyrkii ohjaamaan vuorovaikutteisiin luontokokemuksiin. Esimerkeissäni taidekasvatus vaikuttaa matkailualle ja taidemaailmaan. Taidekasvatuksen ja taiteen tuottama yhteisö on avoimuuteen ja empaattisuuteen

pyrkivä ja vuorovaikutus on kehollista, sanatonta tai monikielistä. Yhteisöllisyys laajenee myös taiteilijatyöryhmiksi ja kollektiiveiksi, joissa taiteilijat tekevät yhteistyötä toisten taiteilijoiden, luonnonmateriaalien ja -elementtien kanssa.

Abstract

Environmental crises and experiences of loneliness challenge art educators and artists to create situations where participants feel they belong to a community. Posthumanistic philosophy directs the conception of community into a network that also includes the nonhuman nature. In this visual essay, I examine the expansion of the sense of community through the means of art education and community art in art-based action research. I analyse community in the context of creative tourism as an encounter between locals and guests, and in a participatory installation art that seeks to guide the audience into an interactive nature experience. In my examples, art education affects the tourism industry and the art world. The community produced by art education and art strives for openness and empathy, and the interaction is bodily, nonverbal or multilingual. Communitality also expands into artist working groups and collectives, where artists collaborate with other artists, natural materials and other elements of nature.

Asiasanat

Yhteisötaide, luova matkailu, yhteisö, osallistava taide, taideperustainen toimintatutkimus

Keywords

Community art, creative tourism, community, participatory art, art-based action research

Kohti empaattisia yhteisöjä

Ympäristökriisit, posthumanistinen filosofinen ajattelu sekä lisääntyvät yksinäisyyden kokemukset haastavat taidekasvatusta ja yhteisötaidetta. Ympäristökriisien myötä tutkijat sekä taide- ja ympäristökasvatuksen kehittäjät peräänkuuluttavat entistä empaattisempaa ja vuorovaikutteisempaa luontokokemusta ja -suhdetta (Ylirisku, 2021; Värrä, 2018).

Posthumanistinen filosofia avaa perinteisen yhteisökäsityksen laajeneviksi verkostoiksi, jotka sisältävät myös ei-inhimillisen luonnon, kuten myös koneet ja muun materiaallisen maailman (Lummaa & Rojola, 2014; Tammi & Hohti, 2017). Samaan aikaan tutkijat ovat todenneet taiteeseen osallistumisen ehkäisevän yksinäisyyden kokemusta (Perkins ym., 2021). Arvojen ja elämäntapojen syvälinen muutos on todettu välttämättömäksi kasvatuksessa ekososiaaliseen sivistykseen (Salonen & Bardy, 2015; Soini & Birkeland, 2014) ja taidekasvatuksessa eko- tai luontokulttuuriseen kestävyteen (Huhmarniemi ym., 2020; Huhmarniemi, Jokela ym., 2021). Myös taiteellisen ja taideperustaisen tutkimuksen metodikirjallisuudessa peräänkuulutetaan tutkimusta, joka johtaa aiempaa empaattisempiin inklusiivisempiin yhteisöihin (Siegesmund & Cahnmann-Taylor, 2008).

Kuva 1: *Loitsutulet-*
tanssiesitys,
Kuva: Minna Kovero, 2021.

Kuva 2: *Loitsutulet-*
työryhmä. Kuva: Maija
Tavastila, 2021.

Tässä visuaalisessa esseessä kuvaan ja pohdin empatian ja yhteisön laajentamista taidekasvatuksen ja yhteisötaiteen keinoin taideperustaisessa toimintatutkimuksessa kahdessa pitkäkestoisessa tutkimusyhteistyössä. Luovan matkailun tutkimuksellinen kehittäminen on Lapin yliopistossa kohdentunut muun muassa ympäristötaiteen käyttöön matkailuympäristöissä (Jokela ym., 2018), osallistavaan käsityömatkailuun (Kugapi ym., 2020; Huhmarniemi, Kugapi ym., 2021) ja luontokuvauksesta juonnettuihin matkailupalveluihin (Jokela ym., 2020; Jokela & Huhmarniemi, 2020a). Tässä esseessä käsittelemäni työpajat on toteutettu Taideperustaisia palveluja matkailuun -hankkeessa, jota Euroopan aluekehitysrahasto ja Lapin liitto ovat rahoittaneet. Hankkeessa on konseptoitu ja pilotoitu matkailupalveluita, joissa hyödynnetään kuva- ja tanssitaiteilijoiden osaamista, paikalliskulttuureja ja pohjoista luontoa transformatiivisten kokemusten mahdollistajana. Kehittämistutkimus jatkaa tutkimustraditiota, jossa Lapin yliopiston taiteiden tiedekunta on työskennellyt yhteistyössä matkailuyrittäjien kanssa 1990-luvulta alkaen yhteisötaiteen teorian ja tutkimuksen viitoittamana (Hiltunen, 1999, 2009). Taideperustaisten menetelmien kehittäminen matkailualalle on perustunut kestävän kehityksen tavoitteisiin tilanteessa, jossa matkailuelinkeino vaikuttaa voimakkaasti Lapin luontoon, kulttuuriin ja elinkeinoin. Kehittämistyö perustuu oletukseen, että taideperustaiset palvelut voisivat tukea matkailuelinkeinon ekologista, kulttuurista ja sosiaalista vastuullisuutta ja kestävyyttä.

Yksi esittelemäni produktio on osallistava installaatio, joka on toteutunut osana Acting on the Margins – Arts as a Social Sculpture (AMASS) -hanketta, joka on Euroopan Unionin Horisontti 2020 Transformations -ohjelmasta rahoitettu kansainvälinen tutkimushanke.

AMASS-hankkeessa tarkastellaan muun muassa kuvataidekasvatuksen ja kuvataiteen kokeiluita sosiaalisten ongelmien ratkaisemiseksi Euroopan reuna-alueilla. Teos *Kohtaa puu* -on sisällynyt AMASS-hankkeen kokeiluihin. Sen tausta on myös kansainvälisten tapahtumien International Socially Engaged Art Symposium Finland (ISEAS) (Huhmarniemi & Juhola, tulossa) ja Art Äkäslöpolo yhteistyönä toteuttamassa taidetyöpajassa, jossa yhteisötaide on toiminut interventiona ympäristökonflikteihin kyläyhteisössä (Huhmarniemi, 2018, 2021a, b).

kuva 3: Tuohityöpajan päätöshetki. Kuva: Tatiana Kravtsov, 2020.

Taidekasvatus yhteisöissä

Yhteisön käsitteen laajentaminen posthumanistisessa taide- ja ympäristökasvatuksessa nousee kehollisuuden ja aineellisuuden merkityksellisyyttä korostavista ajattelutavoista sekä ihmisen sidosten tunnistamisesta monenlaisiin elämää ylläpitäviin verkostoihin (Datta, 2016; Tammi & Hohti, 2017; Rautio & Stenvall, 2018; Ylirisku, 2021). Taiteilijat ja taidekasvattajat pyrkivät lisäämään ihmisten vuorovaikutusta ja yhteistyötä ei-inhimillisen luonnon kanssa, kun posthumanistinen ajattelu vaikuttaa taidekasvatuksen strategioihin ja pedagogisiin valintoihin (Ainalinpää, 2009; de Oliveira & Lopes, 2016; Rousell & Fell, 2018; Ylirisku, 2021). Ylirisku (2021) ehdottaa, että taidekasvatuksella niin sanotusti outoutettaisiin normatiivisia ihmis-luontosuhteita sekä suuntauduttaisiin entistä vahvemmin kriittisiin, kokeellisiin, avoloppuisiin ja tieteenoaloja ylittäviin strategioihin ja toimintatapoihin.

Tässä esseessä tarkastelen uudenlaisten ihmis-luontosuhteiden mahdollisuutta luovan matkailun alalla pilotoiduissa työpajoissa sekä osallistavassa installaatiotaiteessa. Posthumanismin lisäksi taustalla on dialoginen ja pedagoginen käänne nykytaiteessa (Kantonen, 2010; Kester, 2004). Tarkastelemani produktiot ovat toteutuneet Lapissa, jossa perinne- ja paikalliskulttuurit ovat sidoksissa vuodenaikoihin ja luonnon elementteihin siten, että paikallisten identiteettejä määrittelevää kulttuuria voi luonnehtia luontokulttuuriksi. Taiteilijat ja taidekasvattajat voivat ylläpitää ja uudistaa luontokulttuuria. Yhteisötaiteen tekijät ja osallistajat toimivat osana laajenevaa ja verkostoitunutta yhteisöä osana luontokulttuuria, jossa luonnon toimijuus tunnustetaan ja sitä kunnioitetaan (Huhmarniemi ym., 2020).

Yhteisöllisyys voi olla avointa tai muut poissulkevaa. Empatiatutkija Sami Keto (2018) on kuvaillut, että sosiaalisuutemme rajat vaikuttavat empatian kohteemme laajuuteen. Hän esittää, että on tärkeää pyrkiä olemaan tekemisissä monenlaisten ihmisten ja ihmisryhmien sekä eläinten kanssa ja laajentaa empatian piiriä tiedostaen, että ihmiskunta jakaa maapallon muun elämän kanssa (Keto, 2018). Empatiatutkimus siirtää ihmistä pois keskiöstä, kuten Yliriskun (2021) mukaan myös kriittiset, feministiset ja posthumanistiset teoriat. Taidekasvatukselle ja taiteelle siirtymä on haastava: ihmisyyden on edelleen taiteen tekijyyden ja kokijuiden ytimessä, vaikka erilaisia posthumanistisia taide- ja taidekasvatuskokeiluita tehdään enenevässä määrin.

"Kun jokaisessa kortissa on erilaiset puunsyyt ja mehiläisväriseissä tuoksu ja muita aisteja, tekniikka avaa itsessään luonnon voimien luonnetta: kaikkea ei voi hallita, mutta voi oppia elämään ja luomaan mukana. Loitsutulissa puukortit ja mehiläisvahavärit toimivat luontosuhteen vahvistajana."
-Taiteilija Minna Kovero, sähköpostiviesti Huhmarniemelle

kuva 4: Yksityiskohta *Loitsutulet*-työpajan mehiläisvärimaalauksesta. Kuva: Minna Kovero, 2020.

Taideperustaisen toimintatutkimuksen muutoshakuinen tiedontarve

Kuva 5: Tuohityön tekeminen. Kuva: Tatiana Kravtsov, 2020.

"Mieleeni jäi, että yksi osallistuja sanoi rakastuvansa koivun tuoheen. Toinen totesi, että hänestä tuntuu, kuin hänen venäläiset esi-isänsä auttaisivat häntä tässä perinnekäsityössä. Tämä oli kiinnostavaa yhteisöllisyyden näkökulmasta."

-Maria Huhmarniemi, Kravtsoville kerrottu työpajan osallistumisen reflektio

Taidekasvatuksen ja taiteen aloilla on tiedontarvetta, joka liittyy ratkaisujen hakemiseen, kestävän kehityksen edistämiseen ja nyky-yhteiskunnan haasteisiin vastaamiseen. Taideperustainen toimintatutkimus on tutkimusstrategia, joka nousee muutoshakuisesta tiedontarpeesta (Jokela, 2019; Jokela & Huhmarniemi, 2020b). Lähestymistavan tyypillisenä tavoitteena on kehittää taidepedagogiikkaa ja dialogista nykytaidetta, kuten myös tässä tutkimuksessani.

Taideperustaiset toimintatutkimuksen juuret ovat taideperustaisessa ja taiteellisessa tutkimuksessa sekä toimintatutkimuksessa (Huhmarniemi, 2016). Näissä tutkimusstrategioissa korostetaan reflektiivisyyttä, ratkaisukeskeisyyttä ja toimivan teorian kehittämistä. Taideperustainen toimintatutkimus on saanut vaikutteita myös yhteisötaiteen teorioista ja toimintatavoista, joissa tavoitteena on vaikuttaminen luomalla vuorovaikutustilanteita taiteen keinoin (Hiltunen, 2009). Taideperustainen toimintatutkimus etenee syklisesti sisältäen suunnittelun, toiminnan ja arvioinnin vaiheita. Arviointi on usein yhdistelmä itsereflektiivisyyttä sekä dokumenttien analysointia ja rinnastamista muihin teoksiin ja tutkimuksiin.

Taideperustaisessa toimintatutkimuksessa prosessiin sisältyvät ja lopputuloksena esitetyt produktiot dokumentoidaan tutkimusaineistoksi (Huhmarniemi & Jokela, 2020b). Tässä esseessä arviointini on reflektiivistä ja aineistona on kehittämistutkimuksessa syntyneitä produktioita: teoksia, jotka pyrkivät synnyttämään muutosta visuaalis-esteettisesti kiehtoen, moniaistisesti havahduttaen ja arvokeskustelua ja pohdintaa herättäen. Produktiot ovat siis muutokseen pyrkivän tutkimuksen interventioita.

Reflektioni kohdistuu teosten arviointiin yhteisöllisyyden ja empatian laajentamisessa: ei taiteilija-tutkijan omaan rooliin ja oman toiminnan ymmärtämiseen. Taiteilijoiden ja osallistujien reflektioiden otteet ovat sähköpostiviesteistä ja ne on julkaistu henkilöiden luvalla. Taideperustaista toimintatutkimusta tehdään erilaisissa ryhmissä, joissa on jäseninä taiteilijoita ja tutkijoita eri tieteenaloilta, tai vielä laajemmissa verkostoissa erilaisten ryhmien, organisaatioiden, taidetapahtumien ja kehittämishankkeiden välissä. Moninaisista yhteistyömuodoista haetaan sekä käytännön toiminnan resurssija että vaikuttavuutta tutkimusprosessin ja tulosten laajetessa verkostomaisesti. Tässä visuaalisessa esseessä käsittelemissäni produktioissa taiteilijat ovat osallistuneet toistensa toteuttamiin osallistaviin teoksiin, reflektoineet kokemuksiaan vuorovaiutuksessa muiden taiteilijoiden ja tutkijoiden kanssa ja aloittaneet uusia kanssataiteilijuuksia.

Kuva 6. Tatiana Kravtsov esittelee tuohta materiaalina. Kuva: Elina Härkönen, 2020.

Puiden ja revontulten kohtaamisia

Taiteilija-tutkija Tatiana Kravtsov työskenteli Taideperustaisia palveluja matkailuun hankkeessa suunnitellen ja kokeillen tuohityöpajaa kesämatkailupalveluna (Kravtsov ym., tulossa). Työpajassa käytettiin materiaalina koivun tuota ja tekniikkana perinteistä tuohityötä (kuvat 3 & 5–7). Työpaja koostui Kravtsovin alustuksesta tuoheen materiaalina ja tuohitöiden perinteisiin. Sen jälkeen Kravtsov opetti osallistujaryhmälle, miten tuohesta voi tehdä nykyaikaisen rannekorun. Kehittämistutkimuksessa Kravtsov kokeili työpajaa kaksi kertaa osallistujaryhmille, joissa oli mukana paikallisia rovaniemeläisiä ja taustaltaan ulkomaalaisia (Kravtsov ym., tulossa). Keskustelut työpajan osallistujien kanssa sisälsivät työpajan reflektointia ja niiden nauhoitteet toimivat tutkimusaineistona, jonka avulla on arvioitu työpajan toimivuutta (Kravtsov ym., tulossa).

Kuva 7: Tuohityöpajan kokeilu puistossa. Kuva: Tatiana Kravtsov, 2020.

Yksi taiteilijoista työsti puun kohtaamisen ohjeeksi harjoituksen, jota toinen taiteilija oli aiemmin käyttänyt yhteisötaiteen menetelmänä. "Mie käytän tätä harjoitusta, se oli mulla niin voimakas kokemus, että haluan jakaa sen." - viesti Huhmarniemelle.

Kohtaa puu on osallistava installaatio, jonka tavoitteena on elvyttää ihmisten puusuhteita (kuvat 8–9). Taiteilijana on Huhmarniemi yhteistyössä muutamien ISEAS 2020 -symposiumiin osallistuneiden taiteilijoiden kanssa. Teoksen taustalla oli Powers of Nature yhteisötaidetyöpaja, jonka Huhmarniemi, Francis Joy, Hugo Peña ja Smaranda Moldovan toteuttivat laajentaakseen yhteisöllisyyden kokemusta ihmistä luonnonelementteihin ja -henkiin. Toisaalta taustalla vaikutti myös rovaniemeläinen Puiden ystävät -yhteisö, johon kuuluu useita taiteilijoita, ja jonka tarkoituksensa on lisätä puiden arvostusta Rovaniemellä. Kanssataiteilijat olivat yhteisötaidetyöpajan toteuttajia ja osallistujia ja he kirjoittivat teoksen puiden kohtaamisen ohjeita. Huhmarniemen roolina oli teoskonseptin ideointi, taiteellis-esteettinen suunnittelu ja toteuttaminen. Teos osallistaa näyttelyyleisöä siten, että se sisältää puiden kohtaamisten harjoitteiden ohjeita. Teos koostuu seinäkollaasista, jaettavista korteista sekä Instagram-tilistä. Korteissa ja Instagramissa on ohjeita puiden kohtaamiseen monilla eri kielillä. Teoskonseptin lähtökohtana oli taide- ja ympäristökasvatusajattelu empaattisten ja vuorovaikutteisten luontosuhteiden vahvistamisessa sekä osallistujien johdattaminen yhteisöllisyyden kokemukseen puiden ja luonnon henkien kanssa. Sen ajankohtaisuus liittyi koronapandemiaan, ihmisten välisten kohtaamisten rajoittamiseen sekä metsän hengellisen luontokokemuksen merkitykseen luotokadon torjumisen yhtenä perusteena (Huhmarniemi, 2021a).

Kuva 8–9: Maria Huhmarniemi ja kanssataiteilijat Francis Joy, Misha del Val, Hugo Peña, Amir Abdi, Tanja Koistinen, Raisa Raekallio ja Smaranda Moldovan. *Kohtaa puu*, 2021, osallistava installaatio (kuvakollaasi seinällä, jaettavat kortit, instagram @encounteratree), 1782 mm X 5940 mm. Teos ISEAS: Keskustelu -näyttelyssä. Kuva: Marko Junttila, 2021.

Loitusutulet – Language of Auroras on taiteilija-muotoilija Minna Koveron kehittämä ja konseptoitu teoskokonaisuus luovan matkailun palveluksi. Teos johdattaa osallistujat, kuten matkailijaryhmät, revontulikokemukseen. Palvelu koostuu tanssi- ja musiikkiesityksestä, joka representoi revontulten vaiheita ja ”tanssia” taivaalla (kuvat 1 & 10), taiteilijoiden ja yleisön välisestä keskustelusta sekä työpajasta, jossa osallistujat sulattavat mehiläisvahaväriä puukortteille revontulikuvikseen (kuvat 4 & 11). Palvelun pilotit on dokumentoitu videoiksi, joita on käytetty arvioinnin aineistona ja kehittämisen työkaluna. Keskusteluissa osallistuvan yleisön kanssa on noussut esiin, että palvelukokonaisuus on hyvin moniaistinen sisältäen musiikin, esiintymisasut, liikkeitä ja tuoksutkin. Kovero on kehittänyt *Loitusutulet*-kokonaisuuden Maisemapiiri-työryhmän kanssa. Työryhmään kuuluvat Koveron lisäksi kuvataiteilija Eliina Hurtig, tanssija Pia Lindfors ja viulun soittaja Anniina Poikela (kuva 2).

Kuva 10: *Loitusutulet*. Kuva: Minna Kovero, 2021.

Kuva 11:
Loitusutulet-työpaja.
Kuva: Tatiana
Kravtsov, 2020.

Tuohi ja mehiläisvahavärit sekä yhteisöllisyyden ja puun kohtaamisen teemat yhtyivät *Luopuu*-teoksessa, jonka taiteilijat Minna Kovero ja Niina Oinas toteuttivat *Kumma Puutarha* -ympäristötaidenäyttelyyn Rovaniemellä kesällä 2021. Taiteilijat ohjasivat taidetyöpajoja, joissa osallistujat maalasivat mehiläisvahaväreillä tuohelle. Osallistujaryhminä olivat ikäihmisten ryhmä sekä avoin taidetyöpaja, johon kuka vain sai osallistua. Teoksen nimi, *Luopuu*, assosioi luovuuteen, puuhun ja luopumiseen. Osallistuminen oli merkityksellistä lisääntyneen yksinäisyyden aikakaudella. Samalla keskusteluissa mahdollistui yksinäisyyden kokemuksen jakaminen keskustellen.

- "Erityisesti avoimissa työpajoissa korostui koronan aiheuttamat yksinäisyyden tunteet, kohtaamisen ilo ja taiteellisen heittäytymisen tuoma vapautuminen."
- taiteilija Niina Oinas, sähköpostiviesti Huhmarniemelle

Kuva 12–13. Minna Kovero ja Niina Oinas (2021). *Luopuu*. Tuohi, mehiläisvahavärit ja tervanaru. *Kumma puutarha* -ympäristötaidetapahtuma, Rovaniemi. Kuva: Maria Huhmarniemi

Arviointi: miten produktiot toimivat?

Tuohityöpajan, *Loitsutulien*, *Kohtaa puu* -installaation ja *Luopuun* taustalla on hyvin käytännöllinen yhteisöllisyyden laajentamisen ja luontosuhteiden syventämisen tavoite. Näissä kaikissa neljässä produktiossa yhteisöllisyys on tarkoittanut sekä ihmisten välisyyttä että luontoyhteyttä. *Tuohityöpaja* ja *Loitsutulet* synnyttivät dialogia paikallisten ja matkailijoiden välille työpajoihin sisältyneissä keskusteluissa. *Kohtaa puu* -teoksessa välinen yhteisöllisyys toteutui taiteilijaryhmän yhteistyönä ja *Luopuu*-teoksessa kahden taiteilijan ja osallistujaryhmien yhteisöllisyytenä. Kaikki teokset olivat yhteisöllisyydeltään siinä mielessä inklusiivia, että ne olivat monikielisiä ja niissä ohjattiin osallistujia sanattomaan, keholliseen ja moniaistiseen vuorovaikutukseen. Siten kielitaidottomuus ei muodostunut yhteisöllisyyden kokemuksen esteeksi matkailupalveluissa ja taidenäyttely-yhteisössä. Esimerkiksi *Kohtaa puu* -teoksessa on ohjeita kuudellatoista kielellä (kuvat 14 & 15). Inklusiivisuus toteutui produktioissa myös siten, ettei osallistuminen edellyttänyt erityistä taiteen tuntemista tai teknisiä taitoja.

Empatiaan liittyy kyky omaksua toisen näkökulma: luoda emotionaalinen side toisen kanssa (Brown ym., 2019). Kun haluaa olla empaattinen, on hankittava kokemuksia, jotka synnyttävät toveruuden tunteita (Peloquin, 1996). Yhteisöllisessä taiteen tekemisessä näitä toveruuden kokemuksia voi syntyä vuorovaikutuksen, keskustelujen ja yhdessä tekemisen myötä ihmisten välille. Mutta miten empaattisuutta voi laajentaa taiteen kautta ei-inhimilliseen luontoon Keton (2018) tarkoittamalla tavalla? Peloquin (1996) mukaan moniaistisuus on välttämätöntä empatian kokemiseksi. *Tuohityöpajassa* ja *Loitsutulissa* moniaistisuus toteutui muun muassa materiaalien tunnun, tuoksujen ja visuaalisuuden kautta. Tuohityöpajasta kootun aineiston analysointi onkin osoittanut, että osallistujien empaattinen suhde puihin lisääntyi työpajan aikana (Kratvsov ym., tulossa). *Kohtaa puu* -teoksesta ja *Loitsutulet*-esityksestä ja työpajasta ei kuitenkaan ole vastaavaa aineistoa koottuna osallistumisen transformatiivisuuden näkökulmasta. Produktiot kuitenkin esittävät ja välittävät sensitiivisiä ja empaattisia luontosuhteita sekä lappilaista luontokulttuurin nyky-yhteiskuntaan.

Kuva 14: Yksityiskohta *Kohtaa puu* -teoksesta. (Maria Huhmarniemi ja kanssataiteilijat Francis Joy, Misha del Val, Hugo Peña, Amir Abdi, Tanja Koistinen, Raisa Raekallio ja Smaranda Moldovan, 2021). Kuva: Maria Huhmarniemi.

Nikolić ja Skinner (2019) ovat tarkastelleet posthumanistisen ja uusmaterialistisen yhteisöllisyyden laajenemista ekologisesti ja yhteisöllisesti orientoituneessa taiteessa, kuratoinnissa ja aktivismissa. Heidän mukaansa posthumanistisen taiteen ydinkysymys ei ole tuottaa uutta yhteisöä, vaan pitää huolta toiseudesta, joka on aina kuulunut yhteisöön. Tämän välittämisen, huolenpidon ja inklusiivisuuden ei tulisi rajautua tiede- ja taidemaailmaan (Nikolić ja Skinner, 2019). Kun taideperustaisia esityksiä ja työpajoja kehitetään taide- ja tiedeyliopistossa ja toteutetaan matkailualan kontekstissa, tiede- ja taidemaailman ylittämistä tapahtuu luontevasti. Arkeen posthumanistinen yhteisöllisyys voi laajeta, kun taitetyöpaja toteutuu esimerkiksi ikäihmisten palvelukodissa ja esitetään kaupunkipuistossa, kuten *Luopuu*-teoksessa. Myös sosiaalinen media siirtää nykytaiteen kohtaamista taidemaailmasta keskelle elämää, kuten *Kohtaa puu* -teoksen Instagram-julkaisuissa.

Taideperustaisen tutkimuksen arvioinnista ja validoinnista on paljon keskustelu tutkimuskirjallisuudessa (Barone & Eisner, 2012; McNiff, 2013; Siegesmund & Cahnmann-Taylor, 2008). McNiff (2013) ehdottaa mahdolliseksi arviointikriteereiksi tutkimuksen transformatiivisuuden, visionäärisuuden ja taiteellisen haasteellisuuden. Transformatiivisuutta voinee arvioida vain osallistujien kokemusta välittävistä aneistoista, kuten keskustelujen dokumentoinneista. Visionäärisuutta ja taiteellisen haasteellisuutta on puolestaan vaikea määrittää. Tässä esseessä käsittelemäni produktiot ovat kuitenkin Suomen Lapin kuvataidekentässä sekä luovan matkailun kontekstissa soveltavan taiteen ja nykytaiteen alaa kehittäviä. Tämä ilmenee muun muassa jatkuvasti uudelleen organisoituvina taiteilijoiden työryhminä ja yhteisömuotoina, joissa taiteilijat kehittävät ilmaisuaan ja työtapojaan yhteistyössä toisensa ja osallistuvien yhteisöjen kanssa. Taide sosiaalisena väistökseenä näyttäytyykin tarkastelemissani produktiossa taiteilijoiden ja laajenevien yhteisöjen luovina ja oppivina verkostoina. Oppiminen kohdistuu sekä yhteisöllisyyden eri muotoihin, että luonnosta saatujen materiaalien käyttöön. Esimerkiksi tuohi ja mehiläisvahavärit on omaksuttu taiteilijoilta toisille ja kiinnostunut puusuhteeseen ilmenee useissa teoksissa. Produktiot ovat oppimisprosesseja sekä tekijöille että osallistuville yksilöille ja yhteisöille kuten taideperustaisessa toimintatutkimuksessa yleensä (Jokela & Huhmarniemi, 2020b).

Taiteellinen haasteellisuus tuohityöpajassa, *Loitsutulissa*, *Kohtaa puu*, ja *Luopuu* -teoksissa liittyy Yliriskun (2021) peräänkuuluttamaan ei-inhimillisten toimijuuksien tunnistamiseen ja uudenlaisen yhteisöllisyyden repsentoimiseen ja välittämiseen taiteen keinoin. Tätä haastetta ei mielestäni ole vielä riittävästi vastattu: empatian ja yhteisön laajentamiseen taiteessa on edelleen kasvava tarve.

Kuva 15: Yksityiskohta *Kohtaa puu* -teoksesta. (Maria Huhmarniemi ja kanssataiteilijat Francis Joy, Misha del Val, Hugo Peña, Amir Abdi, Tanja Koistinen, Raisa Raekallio ja Smaranda Moldovan, 2021). Kuva: Maria Huhmarniemi.

Johtopäätökset

Posthumanistinen filosofia, joka suuntaa yhteisökäsitystä luontosuhteiden verkostoksi, vaikuttaa luovan matkailun kehittämiseen, taidekasvatukseen ja nykytaiteeseen. Yhteisön laajentaminen ei-inhimilliseen luontoon on tavoite ja tulos produktioissa, joita on toteutettu taiteen-, kulttuurin ja luovan matkailun konteksteissa Lapissa. Yhteisöllisyyden voi kokea laajenevaksi sensitiivisissä, empaattisissa ja moniaistisissa kohtaamisissa ihmisten ja muun luonnon välillä. Vuorovaikutuksen kehollisuus, visuaalisuus ja monikielisyys mahdollistavat syntyvän yhteisöllisyyden avoimuutta ja inklusiivisuutta. Samalla taiteilijoiden välinen yhteistyö lisääntyy synnyttäen kollektiiveja, työryhmiä ja erilaisia kanssataiteilijuuksien muotoja, jotka sulauttavat tekijyyttä, osallistumista ja taiteen kokemista. Taide sosiaalisena veistoksena sisältää myös taiteilijoiden yhteistyön monimuotoisuuden. Posthumanistinen yhteisöllinen taide vastaakin monin tavoin yksinäisyyden haasteeseen, mutta edelleen kehittämistyölle, tutkimukselle ja taideperustaisten menetelmien käyttöönotolle on tarvetta.

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Slow Pace Communication: An Approach for Community Building

Angela Saldanha, Teresa Torres de Eça,
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GriArCE - APECV Research Centre in Arts Education and Community

Biography

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Abstract

This visual essay portrays the first phase of a communication experience via postcards with participants from Portugal of the project "AMASS: Acting on the Margins: Arts as Social Sculpture", under the social distance restrictions of the Covid19 pandemic situation, between January and June 2021. The experience is described and discussed in terms of the dynamics created, the methodologies of the research group and possibilities of the strategy to overcome the limitations of digital communication in disadvantaged communities and arts based projects.

Keywords

**Communication, participatory research, socially engaged arts,
arts based projects**

Figure 1: Postcard, Photograph by Raquel Balsa, 2021.

Figure 2: Postcards, Photograph by Raquel Balsa, 2021.

Figure 3: Postcard, Photograph by Teresa Eça, 2021.

Introduction

The need to overcome the difficulties of contact, due to the COVID 19 pandemic, with the groups participating in the AMASS project lead the GrIArCe research group to look for strategies to get in touch with all the participants: caregivers; artists; designers; researchers; people with multiple disabilities, aged between 18 and 60 years and a Roma community located in Viseu, where it is difficult to enter without prior consent, with children aged between 5 and 12 and adults.

The images that we can see throughout the essay are the result of the exchange carried out between the researchers and the participating groups.

GrIArCE - who we are?

We are members of an independent action research group, called GrIArCE, Research Group on Arts Community and Education, working under the umbrella of the Portuguese Association of Visual Expression and Communication APECV. We are engaged in transformative practices through art education activism and strategies based on pedagogy of hope (Freire, 1992). Normally we work with transdisciplinary teams including educators; teacher artists and artists; social workers and other volunteers interested in bringing art activities to communities from disadvantaged groups. We create the art activities in collaboration with the stakeholders in the communities, and participants from the groups trying to reply to their leisure and educational requests. For us this process is the core of the art education activism.

We don't bring elaborated plans or art programs to the communities, we offer our services to learn with the members of the group through artistic activities aiming mutual understanding, dialogue and civic participation.

Figure 4: Postcard, Photograph by Raquel Balsa, 2021.

AMASS - what are the project goals?

Within the scope of the AMASS International Project "AMASS: Acting on the Margins: Arts as Social Sculpture", funded by the European Union's research and innovation program Horizon 2020 (agreement no. 870621), APECV research group initiated conversations to make collaborative art education activities with five different groups of people including adults and children socially disadvantaged from three regions in Portugal during the Pandemic Covid-19 social distance restrictions. We will describe here the beginning of our work with three of these groups: volunteer adults from two day care centre for people with mental disabilities and another group of volunteer children and adolescents from a Roma community.

AMASS research project is coordinated by the University of Lapland (Finland) and has partners with Karlova University (Czech Republic), University of Malta, Hogskolan i Boras University (Sweden), Corvinus Egyetem University (Hungary), PACO Design (Italy) and Leeds University (England) and APECV. This project seeks to investigate the role of the arts in society's challenges, especially from places located on the margins and aims to promote and investigate transformative actions from the arts with minority or disadvantaged groups from marginalized places in Europe.

Our volunteers were involved in the project by a call launched by us and our collaborators working in social institutions where people living in marginalized situations use to spend leisure time in educational activities. To initiate the conversation processes with our groups, we had to think in alternative communication strategies, avoiding internet communication for two main reasons:

1. the first one- **Equity**- Some participants were able to use cellphones and have access to internet, some others didn't have access to that technology.
2. the second reason- **Trust**, this was related to our vision of communication, a shared relationship between people, where more than passing a message, we can transmit feelings, emotions and care.

In that period caring was crucial for all the groups involved, they were feeling even more marginalized with the lockdown of social institutions where they normally used to have leisure and educational activities, which were closed for visitors. For the APECV team, it was also crucial to start the conversations with the participants by giving and receiving precious things to establish the necessary trust between APECV team, and the other participants.

So we thought to propose to make postcards designed to be sent by post services overcoming barriers of isolation and dematerialization. We discussed the ideas with caregivers from the solidarity institutions, with whom we use to work. They said it could be a good idea, even for those who couldn't write, they would love to receive a postcard or a letter, and they could reply with the help of the caregivers.

Figure 5: Postcards in progress, Photograph by Raquel Balsa, 2021.

Figure 6: Postcard, Photograph by Teresa Eça, 2021.

Our methodology

We usually work on a basis of collaborative construction, with methodologies related to walking pedagogy and pedagogy of hope (Freire, 1992). Through arts based methods we relate places and look for the potential of everyday life' psycho geographical situations (Sansi, 2015; Coverly, 2010). Inspired in the situationists' ideas -to make people recover the control of their own lives, to produce knowledge through aesthetic relationships (Bourriaud, 2019), to create collaboration through artistic tools to question, to dialogue, "to live among" we usually combine different bodies of Action (outside and inside) and different media rich in metaphors such as images, texts and sounds –in practices of drift, deambulation and detour (Visconti, 2014: p.VIII). We borrowed these artistic practices from contemporary art, that were largely conceptualized by artists and collectives in the second half of the twenty century as for example Joseph Beuys, John Cage or the Fluxus Movement (Bishop, 2012).

But in the lockdown situation it was impossible to use such practices in our project. Nevertheless, we kept the idea of travelling and distance to connect to the “other”, as a social transformation regaining alternative forms of communication. In our activism ethos it was not only a matter of social activity but also a symbolic one claiming for a slow pace of life and alternative ways of living together.

Our group is also inspired in the artistic action within an interdisciplinary character, linked to the possibilities of education through arts as a possibility for social change as a gift, for a common good, among all stakeholders, in a democratic participation, without power hierarchies and where the “I” learns from the “You” in action for an “Other” who can trigger other actions.

“The art-community correlation is a way of looking, it’s a way of understanding, it’s a way of problematizing. (...) The art-community correlation, however, goes far beyond a simple channel with a transmitter and receiver. We are in the domain of interaction, game, project, collective manifestation, commitment, enthusiasm, risk, delivery, mutual growth” (Xavier, in Cruz, 2016: Opening Note)

Figure 7: Postcard in progress, Photograph by Teresa Eça, 2021.

12/4/2021

Amiga a primavera
nunca move quando
há pessoas como
você
Gostei de ~~conhe~~ conhecê-la

você
me escreva sempre
você ganhou o
meu coração

GARCIA PEREIRA
VERA LÚCIA

Figure 8: Postcard, Photograph by Raquel Balsa, 2021.

Handwriting letters and postcards: slow pace is important to construct relationships

In our group (GrIArCE) we discussed the issue of handwritten words. Returning to calligraphy, to tell that time and slow pace are important to construct relationships. For us, artists, designers, teachers-artists it was an artistic action. The time to pick the paper, to feel its texture, the time to pick the pen, feel its shape, the ink flowing, enjoy the lines before the words; contemplate the words after the lines (figures 1-8). The written text may not be the most important in the action, but the process of handwriting in itself, in that sense we see the handwriting as a tool for action in the real world shifting the focus from what art says to what art does.

“If we look at artworks as devices for action, we can take a different perspective; we are not just interested in the origin of the artwork, but also in its effects – in particular, how they constitute social relations and agents.” (Sansi, 2015, p.65)

Figure 9: Postcards, Photograph by Ângela Saldanha, 2021.

The Action: Analog contact in times of physical distance

Materiality assumes an affective importance of anchoring in periods of isolation - a time when sensory stimuli are less diverse and the virtualization of days contributes to fragmentation and disorientation - valuing this fantastic medium that is the body, through it we have the perception of things, we communicate and express what goes on in our mind.

In a time of absence of physical contact, we embraced embodied messages of past communication technologies. Instead of the instantaneous digital communication, we chose the difficulties of writing by hand, drawing, putting in an envelope, add a stamp, a physical address, and going to the post office, evoking the physical distances of the travelling, handing it over to the other for the trip that takes us to the other's home: so, he or she can hold us in hands and read and feel the texture and messages of each stroke of the pen. A message with a body! (figures 9-12)

Thus, we tried to explore ways to discover the person, the others, the spaces, the places and the relationships between them through the ritual of emotional writing of a letter or a postcard, made with love by drawing; collage or photography. The postcard designed to be exchanged with the group and with each person: telling to the other the particularities of our day, our preferred places and food; , positive memories, and a last sentence for our dreams of a possible encounter in person as soon as the situation would permit it.

This communication media would be equitable, without leaving anyone behind.

Figure 10: Postcard, Photograph by Raquel Balsa, 2021

Considerations and future

For us, all, this experience has been a transformative educational strategy: celebrating the time to feel the great small things that make our connections so beautiful and valuable!

Although these letters and postcards action experimented with participants from these groups of Portuguese participants in the AMASS project may seem a mail art action, we understand it not solely as mail art, but something else. Mail Art, in the world of visual art, was a procedure used by artists such as Ray Johnson and members of the Fluxus movement, it was very popular in the art galleries in the sixties and seventies of the twenty century, as a subversive way of exposing art works¹. As in the series of drawings of letters over envelopes by Portuguese artist Manuel Alvess², which has been inspirational for our work in this action. Currently there are still calls for mail art exhibitions³. In our experiment, our goal was far away from exposing or trading artworks, we just wanted to use a communication technology that could encapsulate the concept of sharing and caring, giving our precious time to the others to ask them if they wanted to collaborate with us in artistic actions.

¹ As described in <https://news.artnet.com/art-world/mail-art-renaissance-1850670>

² See here Envoi postal by Manuel Alvess, 1969: https://artsandculture.google.com/asset/envoi-postal-alvess-manuel/MwGLNWg3IH9Q_g

³ For exemple: <https://mailart.pt>

Conclusions

Inviting participants to integrate artistic actions, is not always a straightforward process; in our experience, of working with disadvantaged groups, people will enroll, if they want to collaborate, and if they feel they are loved or if they feel that during that action there is a possibility to learn something new; to spend a playful time and to make new friends. This encounter with others, is also one of the main objectives of AMASS project to challenge the margins and the visibility of the voices of people in the margins.

The materiality of epistolary means, despite the absence of the body, conjures the other, intimately. Evoked in the calligraphy, strokes and in the ritual gestures of addressing and sending the postcard. We can see and feel the other when we reveal the message, we physically open it and it unfolds for us in a present moment. The message happens, to me, at that moment. What is handmade imbues the artifact of us. What is done for the other is fulfilled with him. This correspondence places us at the center of the ritual, in the space between one body and another —material and evoked— between one space and another, physical and performative.

The experiment is not closed and will continue now with participants of AMASS project from the other countries, we will explore it also as a connecting artistic communication tool between partners, ensuring the ethical issues and respecting intercultural dialogues. May be it will be useful also for the variety of different types of supporting documentation, return and dissemination of the AMASS international research project.

In this first stage, we can conclude that the action in Portugal enabled

- communication between participants from APECV and the participants from the groups.
- use of tools, techniques, methodologies and strategies of contemporary art to achieve knowledge about the participants life experiences and expectations.

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Figure 11: Postcard with the author; Photograph by Teresa Eça, 2021.

Figure 12: Postcard, Photograph by Teresa Eça, 2021.

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